

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

Proceedings of the
International Conference

Date:
February 11

Beijing, China 2026

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化
国际会议

参与者的英文报告

International Conference
“Scientific research of the SCO
countries: synergy and integration”

Part 1

2026年02月11日，中华人民共和国北京
FEBRUARY 11, 2026. BEIJING, PRC

Proceedings of the International Science Conference
**“Scientific research of the SCO countries: synergy and
integration”** - Reports in English

(February 11, 2026. Beijing, PRC)

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.32.91.034

这些会议文集结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

作者对所引用的出版物，事实，数字，引用，统计数据，专有名称和其他信息的准确性负责

These Conference Proceedings combine materials of the conference – research papers and thesis reports of scientific workers. They examine technical, juridical and sociological aspects of research issues. Some articles deal with theoretical and methodological approaches and principles of research questions of personality professionalization.

Authors are responsible for the accuracy of cited publications, facts, figures, quotations, statistics, proper names and other information.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.32.91.034

©Scientific publishing house
Infinity, 2026

©Group of authors, 2026

CONTENTS

PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

- 基于四面体（类似佛像）粒子的光子钩，该粒子具有刻意打破的空间对称性
Photonic hook based on a four-faced (Buddha-like) particle with deliberately broken spatial symmetry
Minin Oleg Vladilenovich, Minin Igor Vladilenovich9

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

- 蒜氨酸酶对GC-MS法测定大蒜中噻唑啉酮残留量基质效应的影响
The influence of the enzyme allinase on matrix effects in the determination of residual amounts of fosthiazate in garlic by GC-MS
Egorchenkova Olga Evgenievna, Kurpedinov Kirill Sergeevich16

EARTH SCIENCES

- 运用水生生态系统替代稳定状态原理来应对蓝藻污染
Implementation of the principle of an alternative stable state of aquatic ecosystems to counteract cyanobacterial pollution
Pozdnyakova Albina Iskandarovna24

GEOLOGICAL AND MINERALOGICAL SCIENCES

- 南萨哈林岛中新世卢西诺玛属（*Lucinoma* Dall）海生双壳类软体动物及其地层学意义
Sea bivalve mollusks of the genus *Lucinoma* Dall from the miocene of South Sakhalin and their stratigraphic significance
Khudik Vladimir Dmitrievich30

MEDICAL SCIENCES

- 开发和评估针对冠状病毒感染患者的龋齿预防措施的有效性
Development and evaluation of the effectiveness of caries prevention in patients who have had coronavirus infection
Belenova Irina Alexandrovna, Tikhonovskaya Karina Sergeevna, Popova Olesya Borisovna, Primacheva Natalia Vladimirovna, Fisenko Sofia Vladimirovna38

固定矫形结构修复问题的最新进展 Current aspects of the problem of fixing fixed orthopedic structures <i>Andreeva Svetlana Nikolaevna, Iatsenko Kirill Evgenievich, Ishkhan Sergeevich Khumoyan, Mikhail Mikhailovich Andreev</i>	43
严重合并创伤性脑损伤患儿的平均动脉压昼夜节律 Circadian rhythm of mean arterial pressure in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury <i>Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna, Dadabayeva Erkinoy Isakjanovna, Fathulayeva Dildora Murojon kizi</i>	49
对重度合并创伤性脑损伤儿童的卒中量昼夜节律进行比较评估 Comparative assessment of the circadian rhythm of stroke volume in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury <i>Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna, Nasimov Sobir Tahirovich.</i>	59
莫斯科中心区综合诊所患者就诊路线的有效性 The effectiveness of patient routes in polyclinics in the Central District of Moscow <i>Karimova Daniia Yusufovna, Belkina Valeriia Alekseevna, Utkin Aleksandr Vladimirovich.</i>	68
多价噬菌体在预防紧急腹腔内手术感染中的作用 The role of polyvalent bacteriophage in the prevention of surgical infections during emergency intra-abdominal interventions <i>Parshin Dmitry Sergeevich, Topchiev Mikhail Andreevich, Melnikov Vladimir Vitalievich, Mikhailichenko Vyacheslav Yurievich.</i>	73
脑动脉和脑动脉瘤的结构变异 Variants of the structure of cerebral arteries and cerebral aneurysms <i>Gorbunov Alexey Viktorovich, Khvorova Angelina Nikolaevna, Parshin Dmitry Sergeevich, Mikhailichenko Vyacheslav Yurievich</i>	83
现代牙科中颈部侵蚀旋转预备的优化：一种“微创治疗非龋性病变” 的创新方案 Optimization of Rotary Preparation for Cervical Erosions in Modern Dentistry: An Innovative Protocol “Minimally Invasive for Non-Carious Lesions” <i>Babaev Dmitrii Viktorovich.</i>	88
莫斯科地区人群血管性脑疾病死亡率和致死率特征 Features of mortality and lethality from vascular brain diseases in the Moscow region population <i>Yusipova Maryam Rustyamovna, Salakhov Ruslan Zhangirievich.</i>	96

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

土库曼斯坦植物区系中水飞蓟 (*Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn.)
的微克隆繁殖

Microclonal propagation of milk thistle (*Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn.) in the
flora of Turkmenistan

*Durdyyev Tachmyrat Shamukhammedovich, Akmuradov Allamurat,
Danatarov Batyr Govshutgeldievich. 101*

现代移动医疗应用程序与既定治疗依从性原则的符合性

Compliance of modern mobile health applications with consolidated principles
of treatment adherence

*Shestakov Maxim Sergeevich, Babaskin Dmitrii Vladimirovich,
Litvinova Tatiana Mikhailovna, Babaskina Liudmila Ivanovna. 111*

对乙酰氨基酚废弃物生物降解产物影响下金盏花生物量和产量的生长速率
Growth rates of biomass and yield of *calendula officinalis* under the influence of
paracetamol waste biodegradation product

*Gapechkina Elizaveta Dmitrievna, Vikhareva Elena Vladimirovna,
Selyaninov Alexander Anatolyevich 119*

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

浆果粉在功能性面粉糖果产品生产中的应用

The use of berry powders in the production of functional flour confectionery
products

*Tumanova Alla Evgenyevna, Drobysheva Maria Andreevna,
Lyashkova Daria Konstantinovna. 124*

在禽肉生产中使用新型饲料添加剂的合理性

Justification for the use of a new feed additive in poultry meat production

Mizhevikina Yulia Alekseevna, Mizhevikina Anna Sergeevna. 131

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

西伯利亚冷杉提取物作为食品强化功能性成分

Siberian fir extract as a functional ingredient for food fortification

*Tumanova Alla Evgenyevna, Maryasova Alisa Sergeevna,
Popov Pavel Alexandrovich 139*

测试—理论力学在线课程运动学习题

Test — problems in kinematics for online courses in theoretical mechanics

Pirogov Sergey Petrovich 148

基于结构和性能的轧制金属质量评估方法 Methodological approach to quality assessment rolled metal by structure and properties <i>Fomikhina Irina Victorovna</i>	152
机器人助手对军事行动的潜在影响 On the potential impact of robotic assistants on military operations <i>Tikhanychev Oleg Vasilyevich</i>	162
研究审查的理论过程、其机械损伤和分离大豆种子组合的两年期评估研究 Study theoretical process of review, its mechanical injuriousness and separation of soya seeds combine of the biennium assessment study <i>Prisyazhnaya Irina Mikhaelovna, Prisyazhnaya Serafima Pavlovna</i>	170
特殊类型信息收集与传输系统矩阵的分析模型 Analytical models of matrices of special types of information collection and transmission systems <i>Panov Sergei Anatolevich, Minzhesarova Sabina Aleksandrovna</i>	180
基于深度学习的道路交通标志检测与识别研究 Research on deep learning-based road traffic sign detection and recognition <i>Hajiyev Haji Fakhraddin</i>	189
所研制酸液组合对碳酸盐岩储层井底深层增产的有效性 Effectiveness of the developed acid composition for deep stimulation of the bottomhole zone in carbonate reservoirs <i>Baturin Nikita Igorevich, Fattakhov Irik Galikhanovich</i>	193

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.20.17.114

基于四面体（类似佛像）粒子的光子钩，该粒子具有刻意打破的空间对称性

**PHOTONIC HOOK BASED ON A FOUR-FACED
(BUDDHA-LIKE) PARTICLE WITH DELIBERATELY BROKEN
SPATIAL SYMMETRY**

Minin Oleg Vladilenovich

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Full Professor

Novosibirsk Branch of the Institute of Semiconductor Physics,

Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences,

“Technological Design Institute of Applied Microelectronics”

Novosibirsk, Russian Federation

Minin Igor Vladilenovich

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Full Professor

Novosibirsk Branch of the Institute of Semiconductor Physics,

Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences,

“Technological Design Institute of Applied Microelectronics”

Novosibirsk, Russian Federation

摘要：尽管自2015年以来已积累了大量文献，但被称为光子钩的现象仍然备受关注。据我们所知，本文首次证明，我们以四面佛命名的佛陀粒子，在改变同一粒子的光照方向时，可以产生不同的光子钩。

关键词：光子钩，场局域化，对称性破缺粒子，四面佛陀粒子，介观电子学。

Abstract. *Despite the substantial body of literature accumulated since 2015, the phenomenon known as the photonic hook continues to attract attention. For the first time, to our knowledge, it is demonstrated that Buddha particles — named by us after the four-faced god — can generate different photonic hooks when the illumination direction of the same particle is altered.*

Keywords: *photonic hook, field localization, particle with broken symmetry, four-faced Buddha particle, mesotronics.*

Introduction

Mesoscale Janus particles have attracted significant interest over many years due to their intriguing properties and diverse potential applications, including optical manipulation and subdiffraction imaging. The term ‘Janus particle’

(or ‘two-faced’ particle [1]), named after the two-faced Roman god Janus, was introduced into the scientific community in 1998 [2].

Microscopy based on mesoscale particles has proven to be a promising tool for surpassing the fundamental diffraction limit. Simultaneously, the low image contrast in this scenario can be addressed, for instance, by employing oblique illumination through the so-called photonic hook (PH), first discovered in 2015 [3,4]. PH is a new type of artificially generated curved localized near-field beam with a radius of curvature generally smaller than the wavelength. This is a unique near-field effect arising during the propagation of radiation through dielectric microparticles with deliberately broken symmetry, wherein a subwavelength light structure is formed combining localization, directivity, and robustness against perturbations of the particle’s shape or material structure [5]. The operating principle is based on a combination of wave interference effects and differences in phase velocities [5]. The first simplest variant of the PH was implemented based on a multifunctional mesoscale Janus particle — a combination of a wedge prism and a cuboid [3,4] (Fig. 1b). In [3,4], the photonic hook was demonstrated for the first time for directed optical transport and optical manipulation of nanoparticles along a curvilinear trajectory with a radius of curvature on the order of 0.5λ , within unusual structures sized only about $2-3\lambda$. Overall, the conducted studies of optomechanical trapping effects based on the photonic hook have demonstrated that nanoparticles with diameters of approximately 100-500 nm and a refractive index of about 1.5 can be stably trapped and moved over distances up to 2λ along curved trajectories, bypassing obstacles. Under pulsed illumination, three main types of motion of trapped particles have been identified: motion in the positive direction, where the nanoparticle is repelled from the PH generator; motion in the opposite direction, where the nanoparticle is attracted to the PH generator; and various oscillations, where the nanoparticle oscillates between or among stable points. In general, PHs enable the realization of tunable near-field optical traps suitable for manipulating individual particles without bulky classical optics. These applications are relevant to selective transport, sorting, and targeted delivery of nanoparticles in microfluidic devices and bioanalysis. In addition to nanoparticle transport, PHs are employed in optomechanical manipulations, including trapping particles along specific nonlinear trajectories, as well as in microscopy with ultrahigh resolution and contrast. On the other hand, owing to the unique property of the photonic hook to vary its curvature depending on the wavelength of the optical radiation, such a microstructure enables the realization of a new two-channel optical switch with wavelength scaling, without employing micromechanical devices or nonlinear materials [6]. The photonic hook has found applications in super-resolution microscopy, surface microstructuring tasks, and related areas [5]. The curvature, length, and bending angle of the photonic hook can be regulated by adjusting the degree of asymmetry of the particle or the incident radiation.

Problem statement

Later, the shape of Janus particles for generating photonic hooks was extended [5]. In general, photonic hook formation by particles exhibiting various forms of asymmetry — shape, refractive index, and structured illumination — has been studied in considerable detail and summarized in [5]. The photonic hook phenomenon has been experimentally demonstrated in the terahertz and optical ranges, in acoustics, and for focusing surface plasmon waves [5].

Fig. 1. Formation of a photonic hook using a combined prism+cube particle.

Initially, studies of such structures' properties were generally limited to a simple configuration [4-7] — Fig. 1a, b. At the same time, it should be noted that the potential capabilities of Janus particles based on a combination of a wedge prism and cuboid are quite extensive but remain insufficiently represented in the literature. Thus, in the aforementioned works, the particle was illuminated by a plane

wavefront incident from the wedge side (Fig. 1b). The PH was formed in the particle's shadow region along the direction of incident radiation [3-7]. In other words, the phase modulation of the illuminating wave was performed along the direction of radiation propagation. At small angles of incidence, an asymmetric phase is introduced due to the oblique incidence on such a limited-symmetry structure (in the forward direction). However, as additional studies have demonstrated, the PH is formed even when the incidence is perpendicular to the base of a limited-symmetry Janus particle (Fig. 1d). Paraphrasing L. I. Mandelstam, these additional studies became possible thanks to a "second degree of understanding," i.e., by changing the "angle of view" on known phenomena. To the best of our knowledge, this configuration was first mentioned in [5].

As in [8], in the case under consideration, the bending of the field localization region in the shadow region of the dielectric particle is caused by the interference of waves within it during phase velocity dispersion. Due to the broken-symmetry shape of the particle, the total phase of wave oscillations varies irregularly within the particle. As a result, the localized field in the shadow region of the particle is bent. The shape and curvature radius of the PH peak can be controlled by varying the wavelength, polarization of the incident light, and optical parameters of the emitting particle at a fixed morphology.

Results. In the considered particle with deliberately broken spatial symmetry, the left and right halves of the particle (Fig. 2) have different thicknesses along the radiation propagation direction. This results in a phase difference of the plane wave passing through the particle, inducing a concave deformation of the wavefront inside the particle, which leads to the formation of the photonic hook. As the angle θ increases (inset of Fig. 1), the symmetry of the flow is broken, and the flow begins to tilt toward the longer side of the asymmetric particle, leading to an increase in the photonic hook tilt angle α .

A comparison of the configurations in Fig. 1b and Fig. 1d demonstrates that the photonic hook bends in different directions relative to the radiation propagation direction. However, in all cases, the bending direction is toward the side opposite the apex of the prism. This is explained by the arrangement of optical vortices within the considered particle (Fig. 2). As a result of light interference near singular points with zero Poynting vector within the considered structure, energy vortex singularities are formed [8-11], which, in particular, demonstrates the inadequacy of traditional geometrical optics at this scale. The structure and properties of optical vortices and the initial configuration of the particle (Fig. 1b) were analyzed in detail in [12].

Interference caused by variations in particle thickness across the propagation direction of the incident plane wave generates several singular points near the shadow surface of the larger base of the asymmetric particle. Thus, as seen in Fig.

2, two optical vortices are formed, which divide the optical flow into two parts, whose interference results in the formation of the photonic hook at the exit from the shadow region of the particle. The intensity peak of the PH fully corresponds to the distribution of power flows in the shadow region of the particle.

Figure 2. Formation of the photonic hook upon illumination from the small base side of the particle and the structure of vortex fields inside the particle. 1,2 — subwavelength optical vortices with a diameter on the order of 0.1λ .

The table lists the main comparative characteristics of the photonic hook generated by the considered particle.

Particle configuration	FWHM, λ	α , degrees	Max($ E/E_0 ^2$)
Fig.1b	0.44	25	12.9
Fig.1d	0.37	28	11

Conclusion

Thus, the configuration of the considered particle, representing a combination of a dielectric prism and cuboid, similarly to [2], can be regarded as a four-faced “Buddha-like” (named by us after the Thai four-faced Buddha deity in Macau) [13] particle (see Fig.1 a, b and Fig.1 c, d). Note that in Hinduism, the god Muraling has more than one face, usually up to five [14]. Therefore, it is possible to form a stable photonic hook by properly selecting the orientation of the four-faced ‘Buddha-like’ particle relative to the direction of the incident radiation.

The four-faced ‘Buddha-like’ particle can focus light into a stable photonic hook in two orientations. As studies have shown, the new configuration for PH

formation resolves the issue of particle placement on a substrate [15]. The concept of the photonic hook enables precise control over particle motion for manipulating and sorting cells on «lab-on-a-chip» platforms, for in vitro applications — selectively directing cells along a curved trajectory for their subsequent differentiation [16], as well as for transporting nano-objects in intercellular or intracellular environments along a bent path, delivering nanomedicines across central nervous system barriers, nanostructuring surfaces [17,18], microscopy, novel photonic devices in mesotronics, and other areas.

At intermediate spatial orientations relative to the incident radiation direction, the considered photonic hook configuration does not form. Although Buddha particles are still at the laboratory research stage, their simple design appears extremely promising in mesotronics [19,20]. Future prospects for localized photonic hook beams [21] based on four-faced Buddha particles may involve controlling the local chirality of vortex beams at the subwavelength scale, similarly to [22].

References

1. M. Lattuada, T. A. Hatton. *Synthesis, properties and applications of Janus nanoparticles*. *Nano Today*. 6(3), 286-308 (2011). doi: 10.1016/j.nantod.2011.04.008
2. Casagrande C., Veyssie M., C. R. *Janus Beads — Realization and 1st Observation of Interfacial Properties*. *Acad. Sci. (Paris)*, 306 11, 1423, 1988
3. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *RF Patent 161207*. Filed October 27, 2015. Published April 10, 2016, *Bulletin 10*. https://rusneb.ru/catalog/000224_000128_0000161207_20160410_U1_RU/?ysclid=mjmbtuv7vq891616389
4. I. V. Minin, O.V; Minin. *Diffractive Optics and Nanophotonics*. (Springer: Berlin, Germany, 2016).
5. I. V. Minin, O.V; Minin. *Photonic hook: From Optics to Acoustics and Plasmonics*. (Springer: Berlin, Germany, 2021).
6. Y. Geints, O. V. Minin, L. Yue, and I. V. Minin. *Wavelength-Scale Photonic Space Switch Proof-Of-Concept Based on Photonic Hook Effect*. *Ann. Phys. (Berlin)* 2100192 (2021). DOI: 10.1002/andp.202100192
7. K. Dholakis, G. D. Bruce. *Optical hook*. *Nature Photonics* 13, 229-230 (2019). DOI: 10.1038/s41566-019-0403-9.
8. L. Yue, O. V. Minin, J. N. Monks, A. Shalin, and I. V. Minin, “Photonic hook: a new curved light beam,” *Opt. Lett.* 43, 771-774 (2018). DOI 10.1364/OL.43.000771

9. X. Cai, J. Wang, M. J. Strain, B. Johnson-Morris, J. Zhu, M. Sorel, J. L. O'Brien, M. G. Thompson, and S. Yu, *Integrated Compact Optical Vortex Beam Emitters*, *Science* 338, 363 (2012).
10. B. S. Luk'yanchuk, A. E. Miroshnichenko and Yu. S. Kivshar. *Fano resonances and topological optics: an interplay of far- and near-field interference phenomena*. *J. Opt.* 15, 073001 (2013). DOI 10.1088/2040-8978/15/7/073001
11. Das, B. K., Granados, C., & Ciappina, M. F. *Optical vortices: revolutionizing the field of linear and nonlinear optics*. *Advances in Physics: X*, 11(1) (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23746149.2025.2608076>
12. L. Yue, B. Yan, Y. Xie, Y. Geints, O. V. Minin, I. V. *Near-Field Light-Bending Photonic Switch: Physics of Switching Based on Three-Dimensional Poynting Vector Analysis*. *Photonics* 9, 154 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/photonics9030154>
13. N. M. McGovern. "A Buddhist Cult of Brahma: Thick Description And Micro-Histories in the Study of Religion". *History of Religions*. 55(3), 329-360 (2016). doi:10.1086/684274.
14. T. A. Rao. *Motilal Banarsidass Publisher*. 1985. p. 97.
15. A. Ang, et al. *Low-contrast photonic hook manipulator for cellular differentiation*. *Proc. META 2018, the 9th Int. Conf. on Metamaterials, Photonic Crystals and Plasmonics*. France, 2018
16. W.-Y. Chen, et al. *Numerical and experimental demonstrations of optical trapping and manipulation of a selective red blood cell using a photonic hook based on broken symmetry tapered fiber probe*. *Opt Las Tech*. 180, 111520 (2025).
17. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Experimental Demonstration of the Microprocessing of the Polystyrene Surface Using a Photonic Hook*. *JEPT Letters*. 120(2), 146-150 (2024).
18. A. V. Veluthandath and G. S. Murugan. "Continuously tuneable on-chip photonic hook for manipulating nanoparticles along curved trajectories", *Proc. SPIE 12436, Complex Light and Optical Forces XVII*, 124360K (15 March 2023).
19. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Mesotronics: Some New, Unusual Optical Effects*. *Photonics* 9(10), 762 (2022). DOI 10.3390/photonics9100762
20. I. V. Minin, O. V. Minin. *Recent Trends in Optical Manipulation Inspired by Mesoscale Photonics and Diffraction Optics*. *J of Biomedical Photonics & Eng* 6(2), 020301 (2020). DOI: 10.18287/JBPE20.06.020301
21. *Photonic hook effect*. <https://modem-physics.org/photonic-hook-effect/>
22. Y. Shi, Z. Cui, X. Cao, et al., "Curved chirality distributions of optical vortices induced by photonic hooks," *Opt. Lett.* 50, 1755-1758 (2025).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.21.42.151

UDC 613.6.02:543.064

蒜氨酸酶对GC-MS法测定大蒜中噻唑啉酮残留量基质效应的影响
**THE INFLUENCE OF THE ENZYME ALLINASE ON MATRIX
EFFECTS IN THE DETERMINATION OF RESIDUAL AMOUNTS OF
FOSTHIAZATE IN GARLIC BY GC-MS**

Egorchenkova Olga Evgenievna

Research Fellow

Kurpedinov Kirill Sergeevich

Junior Research Fellow

Federal Scientific Center for Hygiene named after F. F. Erisman,

Mytishchi, Russia

摘要: 由于大蒜基质中蒜氨酸酶活性高,且存在有机硫化物,导致气相色谱分析过程中出现显著的基质效应,因此测定大蒜中噻唑啉酮的残留量(RA)十分复杂。本研究探讨了蒜氨酸酶对背景信号增加的影响,并评估了样品前处理阶段降低基质效应的各种方法的有效性。结果表明,尽管预先对蒜氨酸酶进行热灭活可以降低基质效应,但会导致大蒜基质中噻唑啉酮的降解,从而降低其可检测浓度,导致提取回收率降至45%。作为替代方案,本研究提出了一种基于QuEChERS技术的改进样品前处理方案,该方案包括低温处理、提取物酸化和多级冷冻。优化后的方法能够有效抑制蒜氨酸酶的活性,降低基质效应,并实现噻唑啉酮的高回收率(95.4%)。采用气相色谱-质谱联用(GC-MS)法,并结合基质匹配校准标准,测定了福噻唑酯的定量限(LOQ)。定量限为0.01 mg/kg,相当于欧盟规定的最大残留限量(MRL)的50%。

关键词: 大蒜, 福噻唑酯, 蒜氨酸酶, 基质效应, QuEChERS, GC-MS。

Abstract. *The determination of residual amounts (RA) of fosthiazate in garlic is complicated by the high activity of the enzyme allinase in this matrix and the presence of organosulfur compounds that can cause pronounced matrix effects (ME) during gas chromatographic analysis. This study investigated the influence of the enzyme on the increase of background signal and assessed the effectiveness of various approaches to its reduction during the sample preparation stage. It was demonstrated that preliminary thermal inactivation of allinase, despite reducing ME, causes degradation of fosthiazate in the garlic matrix and, consequently,*

a decrease in its detectable concentration, reflected by a reduction in extraction recovery to 45%. As an alternative solution, a modified sample preparation protocol based on QuEChERS technology was proposed, incorporating low-temperature treatment, acidification of extracts, and multistage freezing. The optimized method ensures effective suppression of the enzymatic activity of allinase, a reduction in ME, and a high recovery rate of fosthiazate (95.4%). The determination of the LOQ of fosthiazate was performed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) with matrix-matched calibration standards. The limit of quantification was 0.01 mg/kg, corresponding to 50% of the maximum residue level (MRL) established by the European Union (EU).

Keywords: *garlic, fosthiazate, allinase, matrix effect, QuEChERS, GC-MS.*

Garlic (*Allium sativum*) is among the most widely cultivated vegetables in global agricultural practice, owing to its valuable nutritional and biologically active properties. Like most allium crops, garlic is vulnerable to various phytopathogens, notably nematodes (such as *Meloidogyne* and *Ditylenchus*), which cause significant damage to the plant root system, thereby reducing yield and quality. By affecting root tissues and feeding on cell sap, nematodes cause structural changes in the roots that disrupt plant nutrition and growth. Organophosphorus nematocides are widely used to combat these phytoparasites through soil application and pre-sowing treatment of garlic cloves.

Fosthiazate—(RS)-S-sec-butyl-O-ethyl-2-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-ylthiophosphate—is an organophosphorus nematocide used as an active ingredient (AI) in plant protection products against phytoparasitic nematodes. Modern formulations based on fosthiazate exhibit contact and fumigant activity against nematodes inhabiting the soil in the root zone [1]. Following soil application, the active ingredient disrupts neuromuscular regulation in nematodes, suppresses their motility, and prevents their migration to plant roots, ultimately resulting in parasite mortality. Fosthiazate possesses systemic activity and is capable of translocating within plant tissues, thereby providing protection to the root system against infection.

The challenges in establishing hygienic safety criteria for the application of the nematocide fosthiazate during garlic treatment cannot be effectively resolved without contemporary methodologies for its analytical identification.

Garlic contains high concentrations of organosulfur compounds, primarily alliin (S-allyl-L-cysteine sulfoxide) and the enzyme allinase [2]. In intact cells, their spatial segregation prevents interaction between the components: alliin is localized in the cytoplasm, while allinase resides in the vacuoles.

However, during the mechanical disruption of garlic cells, such as by crushing or grinding, the integrity of the cell membranes is compromised, resulting in alliin

coming into contact with allinase. During this enzymatic reaction, allicin (diallyl thiosulfinate) is formed — an unstable, volatile, and biologically active compound of garlic (Figure 1), which rapidly decomposes to form a series of organosulfur products, including diallyl sulfide (DAS), diallyl disulfide (DADS), diallyl trisulfide (DAT), as well as dithiins and ajoene [3].

Alliin and its derivatives are regarded as the primary volatile and semi-volatile matrix components of garlic, which can substantially affect the accuracy and reproducibility of analyses for trace pesticide residues by GC-MS combined with a modified QuEChERS procedure [4,5]. The QuEChERS sample preparation method is based on pesticide extraction with an organic solvent followed by cleanup using dispersive solid-phase extraction (dSPE) employing a mixture of sorbents. To minimize matrix effects caused by sulfur-containing compounds, it is necessary to suppress the enzymatic activity of allinase during sample preparation, ensuring the stability of the chemical composition of the matrix and the accuracy of the LOQ of fosthiazate.

Figure 1. Enzymatic conversion of alliin to allicin catalyzed by allinase

The enzymatic activity of allinase in garlic significantly depends on temperature conditions and medium acidity. The maximum catalytic activity of the enzyme is observed at approximately 30 °C. When the temperature falls below 0 °C, the activity of allinase is substantially suppressed. A sharp decline in activity is observed when the temperature exceeds 60 °C, due to thermal denaturation of the enzyme's protein structure [6].

The temperature dependence of allinase activity is crucial during garlic sample preparation, as the extraction and storage conditions of the samples determine the extent of alliin conversion to allicin, which influences the ME during mass spectrometric analysis.

In this study, experiments were carried out to reduce the ME of garlic extract by pre-inactivating allinase prior to the mechanical homogenization of the samples. For this purpose, preliminary thermal treatment of garlic cloves in a water bath, as well as exposure to microwave radiation, was employed. These approaches partially suppressed enzymatic activity, resulting in a reduction of ME during subsequent chromatographic analysis. Although thermal treatment reduced the

influence of sulfur-containing matrix components, this approach caused significant losses of fosthiazate and reduced its extraction efficiency to unacceptable levels (not exceeding 45%).

This necessitated the search for an alternative method to suppress enzymatic activity without causing degradation of the target analyte: low-temperature treatment of samples, which includes preliminary freezing of garlic cloves and performing subsequent sample preparation steps at reduced temperatures.

To obtain satisfactory analytical performance in determining the LOQ of fosthiazate in garlic, the standard QuEChERS sample preparation protocol was adapted through modification.

Garlic cloves were pre-frozen for 24 hours, followed by homogenization in a cutter using dry ice. A 5.0 g portion of the homogenate was placed in a 50 cm³ centrifuge tube, followed by addition of 10 cm³ of ice-cold water, 10 cm³ of chilled acetonitrile, and a ceramic homogenizer; the tube was sealed, manually shaken vigorously for 30 sec, and subjected to low-temperature freezing for 1 hour at a temperature below -18 °C. Extraction yielded positive results when using salts with citrate buffer (magnesium sulfate, sodium chloride, sodium citrate, and disodium hydrogen citrate dihydrate).

When the pH falls below 4.0, allinase activity significantly decreases [7]. To further deactivate the enzymatic activity of the matrix, the extracts were acidified with 40 mm³ of concentrated hydrochloric acid to pH 4.

After re-freezing the extract for 1 hour, a 6 cm³ aliquot of the upper layer was transferred into a polypropylene centrifuge tube containing a sorbent mixture for dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE). The sample was vigorously shaken for 30 seconds and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 4500 rpm. The purified extract was further refrozen at a temperature not exceeding -18 °C for 1 hour.

In d-SPE of the extracts, a sorbent mixture based on amines and magnesium sulfate was used, ensuring effective removal of coexisting matrix components while maintaining high extraction efficiency of fosthiazate. The selection of this sorbent combination is due to the chemical nature of fosthiazate, which contains an organophosphorus group and a heterocyclic fragment, potentially causing sorptive losses on carbon sorbents such as graphitized carbon black (GCB). GCB was excluded from the purification scheme because of its π - π and donor-acceptor interactions with fosthiazate, which reduce extraction efficiency to 60-65%.

Acetonitrile, having a high boiling point, can cause losses of fosthiazate during the sample injection stage, leading to decreased stability of the analytical signal of fosthiazate in GC analysis. To prevent these losses, a concentration process of the extracts was conducted, replacing acetonitrile with a more suitable solvent — hexane.

The analysis of the LOQ of fosthiazate was performed using a chromatograph-mass spectrometer 'Agilent 5977A/7890B', equipped with a capillary quartz column HP-5MS UI (30 m × 0.25 mm, film thickness 0.25 μm) with a stationary phase composed of 5 %-phenyl-95 %-dimethylpolysiloxane. Separation was conducted in temperature programming mode. Helium was used as the carrier gas; the injection volume of the sample (1 mm³) into the injector was performed without flow splitting. Electron ionization (EI) (70 eV) was utilized; mass spectra were acquired in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode, with mass-to-charge ratios (m/z) of 195 (quantitative analysis), 227, and 283 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Ion fragments of fosthiazate molecular ions under electron ionization.

Fosthiazate consists of four stereoisomers due to the presence of two chiral centers at the carbon and phosphorus atoms (Figure 3). The molar ratio of the four stereoisomers in the racemic fosthiazate standard is approximately 1:1:1:1 [8,9].

Figure 3. Four stereoisomers of fosthiazate

The stereoisomers with configurations 1S,3S and 1R,3R constitute one pair of enantiomers, while the other pair of enantiomers is formed by stereoisomers with configurations 1R,3S and 1S,3R. Two pairs of enantiomers exhibit diastereomeric properties, and under the conditions of the selected GC-MS method, fosthiazate produces two nearly equal peaks (Figure 4).

To identify interfering impurities potentially arising from deficiencies in sample preparation or from impurities in the reagents, an analysis of a blank reagent sample was also conducted. This analysis involved performing the sample preparation procedure and analysis of the sample without a matrix, that is, using only solvents and auxiliary materials. Additionally, a single control garlic sample was analyzed.

Figure 4. Total ion current (TIC) chromatogram obtained in SIM mode of garlic extract spiked with fosthiazate at a concentration of 0.1 mg/kg.

Under the selected sample preparation conditions, comparison of the signal response for a standard at a concentration of 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (corresponding to the

lower limit of quantification — LOQ), prepared in solvent and in a matrix extract derived from garlic cloves, indicated that the ME exceeded 20%, reaching 44.7%.

The obtained ME value served as the basis for constructing the calibration curve using solutions prepared in matrix extract. The calibration curve constructed over the range of 0.01-0.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ on standards prepared from garlic clove extract ensured effective compensation for ME and high accuracy in determining fosthiazate concentrations.

Quantitative determination of the substance content was performed based on the sum of the areas of two substance peaks using a calibration curve constructed by regression analysis from chromatographic data of a series of calibration solutions prepared in a matrix background.

In the Russian Federation, the maximum allowable level (MAL) of fosthiazate in garlic has not been established; in the European Union (EU), the MRL (Maximum Residue Limit) is 0.02 mg/kg [10].

The modified QuEChERS sample preparation combined with GC-MS enabled not only a low limit of quantification of 0.01 mg/kg (corresponding to 50% of the MRL) but also a high extraction efficiency of fosthiazate (95.4%).

It has been demonstrated that the high enzymatic activity of garlic, attributed to the action of allinase, is a key factor contributing to matrix effects in the determination of the LOQ of fosthiazate by GC-MS. It has been established that preliminary thermal inactivation of allinase reduces matrix effects; however, this causes significant analyte losses due to the thermolability of fosthiazate and does not yield optimal analytical results. As an effective alternative, a modified sample preparation protocol based on the QuEChERS methodology is proposed, incorporating low-temperature treatment, acidification of extracts, and multi-stage freezing, which suppresses enzymatic activity in the matrix while maintaining high extraction efficiency of fosthiazate. The optimized method is characterized by satisfactory reproducibility, a limit of quantification of 0.01 mg/kg, and an average extraction recovery of 95.4%, which allows its recommendation for analytical monitoring of the LOQ of fosthiazate in garlic.

References

1. Hai Yan Wu, Man Luo, Lu Yuan Zhang, and Xun Bo Zhou. *Nematicidal Activity of Fosthiazate Against Soybean Cyst Nematode Heterodera glycines*. *J Nematol.* — 2019. — Vol. 51: e2019-21. DOI: 10.21307/jofnem-2019-021.
2. Jan Borlinghaus, Frank Albrecht, Martin C. H. Gruhlke, Ifeanyi D. Nwachukwu and Alan J. Shusarenko. *Alliin: Chemistry and Biological Properties // Molecules.* — 2014, — Vol. 19, P. 12591-12618. DOI:10.3390/molecules19081259.

3. Rahman M. S. *Allicin and Other Functional Active Components in Garlic: Health Benefits and Bioavailability // International Journal of Food Properties.* — 2007. — Vol. 10. P. 245-268. DOI: 10.1080/10942910601113327.
4. Aspromonte J., Lancioni C., Purcaro G. *Solid-Phase Microextraction — Gas Chromatography Analytical Strategies for Pesticide Analysis. Methods Protoc.* — 2022; 5(5):82. DOI: 10.3390/mps5050082.
5. Anastassiades, M. *Fast and Easy Multiresidue Method Employing Acetonitrile Extraction/Partitioning and Dispersive Solid-Phase Extraction for the Determination of Pesticide Residues in Produce / M. Anastassiades, S. J. Lehotay, D. Stajnbaher, F. J. Schenck // Journal of AOAC International.* — 2003. — Vol. 86, № 2. — P. 412-431.
6. Zilei Chen, Hong Zhang, Bing Liu, Guosheng Yang, Hassan Y. Aboul-Enein, Wenbo Wang, Ruiyan Ding, Hongxia Du, Huidong Li. *Determination of Herbicide Residues in Garlic by GC-MS // Chromatographia.* — 2007. — Vol. 66. — P. 887-891. DOI: 10.1365/s10337-007-0425-10009-5893/07/12.
7. Janská P., Knejzlik Z., et al. *Effect of physicochemical parameters on the stability and activity of garlic alliinase and its use for in-situ allicin synthesis // PLOS ONE.* — 2021. — Vol. 16. No. 3. e0248878. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0248878.
8. Lianshan Li, Jiangyan Xu, Bo Lv, Amir E Kazim, Fang Liu, Haiyan Shi, Minghua Wang. *Chiral Organophosphorus Pesticide Fosthiazate: Absolute Configuration, Stereoselective Bioactivity, Toxicity, and Degradation in Vegetables. J Agric Food Chem.* — 2020. — Vol. 68(29). — P. 7609-7616. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jafc.0c03008.
9. Lin, K., Zhang, F., Zhou, S., Liu, W., Gan, J., & Pan, Z. (2007). *Stereoisomeric separation and toxicity of the nematicide fosthiazate. Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry.* — Vol. 26. P. 2339-2344. DOI: 10.1897/07-255r.1.
10. EU Pesticides Database. URL: <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/mrl> (accessed: 27.01.2026).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.22.48.065

运用水生生态系统替代稳定状态原理来应对蓝藻污染
**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF AN ALTERNATIVE
STABLE STATE OF AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS TO COUNTERACT
CYANOBACTERIAL POLLUTION**

Pozdnyakova Albina Iskandarovna

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Russian State Hydrometeorological University*

摘要：在日益加剧的人为压力和全球气候变化的背景下，现代水生生态学的一个关键问题是富营养化—生物源元素（主要是氮和磷）过量流入水生生态系统。这一过程导致初级生产者群落组成发生根本性重组，使原本水生植物丰富的清澈湖泊转变为受水华现象困扰的退化系统。抑制局部水生生态系统中蓝藻大量繁殖最有效且最有前景的方法是促进能够吸收过量营养物质（氮磷）的竞争性高等水生植物的快速繁殖。这种方法消除了蓝藻污染的根本原因，而其他方法仅能解决其后果。此外，每个水体的具体物理地理和微气候特征决定了在制定最佳刺激方案时需要采取个性化的方法。

关键词：大型植物；蓝藻；水生生态系统竞争之争。受自然启发而开发的蓝藻抑制技术

Abstract. *Amid increasing anthropogenic pressure and global climate change, a key issue in modern hydroecology is eutrophication — the excessive influx of biogenic elements (primarily nitrogen and phosphorus) into aquatic ecosystems. This process causes a fundamental restructuring of primary producer community composition, converting clear lakes with abundant flora into degrading systems afflicted by water 'bloom' phenomena. The most effective and promising approach to suppressing the mass development of cyanobacteria in local aquatic ecosystems is the stimulation of accelerated propagation of competitive higher aquatic plants that absorb excessive nutrient (nitrogen-phosphorus) substances. This approach eliminates the root cause of cyanobacterial pollution, while other methods address only the consequences of this process. Moreover, the specific physico-geographical and microclimatic characteristics of each aquatic body necessitate an individualized approach when developing the optimal regimen for such stimulation.*

Keywords: *Macrophytes. Cyanobacteria. Aquatic ecosystems. Competitive struggle. Nature-inspired technology for cyanobacteria suppression*

Cyanobacteria, or blue-green algae, constitute a division of large Gram-negative bacteria capable of photosynthesis accompanied by oxygen evolution. Currently, these are considered the oldest microorganisms existing on Earth, and their mass proliferation led to the emergence and accumulation of free oxygen in the planet's atmosphere. However, their crucial role on a global scale can have negative consequences when manifesting locally. During their life cycle, by consuming nitrogen-phosphorus compounds present in the aquatic environment, many cyanobacteria release highly toxic organic substances. These substances disrupt the normal physiological functions of other organisms, ultimately causing their death. Thus, the primary function of these bacterial toxins is to suppress the reproduction of competing species. Water containing these toxins becomes lethally hazardous for use at certain concentrations.

In this context, various methods to combat blue-green algae have long been proposed, most of which prove ineffective due to the very high ability of cyanobacteria to withstand adverse effects. For example, the use of ultrasound. Cyanobacteria possess a unique adaptation — gas vacuoles (vesicles). These are tiny cavities inside the cell filled with gas, which allow them to regulate buoyancy: rising to the light during the day and sinking for nutrients at night. Ultrasound waves of a specific frequency induce the effects of cavitation and resonance, causing the gas vacuoles inside the cells of cyanobacteria to burst, the cell loses buoyancy and irreversibly settles at the bottom, where, in most cases, without access to sunlight, photosynthesis ceases, and the algae die. However, a serious problem arises — when ultrasound destroys the cell membrane of a cyanobacterium, all its internal contents, including hazardous cyanotoxins, are instantly released into the water. Thus, the water may temporarily become clear but even more toxic. Moreover, ultrasound can negatively impact zooplankton (such as daphnia), which are natural enemies of cyanobacteria. If the daphnia perish, cyanobacteria will return even faster once the installation is turned off. However, most importantly, the application of ultrasound eliminates the symptoms but not the cause of the mass proliferation of cyanobacteria (excess nitrogen and phosphorus). Once the ultrasound device is turned off, cyanobacteria will begin to grow again, since the nutrients remain in the water. There are numerous examples of similar unsuccessful attempts to apply various methods for combating cyanobacteria [1,2,3].

In this context, the most effective approach to eliminating not the consequences but the root causes of conditions enabling the mass development of cyanobacteria colonies is the method of stimulating interspecific competition between higher aquatic plants (macrophytes) and cyanobacteria. In this case, the concept of the so-called 'alternative stable states' [4] is implemented. According to this, shallow ecosystems can exist in two modes: either in a state dominated by higher aquatic plants, characterized by high water transparency and stable biocenosis, or in a state dominated by phytoplankton, in which the water becomes turbid and biological diversity sharply decreases.

During this process, higher aquatic plants not only accumulate biogenic substances by absorbing them from the water column, but also create a distinct physical structure of the environment, serve as a substrate for periphyton, and provide refuge for zooplankton — the main consumers of algae. At the same time, cyanobacteria, possessing high biological plasticity, the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen, and the production of potent cyanotoxins, can effectively counteract and suppress the growth of macrophytes, displacing them from their ecological niche.

Direct competition between macrophytes and cyanobacteria occurs in two primary dimensions: competition for access to light and competition for mineral resources (biogenic substances). The outcome of this confrontation ultimately determines the dominant species.

Light is the primary limiting factor for all photosynthesizing organisms. Higher aquatic plants, possessing a complex morphological structure, employ strategies of spatial domination. In this case, plants with floating leaves or forming a continuous cover on the water surface (for example, *Eichhornia crassipes* or *Nuphar lutea*) absorb up to 90-95% of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR). Under such light-deficient conditions, the development of cyanobacteria in the water column is physically impossible. Moreover, submerged macrophytes — hydratophytes (*Elodea canadensis*, *Ceratophyllum demersum*)—effectively reduce illumination in the lower strata, thereby inhibiting the development of benthic cyanobacterial forms. Simultaneously, higher aquatic plants act as significant biogenic reservoirs. In contrast to fast-growing but short-lived cyanobacteria, macrophytes sequester nitrogen and phosphorus from the nutrient cycle for an extended period (virtually throughout the entire growing season). This creates a ‘hungry ration’ for phytoplankton at the beginning of summer. Moreover, macrophytes have a unique advantage — the ability to absorb nutrients both from the water column (via leaves) and from bottom sediments (via roots). Cyanobacteria, however, are limited by resources dissolved in the water.

However, with excessive input of nitrogen-phosphorus compounds, cyanobacteria begin to reproduce rapidly. High cell density in the surface layer causes a sharp increase in water turbidity. As a result, hydratophytes stop receiving sufficient light for photosynthesis. This leads to a reduction in their biomass and gradual die-off, thereby freeing even more resources for the development of cyanobacterial colonies. Moreover, under conditions of nitrogen deficiency, many cyanobacterial species (for example, the genera *Anabaena*, *Aphanizomenon*) activate heterocysts — specialized cells for atmospheric nitrogen fixation. This confers upon them an absolute advantage over higher aquatic plants in nitrogen-limited water bodies.

Finally, during active photosynthesis, higher aquatic plants and cyanobacteria significantly alter the chemical composition of the water, which also functions as

a competitive mechanism. Intensive carbon dioxide uptake in dense plant stands or in “bloom” patches leads to a sharp increase in pH (sometimes up to 9.0-10.0). Many cyanobacteria possess more advanced carbon concentrating mechanisms, enabling them to continue photosynthesis at pH levels that inhibit most higher aquatic plants.

A key element of competition between macrophytes and cyanobacteria is allelopathy — the direct or indirect chemical effect of one organism on another through the release of secondary metabolites (allelochemicals) into the surrounding environment. In the ‘macrophytes–cyanobacteria’ system, allelopathy functions as a mechanism of active defense and expansion, enabling organisms to suppress the growth of competitors without direct physical contact.

Higher aquatic plants synthesize a broad range of exometabolites possessing algicidal (algae-lethal) properties. The most active “chemical agents” are:

- Polyphenols and tannins: the most well-studied example is Eurasian water-milfoil (*Myriophyllum spicatum*), which secretes tellimagranin II. This compound effectively inhibits the photosystems of cyanobacteria by blocking electron transport during photosynthesis.

- Cyclic sulfur-containing compounds: charophyte algae (*Chara* spp.), which are morphologically close to higher plants, secrete dithiolane and trithiane. These substances not only inhibit the cell division of cyanobacteria but also reduce the intensity of their “blooming” even under eutrophic conditions.

- Fatty acids: Some species of pondweeds (*Potamogeton*) secrete a complex of unsaturated fatty acids that disrupt the cell membranes of cyanobacteria, causing cytoplasm leakage and cell death.

In this regard, the allelochemicals of macrophytes attack cyanobacteria through several mechanisms:

- destruction of the photosynthetic apparatus — suppression of the activity of enzymes responsible for carbon fixation, and degradation of chlorophyll-a;

- oxidative stress — induction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production inside cyanobacterial cells, leading to damage to DNA and proteins;

- enzymatic inhibition — blockage of the activity of extracellular enzymes (for example, alkaline phosphatase), which prevents cyanobacteria from assimilating organic phosphorus from the water.

In response to pressure from macrophytes or upon reaching high population density, they release potent cyanotoxins (microcystins, anatoxins, cylindrospermopsin).

Although the primary role of these toxins is protection against zooplankton grazing, recent studies demonstrate their negative effects on macrophytes. Cyanotoxins can reduce the germination rate of seeds and spores of aquatic plants, cause necrosis of leaf tissues, slow the growth of the root system, and disrupt nitrogen metabolism in plant tissues, thereby weakening them in the competitive struggle for survival.

It is important to note that allelopathic effectiveness strongly depends on external factors. For example, under high temperature or intense illumination, the toxicity of macrophyte exudates may be enhanced. However, in heavily polluted (hypereutrophic) water bodies, bacterial decomposition of allelochemicals occurs faster than plants can synthesize them, giving cyanobacteria an advantage and leading to the eventual degradation of the phytocoenosis. That is, success in competitive interactions is determined by the ability of organisms to efficiently utilize resources. Macrophytes dominate under conditions of moderate biogenic loading, employing mechanisms such as shading, nutrient uptake from bottom sediments, and allelopathic suppression. Cyanobacteria gain an advantage under hyper-eutrophication and increased temperatures by utilizing their high reproduction rate, buoyancy, and ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. At the same time, contemporary studies show that climate change favors cyanobacteria. The increase in water temperature not only accelerates their growth but also strengthens thermal stratification of water bodies, which impedes the growth of submerged macrophytes. In this context, the establishment of regulations for the early artificial introduction (at the very beginning of the growing season, once a suitable favorable temperature regime is achieved) of the most effective species of higher aquatic plants, along with their timely removal at the end of the vegetation period, represents the most effective and simultaneously the most ecologically sound method to counteract cyanobacterial proliferation. Special attention should be given to shallow zones at locations of intense external load input [5]. These sites must be densely colonized by macrophytes, through which polluted water will be filtered. In this context, macrophytes act as a mechanical and biological filter, suppressing the development of cyanobacteria at the entry to the main water body. Therefore, a thorough analysis of the points of input of both point and diffuse external loads is required, necessitating an individual approach to each water body in the development of the stated regulation.

References

1. Nikitin O. V., Latypova V. Z., Pozdnyakov Sh. R. *Ecotechnologies for Reservoir Restoration*. Kazan: Publishing House of Kazan University, 2015. — 139 p.
2. Pavlyuk T. E., Popov A. N., Ushakova O. S., Mukhutdinov V. F., Padalka A. A. *Correction of algocenoses through Chlorella introduction: analysis of application attempts // Water Resources, 2023, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 324-333.*
3. Rumyantsev V. A., Kryukov L. N., Pozdnyakov Sh. R., Zhukovsky A. V. *Cyanobacterial "blooming" of water — a source of environmental management problems and a stimulus for innovation in Russia // Society. Environment. Development. — 2011. — No. 2 (19). — pp. 222-228.*

4. *Lewontin R. C. Meaning of stability. Diversity and stability in ecological systems (Brookhaven Symposia in Biology N22) Brookhaven Laboratory, New York. 1969, P. 13-24.*

5. *Pozdnyakov Sh.R., Kondratyev S. A. Diffuse biogenic loading — a possible cause of anthropogenic eutrophication of water bodies // Russian Journal of Applied Ecology. — 2022. — No. 4. — Pp. 28-35.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.22.60.106

南萨哈林岛中新世卢西诺玛属 (LUCINOMA DALL) 海生双壳类软体动物及其
地层学意义

**SEA BIVALVE MOLLUSKS OF THE GENUS LUCINOMA DALL
FROM THE MIOCENE OF SOUTH SAKHALIN AND THEIR
STRATIGRAFIC SIGNIFICANCE**

Khudik Vladimir Dmitrievich

*Candidate of Geologo-Mineralogical Sciences, Senior Research Officer
Far Eastern Geological Institute of the Far Eastern Branch of the
Russian Academy of Sciences, Vladivostok, Russia*

摘要: 本文研究了来自萨哈林岛南部中新世地层的海洋双壳类软体动物——卢西诺玛属 (*Lucinoma* Dall) 的代表物种。追溯了该属的研究历史, 确定了其分类组成, 并进行了修订。研究确定了萨哈林岛南部中新世地层中存在两个物种: 尖线卢西诺玛 (*L. acutilineata* (Conrad)) 和环状卢西诺玛 (*L. annulata* Reeve)。追溯了它们在中新世地层中的分离和分布历史, 并论证了这些物种对萨哈林岛宿主地层 (包括具有油气潜力的地层) 地层学的重要意义。探讨了气候因素与萨哈林岛中新世卢西诺玛属发育之间的关系。研究表明, 萨哈林岛和西北太平洋地区 (堪察加半岛、科里亚克共和国) 的中新世卢西诺玛属发育活跃。

关键词: 双壳类软体动物, 中新世, 南萨哈林岛。

Abstract. *Representatives of marine bivalve mollusks of the genus Lucinoma Dall from Miocene deposits of southern Sakhalin are studied. The history of genus research is traced, its taxonomic composition is established, and its revision is conducted. The presence of two species — L. acutilineata (Conrad) and L. annulata Reeve — has been established in the Miocene of southern Sakhalin. The history of their isolation and distribution in Miocene deposits is traced, and the significance of these taxa for the stratigraphy of host strata on Sakhalin, including those with hydrocarbon potential, is substantiated. The relationship between climatic factors and the development of the genus in the Miocene of Sakhalin is considered. A period of active lucinomas development in the Miocene of Sakhalin and regions of the northwestern Pacific (Kamchatka, Koryakia) is demonstrated.*

Keywords: *Bivalve mollusks, Miocene, South Sakhalin.*

Recent research has convincingly demonstrated that the origin and industrial production of hydrocarbons on Sakhalin are linked to Paleogene-Neogene marine sediments, which often contain remains of marine bivalve mollusks. Unfortunately, many of these faunas remain poorly studied, including mollusks of the genus *Lucinoma* Dall (Fig.1).

F. Kilmer [29], studying the history of the development of the Pliocene faunas of Japan, came to the conclusion that the most ancient representatives of the genera and subgenera of bivalve mollusks of Honshu and Hokkaido arose in the Jurassic and Cretaceous periods of this region. However, with regard to the genus *Lucinoma*, he proposed that only representatives of this genus from the Oligocene faunas of Japan be considered valid. However, while pointing this out, he still acknowledged the insufficiently clear history of the development of the genus as a whole.

There is information about the possible presence of representatives of the genus *Lucinoma* in the Cretaceous faunas of Japan [35]. Thus, from the Lower Cretaceous of Japan (Hiraiga Formation of the Tanyuhata District), I. Hayami [26] described shells of bivalve mollusks as *Lucinoma* (?) *kotoi* (Nagao), which are no different from the Paleogene-Neogene representatives of this genus. According to our observations, both have similar shell outlines, the structure of the lunula and scutellum, and the nature of the sculpture of the valve surface is similar. I. Hayami doubts the generic affiliation of the forms described by him, but we consider it possible that they correspond to the genus *Lucinoma*. If we assume that lucinomas appeared in the Early Cretaceous of Japan, this does not correspond to the above-mentioned ideas of F. Kilmer [50] about the Cenozoic period of migration of the genus from west to east in the Pacific regions, and allows us to assume a possible earlier stage of its development here in the Middle — Late Mesozoic. In any case, no visible physical or geographical barriers have been identified. Therefore, questions regarding the possible early migration of lucinomas and the accompanying conditions remain open.

Fig. 1. Overview scheme of the study area

In the early periods of studying the fossil faunas of the Far East, in the domestic literature, most lucinids were considered as part of the genus *Phacoides* Blainville [6,8,12], and later — as part of the genus *Lucinoma* Dall [3,4]. It is noteworthy that at the same time, in the “Key to the genera of Bivalve mollusks of the USSR” [10], in accordance with the views of its authors, the genus *Phacoides* is considered a junior synonym of the genus *Lucina* Bruguiere, and the genus *Lucinoma*, at least in the Cenozoic, was not listed at all. All this introduced confusion into the taxonomy of Far Eastern lucinids and the understanding of their role in the development of the malacofaunas of the northern Pacific, especially since representatives of the genus *Lucinoma* have long been known in the Cenozoic faunas of Japan and Northwest America, which can be traced to Sakhalin, Koryakia and Kamchatka.

Information obtained during the analysis of dredged bottom sediments from the Central Basin (Vasilkovsky Ridge) of the Sea of Japan and the central part of the Sea of Okhotsk, recovered during marine geological studies by the Pacific Oceanological Institute of the Far Eastern Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences on board the research vessel Akademik M. A. Lavrentyev (cruise no. 58), also indicates the presence of representatives of the genus *Lucinoma* (*L. annulata* Reeve) in the marine Miocene faunas of the Sea of Japan [14]. In our opinion, a comparison of the faunas of these areas is important for correlating and substantiating the age of the host Cenozoic strata (including oil and gas bearing) of Sakhalin and a vast region of the northwestern Pacific. On the other hand, an analysis of the paleobiogeographic structure of bivalve mollusk communities in the Miocene of southern Sakhalin [16, 17] showed that lucinomas played an important role in the composition of warm-water faunas of the region. Thus, along with the subtropical — low boreal mollusks of the genera *Glycymeris*, *Taras*, *Cultellus* and *Periploma*, they constituted up to 24% of the generic composition of the Sertunai (= Aushi) communities. Lucinomas are also present in the warm-water faunas of Japan [19] and northwestern America [31]. In this regard, the study of these mollusks and an attempt to use them as a kind of indicator of the paleobiogeographic structure of the Cenozoic faunas of the region, which often reflect the nature of the climatic conditions of past eras, in our opinion, also deserve attention.

According to several researchers [7,13], one of the most powerful centers of evolution for Cenozoic malacofaunas in the northwestern Pacific existed in the area of Hokkaido Island and southern Sakhalin during the late Oligocene to early Miocene. This center was quite active, likely isolated from the Tethys Sea, and exerted a significant influence on the formation of Miocene faunas in this region and the entire northern Pacific basin. The development of lucinoid mollusks, along with other genera of bivalves, in this area may well have been influenced by it.

In our opinion, one possible reason for the formation of this evolutionary center could have been the significant climate fluctuations in the region at the end

of the Oligocene — early Miocene [1,15,16]. Apparently, the rather unstable and significantly different conditions for the existence of organisms (including marine benthic organisms) could have served as a kind of impetus for the rapid evolutionary development in the region as a whole. We believe it is possible to assume that the unstable climatic conditions in this region, caused by relatively sharp climate fluctuations at the end of the late Oligocene — beginning of the early Miocene, could have served as an important factor in the rapid evolutionary development of certain genera of bivalve mollusks, including *Lucinoma*.

Of interest are data on the range of the genus *Lucinoma*. While finds of lucinomas are not uncommon within the northwestern Pacific in the Paleogene-Neogene strata of Sakhalin [8,12,16,17], Kamchatka [5], and the Koryak Highlands [2], they are currently absent from areas north of Hokkaido Island [13]. In this regard, it is noteworthy that lucinoma species are also absent from the Anthropogene in the northern Far East [11].

It is clear that the southward shift in the genus's range, corresponding to its current position, began around the late Pliocene-Pleistocene period. This could have been caused by the progressive cooling of the region, noted by many researchers during this time [1,15]. Modern lucinomas in the northwestern Pacific are predominantly inhabitants of warm (tropical, subtropical) and relatively warm (subtropical-low boreal) waters.

The significant morphological variability of lucinoma shells has prompted many researchers over a long period of time to identify new species and forms among them. According to Y. Goto and G. Pope [24], the modern world fauna of marine bivalve mollusks includes 13 species of the genus *Lucinoma*. Among them are *L. adamsiana* Habe, *L. acutilineata* (Conrad), *L. aequizonata* Stearns, *L. annulata* Reeve, *L. atlantis* Mclean, *L. blakeana* Bush, *L. borealis* Linne, *L. filosa* Stimpson, *L. galathea* Marwick, *L. heroica* Dall, *L. japonica* Habe, *L. spectabilis* Yokoyama, *L. yoshidai* Habe. At the same time, in the Cenozoic of the northern Pacific, the genus *Lucinoma* is represented by more than 20 taxa, with the greatest species diversity noted in the Cenozoic of Japan [19,28]. According to K. Hirayama [27], by the mid-1960s, 15 species of lucinomas had been isolated there (*L. izirii* Otuka, *L. otukai* Hatai et Nishiyama, *L. katayosensis* Aoki, *L. hanezawaensis* Nomura et Zinbo, *L. acutilineata* (Conrad), *L. annulata* (Reeve), *L. spectabilis* (Yokoyama), *L. concentrica* (Yokoyama), *L. meisensis* Makiyama, *L. shimogoenensis* Hirayama, *L. nipponica* Nomura et Hatai, *L. corrugate* (Deshayes), *L. stearnsiana* Oyama, *L. edentula* (Linne), *L. mochizukii* Kuroda), although many of which can hardly be considered valid.

It is noteworthy that in early paleontological works, the comparison of species during their descriptions is often overly brief, which makes it difficult to understand its scope in the author's view. Frequently, the same taxon is identified in the composition

of modern and fossil faunas. For example, the species *L. acutilineata* (Conrad), according to Japanese researchers [18, 27], characterizes the Miocene strata, but is still found today. In the “Atlas of the Paleogene and Neogene Fauna of the Northeast of the USSR” [2], the geological age of this species is given from the Eocene to the present day. If this is true, then it is necessary to recognize the extreme degree of stability and conservatism of the species over time as a whole, for almost 55.8 million years. Such a duration of existence of a mollusk species is highly questionable. While processing lucinomas from Tertiary deposits in southern Sakhalin, we encountered a rare example of the significant variability inherent in individual taxa of the genus, including *L. acutilineata*. Within a single paleocenosis, individual shells are often found that only vaguely resemble the typical appearance of the species. Only excellent preservation of the shell material (which is extremely rare), including the dentition, imprints of internal shell structures, and the nature of their external sculpture, can significantly aid in the differentiation of fossil lucinomas between species.

The analysis of our collection of fossil lucinomas along with the available literature data on this group of mollusks for the territories of adjacent regions (Kamchatka, Japan, northwestern America), convinced us of the need, following L. V. Kristofovich [9], to distinguish at least two fairly comprehensive species in the Oligocene-Miocene history of the southern Sakhalin basin: *L. annulata* (Reeve) and *L. acutilineata* (Conrad). The first of these was identified by L. Reeve [33] from the Pliocene-Pleistocene strata of northwestern America as *Lucina annulata*, but was subsequently transferred to the genus *Lucinoma* Dall [25], within the scope of which it is still considered. Judging by the available data [18,32], within the northern Pacific and on Sakhalin, this species has been a common element of marine bivalve mollusk communities from the Pliocene to the present day.

The second species, *L. acutilineata*, was first isolated by E. Conrad [20] from the Miocene of northwestern America under the name *Lucina acutilineata*, and later transferred by him to the genus *Cyclos Morch* [21]. It is noteworthy that simultaneously with the isolation of this species, in the same work T. Conrad established the taxon *Pectunculus pulus* (Conrad, 1849, p. 726, pl. 18, figs. 8, 8a), which, according to a number of researchers, is the typical form of *Lucina acutilineata* and is accepted as the holotype of this species [30,31]. Later, W. Doal [22] proposed to consider the taxon as part of the genus *Phacoides* Blainville, and T. Etherington [23] assigned it to the subgenus *Lucinoma* Dall. This subgenus then received the status of a genus and is currently considered in this rank by malacologists. In our opinion, taking into account literary data [2,31,32], in northwestern America and on Sakhalin, *Lucinoma acutilineata* characterizes the mollusk fauna of the Eocene-Late Miocene age.

Based on the above, we accept a well-defined stratigraphic position for lucinomas in the Cenozoic section of southern Sakhalin and, possibly, the entire

northwestern Pacific (Sakhalin, Koryakia, and Kamchatka). The species *L. acutilineata* is undoubtedly more ancient, characterizing the Eocene-Upper Miocene strata of the region; by the end of the Miocene, it was replaced by *L. annulata*, which still exists today. Forming a significant part of the faunas of the subtropical-low-boreal waters of the northwestern Pacific, it extends northward to approximately 45° N.

The results of these studies allow us to trace the evolutionary history of marine bivalve mollusks of the genus *Lucinoma* Dall. A revision of the Miocene representatives of the genus in the northwestern Pacific basin was conducted. The paleobiogeographic analysis of the genus's taxa allows us to consider them as a significant component of the thermophilic bivalve communities of the Miocene of Sakhalin and adjacent regions of the northwestern Pacific (Kamchatka, Koryakia). In southern Sakhalin, we identified the aforementioned taxa, which have stratigraphic significance for the subdivision of host strata with hydrocarbon potential.

References

1. Gladenkov Yu. B. *Climatic fluctuations in the Neogene of the northern part of Kamchatka* // *Dokl. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Ser.geol.* 1982. T. 265, No. 2. P. 407-409.
2. Devyatilova A. D., Volobueva V. I. *Atlas of the Paleogene and Neogene fauna of the northeast of the USSR. M.: Nedra, 1981. 219 p.*
3. Zhidkova L. S., Bezv V. E., Ilyina A. P., Krishtofovich L. V., Neverova T. I., Savitsky V. O., Sheremetyeva G. N. *Atlas of Neogene mollusks of the Kuril Islands. M.: Nauka, 1972. 166 p.*
4. Zhidkova L. S., Mishakov G. S., Neverova T. I., Popova L. A., Salnikov B. A., Salnikova N. B., Sheremetyeva G. N. *Biofacies Features of the Mesozoic-Cenozoic Basins of Sakhalin and the Kuril Islands. Novosibirsk: Nauka, 1974. 251 p.*
5. Ilyina A. P. *Mollusks of the Neogene Deposits of Southern Sakhalin* // *Mollusks of the Tertiary Deposits of Southern Sakhalin. Leningrad: Gostoptekhizdat, 1954. pp. 188-316. (Proceedings of the VNIGRI; Issue 10).*
6. Ilyina A. P. *Mollusks of the Neogene of Kamchatka. Leningrad, 1963. 240 p. (Proceedings of the VNIGRI. Issue 202).*
7. Kafanov A. I. *On the centers of origin and some features of the ecological evolution of cold-water marine malacofaunas of the Northern Hemisphere. Biology of the Sea, 1978. No. 1. P. 62-68.*
8. Kristofovich L. V. *Mollusks of the Tertiary Deposits of Southern Sakhalin (Lower Formations)* // *Mollusks of the Tertiary Deposits of Southern Sakhalin. Leningrad: Gostoptekhizdat, 1954. pp. 5-186. (Proceedings of VNIGRI; Issue 10).*
9. Kristofovich L. V. *Mollusks of the Tertiary Deposits of Sakhalin. Leningrad: Nedra, 1964, 342 p. (Proceedings of VNIGRI; Issue 232).*

10. Merklin. R. L., Nevesskaya L. A. *Key to Genera of Bivalve Mollusks of the Neogene of the USSR (on punched cards)*. Moscow: Nauka, 1974. 213 p.
11. Petrov O. M. *Marine Mollusks of the Anthropogene of the Northern Part of the Pacific Ocean*. Moscow: Nauka, 1982. 141 p.
12. Simonova, A. A. *Fauna of Tertiary Deposits in the Southeastern Part of Soviet Sakhalin*. Leningrad: Gostoptekhizdat, 1941. 79 p. (Tr. NGRI, Series A; Issue 18).
13. Skarlato, O. A. *Bivalves of the Temperate Latitudes of the Western Pacific Ocean*. Leningrad: Nauka, 1981. 480 p.
14. Se'edin, V. T., Lobanov, V. B., Koptev, A. A., Vaschenkova, N. G., Kalinchuk, V. V., Lopatnikov, E. A., Tsoi, I. B., Khudik, V. D. *Results of Geological Surveys during Cruise 58 of the R/V Akademik M. A. Lavrentyev (Central Basin, Sea of Japan)*. *Pacific Geology*, 2014. Vol. 33, No. 3, pp. 99-104.
15. Fot'yanova, L. I. *Cenozoic floras and climate of the Northern Pacific. Fossil flora and fauna of the Far East and issues of Phanerozoic stratigraphy*. Vladivostok: Far Eastern Scientific Center of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1977. P. 65-82.
16. Khudik, V. D. *Bivalve mollusk communities and climate changes in the Miocene of southwestern Sakhalin. Abstract of the 2nd All-Union Conf. on Marine Biology "Biology of shelf zones of the world ocean."* Part 2. Vladivostok: Far Eastern Scientific Center of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1982. P. 48-50.
17. Khudik V. D. *Bivalves of the Miocene of Southwestern Sakhalin*. Vladivostok: Far Eastern Branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1989. 130 p.
18. Amano K. *Paleontological study of the Togeshita molluscan fauna in Rumoi district, Hokkaido* // *Sci. Repts. Inst. Geosci. Tsukuba Univ.* 1983. Sec. B. Vol. 4. P. 1-72.
19. Chinzei K. *Neogene molluscan faunas in the Japanese Islands: An ecologic and zoogeographic synthesis* // *Veliger*, 1978. V. 21, N 2. P. 154-170.
20. Conrad T. A. *Fossils from Northwestern America, in Dana J. D., U. S. Explor. Exped., 1838-1842, under the command of Charles Wilke* // *U.S. N. Geology*, 1849. V. 10. P. 722-728.
21. Conrad T. A. *Catalogue of the older Eocene shells of Oregon* // *Amer. J. Conchology*. 1865. V. 1. P. 150-154.
22. Dall W. H. *Contributions to the Tertiary paleontology of the Pacific coast. 1. The Miocene of Astoria and Coos Bay, Oregon*. 1909. 278 p. (*U. S. Geol. Surv. Prof. Paper* 59).
23. Etherington T. J. *Stratigraphy and fauna of the Astoria Miocene of southwest Washington* // *Calif. Univ. Dept. Geol. Sci. Bull.* 1931. V. 20, N 5. P. 31-142.

24. Goto Y., Poppe G. T. *A list of Living Mollusca. Part II. Vol. 2.* Edited by L'Informatore Piceno Ancona- Italy, 1996. 1031 p.
25. Habe T. *Genera of Japanese Shell. 2. Pelecypoda // Kairui Bunken Kanko-Kai. Kyoto, 1951. P. 97-186.*
26. Hayami I. *Lower Cretaceous marine Pelecipods of Japan. Pt. 11. 1965. 156 p.*
27. Hirayama K. *On some Miocene Species of Lucinoma from Japan, with description of two new species // Japan J. Geol. Geogr. 1954. V.25, N 1-2. P. 101-115.*
28. Kanno S. *The Tertiary system of the Chichibu basin, Saitama prefecture, Central Japan. Part 2. Paleontology // Jap. Soc. Prom. Sci. 1960. P. 123-396.*
29. Kilmer F. H. *History of Pliocene Molluscan Fauna of North Japan // The Veliger, 1978. Vol. 21. No 2. P. 227-231.*
30. Meek F. B. *Check list of the invertebrate fossils of North America, Miocene. 1864. 32 p.*
31. Moore E. J. *Miocene mollusks from the Astoria formation in Oregon. 1963. 109 p. (U. S. Geol. Surv. Paper 419).*
32. Ogasawara K. *Miocene Mollusca from Ishikawa — Toyama area, Japan // Sci. Rep. Tohoku Univ. 1976. Ser. 2. V. 46, N 2. P. 33-78.*
33. Reeve L. A. *Conchologia Iconica. V. 6 Artemis. L. Reeve and Co Ltd., London, 1850. 10 pls.*
34. Scotese C. R., Boucot A. J., Chen Xu, Ruuan Yiping and Fan Junxuan/ *Correlation Between Geologically Marked Climate Changes and Extinction. Earth Sciences Frontiers, 1997. V. 4, No. 3-4. P. 123-128.*
35. Tashiro M. *Nihonno Tuseidai Hakuaku Nimaikai. Tokyo. 1993. 307 p.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.23.38.163

开发和评估针对冠状病毒感染患者的龋齿预防措施的有效性
**DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS
OF CARIES PREVENTION IN PATIENTS WHO HAVE HAD
CORONAVIRUS INFECTION**

Belenova Irina Alexandrovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of Department
Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko*

Tikhonovskaya Karina Sergeevna

*Postgraduate candidate
Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko*

Popova Olesya Borisovna

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko*

Primacheva Natalia Vladimirovna

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko*

Fisenko Sofia Vladimirovna

*Student
Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko*

注释。本研究旨在探讨预测性使用各种预防性口腔卫生产品预防新冠肺炎患者龋齿的可行性。研究方法包括使用不同pH值（酸性和碱性）的口腔卫生产品（牙膏），研究这些产品对口腔液pH值的影响，并同时研究受试者牙釉质的酸溶解度（V. K. Leontyev, V. A. Distel, 1975）。研究对象：分为3组，每组30人，口腔液pH值不同：第1组为弱碱性环境；第2组为中性环境；第3组为酸性环境（有新冠肺炎病史）。该研究的主要结果表明，根据口腔卫生用品的物理化学指标、pH值和口腔液化学成分等因素，采取个性化的口腔卫生用品选择方法，可以提高这些用品对新冠肺炎患者等人群的预防和治疗效果。

关键词：口腔，冠状病毒感染，炎症性牙周疾病，龋齿预防，口腔卫生用品。

Annotation. *The aim of this work was to identify the feasibility of predictive use of various preventive hygiene products to prevent dental caries in patients with a history of covid 19. The method of work consists of using hygiene products (toothpastes)*

with different pH values (acidic and alkaline), studying the effect of these products on the pH of oral fluid, and simultaneously studying the acid solubility of the tooth enamel of the subjects (V.K. Leontyev, V.A. Distel, 1975). Subjects: 3 groups of patients, 30 people each, with different pH values of oral fluid: group 1 — slightly alkalienvironment; group 2 — neutral environment, and group 3 included patients with acidic pH (the patients had a history of covid). The main results of the work showed that an individual approach to the selection of hygiene products, taking into account both their physical and chemical indicators, as well as the pH value and chemical composition of oral fluid, leads to an increase in the preventive and therapeutic properties of these products in relation to patients with covid 19, among others.

Key words: oral cavity, coronavirus infection, inflammatory periodontal diseases, caries prevention, hygiene products.

Introduction. Prevention is a fundamental issue in medicine, particularly in modern dentistry, especially now, when the spread of infectious diseases, which in turn manifest in the oral cavity, is a pressing issue. One such disease is Covid-19 [7,9,11,13,15]. The manifestations of this virus in the oral cavity vary widely, ranging from dry oral mucosa (DOMS) and taste loss to severe damage from various elements. Disruption of the oral microbiome, pH shifts, and a number of other factors lead to increased cariogenicity in COVID-19 patients [1,3,4,6,8,10], necessitating a predictive approach to caries prevention in these patients [2,3,6,7,12,14]. To improve individualized caries prevention, we studied the effects of various oral hygiene products on dental metabolism and the potential for their use as “preventive” agents against increased cariogenicity in the fight against COVID-19 [16,17,18,19].

The aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness of various preventative measures against dental caries in COVID-19 patients.

Materials and Methods: At the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry, we studied 20 toothpastes from various manufacturers, including Oral-B, Sensodyne, Colgate, R.O.C.S., and others. In vitro studies were conducted to examine the effect of oral fluid on pH (using an EV-74 pH meter).

Patients at the N. N. Burdenko VSMU Clinic were also recruited for clinical trials on a voluntary basis (via a preliminary survey). All patients had their oral fluid pH measured. Based on these measurements, three groups of patients with different pH values were formed: Group 1 — slightly alkaline; Group 2 — neutral; and Group 3 — patients with an acidic pH (with a history of COVID-19).

For each group, hygiene products (toothpastes) with different pH values (acidic and alkaline) were selected. pH measurements were taken at various intervals: before brushing, 30 minutes after brushing, and 1 and 2 hours in the morning and evening. In addition, enamel acid solubility was simultaneously studied (V. K. Leontiev, V. A. Distel, 1975): before brushing, 30 minutes after brushing, and 1, 2, and

3 weeks after using the toothpastes. In addition to individual preventative measures, we also considered the method of using LILI (for better activation of metabolic processes in the tooth).

Study results. A series of laboratory tests revealed that when various toothpastes were used in the study groups, some reduced the pH to acidic values, while others either slightly shifted it toward the alkaline side or remained chemically neutral. R.O.C.S. Moisturizing toothpaste demonstrated the best preventative properties in this regard. According to the study results (and use in Group 3, where patients had a history of COVID-19), this toothpaste promoted a shift in pH toward the alkaline side and also demonstrated effective results in relieving dry mouth, a particularly pressing issue for COVID-19 patients.

A study on enamel acid solubility found that alkaline toothpastes, while increasing pH, did not affect enamel solubility, whereas acidic toothpastes (which lowered pH below normal in patients in all three groups) caused increased calcium loss from enamel. The highest calcium loss was recorded at a low baseline pH in patients in Group 3, when using an acidic toothpaste. This suggests that an individualized approach to selecting preventative hygiene products enhances their protective and preventative properties. Laser therapy was also found to significantly enhance the anticaries effect. In the group of patients who received LLLT as an adjunct (before fillings in caries treatment), a 1.5-2-fold decrease in enamel acid solubility for calcium was observed. At later stages of treatment (almost two years later), patients in Group 1 (whose LILI was not used) showed demineralization at the filling-tooth interface, while no such demineralization was detected in Group 2. This suggests the feasibility of its use for sustained preventive and therapeutic effects, including at later stages of treatment.

Conclusions. Thus, based on the study's results, it can be concluded that an individualized approach to selecting hygiene products, taking into account their physicochemical properties, as well as the pH and chemical composition of oral fluid, leads to enhanced preventive and therapeutic properties for these products, including in patients with COVID-19. In particular, good results were observed with the use of R.O.C.S. Moisturizing toothpaste (relevant for COVID-19 patients during both the preventative and recovery periods).

References

1. Belenova I. A., Tikhonovskaya K. S., Morozov A. N., Popova O. B. Analysis of the condition of patients with herpetic manifestations in the mouth against the background of a previous infectious disease (covid 19). A collection of scientific papers dedicated to the founder of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry at Kazan State Medical University, Professor Isaak Mikhailovich Oksman. Kazan, 2025; 78-81. (In Russ.)

2. Belenova I. A., Khryachkov V. I., Popova O. B., Belenova M. S., Moiseeva A. A. Predictive diagnostics of COVID-19 in patients with oral manifestations. In the collection: *Current issues in dentistry. A collection of scientific papers dedicated to the founder of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry at KSMU, Professor Isaac Mikhailovich Oksman. Kazan, 2024; 159-163.*
3. Belenova I. A., Tikhonovskaya K. S., Popova O. B., Azarova O. A., Bulkadarova A. K. Features of the course of herpetic stomatitis against the background of a previous infectious disease (covid 19). In the collection: *Theoretical and practical issues of clinical dentistry. Proceedings of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference. St. Petersburg, 2024; 6-7. (In Russ.)*
4. Belenova I. A., Khryachkov V. I., Popova O. B., Koretskaya I. V., Rusanova T. A., But L. V., Selina S. V. Predictive diagnostics of coronavirus infection covid-19 at a dental appointment. *Institute of Dentistry. 2024; 1(102): 74-76.*
5. Belenova I. A., Khryachkov V. I., Popova O. B., Solovieva A. L., Belenova M. S., Bulkadarova A. K. Manifestations of dental pathology: correlation with the severity of the infection caused by covid-19, long-term results. *Applied information aspects of medicine. 2024; 27(1): 63-68.*
6. Belenova I. A., Popova O. B., Khryachkov V. I. Predictive diagnostics as an important tool in identifying patients with covid-19. In the collection: *Dentistry of the Slavic States. Proceedings of the 16th International Scientific and Practical Conference dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the Honored Doctor of the Russian Federation, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor A. V. Tsymbalistov. Belgorod, 2023; 74-76.*
7. Belenova I. A., Popova O. B., Azarova O. A., Belenova M. S., Sagova D. S. Predictive diagnostics of infectious diseases with manifestations in the oral cavity. *Bulletin of scientific conferences. 2023; 9-2 (97): 10-12.*
8. Gileva O. S., Libik T. V., Gibadullina N. V., Sivak E. Ju., Gavrilenko M. S., Beleva N. S., Zadorina I. I. Key dental challenges during COVID-19 pandemic: oral health monitoring in patients with chronic oral mucosal diseases. *Dentistry. 2021; 100(6-2): 8-15. <https://doi.org/10.17116/stomat20211000628>*
9. Modina T. N., Cinneker D. T., Haritonova M. A., Mahdi Mohajmen Mahmud Mahdi, Mamaeva E. V., Usmanova I. N. SARS-COV-2 in the oral cavity and exacerbation of chronic periodontal pathology in patients with a new coronavirus infection (COVID-19). *Actual problems in dentistry. 2021; 1: 70-75. <https://doi.org/10.18481/2077-7566-20-17-1-70-75>*
10. Makedonova Yu. A., Poroisky S. V., Gavrikova L. M., Afanasyeva O. Yu. [Manifestation of diseases of the oral mucosa in patients who have had COVID-19]. *Proyavlenie zabolevanii slizistoi poloshti rta u bol'nykh, perenesshikh covid-19. Bulletin of VolGMU. 2021; 1 (77): 110-115. DOI 10.19163/1994-9480-2021-1 (77) –110-115. (In Russ.)*

11. Nasibullina A. H., Kabirova M. F., Kabirov I. R., Valishin D. A. Features of the dental status of patients with SARS-COV-2. Actual problems in dentistry. 2021; 17(3):29-34. <https://doi.org/10.18481/2077-7566-21-17-3-29-34>

12. Selina S. V., Smazhko O. A., Makeeva A. V., Lidokhova O. V., Popova O. B. [Clinical features and diagnostics of xerostomia taking into account etiopathogenetic variability]. Klinika i diagnostika kserostomii s uchetoм etiopatogeneticheskoi variativnosti. In the collection: Student Scientific Forum. Proceedings of the International Student Scientific Conference. Edited by N. E. Starchikova, responsible secretary N. I. Moscow, 2023; 45-46.

13. Amorim Dos Santos J., Normando A. G. C., Carvalho da Silva R. L. et al. Oral Manifestations in Patients with COVID-19: A Living Systematic Review. J Dent Res. — 2021; 100(2):141-154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022034520957289>

14. Baig A. M., Khaleeq A., Ali U., Syeda H. Evidence of the COVID-19 virus targeting the CNS: Tissue distribution, host-virus interaction, and proposed neurotropic mechanisms // ACS Chemical Neuroscience. — 2020; 11(7):995-998. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acschemneuro.0c00122>

15. Bhujel N., Zaheer K., Singh R. P. Oral mucosal lesions in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review // Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg. — 2021; S0266-4356(21)00243-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjoms.2021.06.011>

16. De la rocha C., Cid-lópez M. A., Venegas-lópez B. I., Gómez-méndez S. C., Sánchez-ortiz A., Pérez-ríos A. M., Llamas-velázquez R. A., Meza-acuña A. I., Vargas-iñiguez B., Rosales-galván D., Tavares-váldez A., Luna-gudiño N., Hernández-puente C. V., Milenkovic J., Iglesias-palomares C., Méndez-del villar M., Gutiérrez-dieck G. A., Valderrábano-roldán C. G., Mercado-cerda J., Robles-bojórquez J. G. et al. Ivermectin compared with placebo in the clinical course in mexican patients with asymptomatic and mild covid-19: a randomized clinical trial. BMC Infectious Diseases. 2022. T. 22. № 1. C. 1-9. DOI: 10.1186/s12879-022-07890-6.

17. Iranmanesh B., Khalili M., Amiri R., Zartab H., Aflatoonian M. Oral manifestations of COVID-19 disease: A review article // Dermatol Ther. — 2021; 34(1): e14578. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dth.14578>

18. Guo Y., Yuan C., Wei C. Emergency measures for acute oral mucosa diseases during the outbreak of COVID-19 // Oral Dis. — 2021; 27(3):737-739. <https://doi.org/10.1111/odi.13350>

19. Peng X., Xu X., Li Y., Cheng L., Zhou X., Ren B. Transmission routes of 2019-nCoV and controls in dental practice // International Journal of Oral Science. — 2020; 12(1):9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41368-020-0075-9>

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.23.60.146

固定矫形结构修复问题的最新进展
**CURRENT ASPECTS OF THE PROBLEM OF FIXING FIXED
ORTHOPEDIC STRUCTURES**

Andreeva Svetlana Nikolaevna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Full Professor

Russian University of Medicine, Moscow, Russian Federation

Iatsenko Kirill Evgenievich

Orthopedic dentist

Clinic "Care and smile"

Ishkhan Sergeevich Khumoyan

Orthopedic dentist

National Medical Research Center for Otorhinolaryngology of the

Federal Medical-Biological Agency

Mikhail Mikhailovich Andreev

Postgraduate student

Russian University of Medicine, Moscow, Russian Federation

摘要：本研究分析了2020年至2025年间发表的130篇科学论文，重点关注正畸牙科粘接技术应用的趋势和挑战。由于结构材料种类繁多、粘接系统不断更新迭代，以及制造商和研究人员推荐的粘接方案各异，导致固定修复体修复技术多种多样，有时甚至相互矛盾。对于临床医生而言，根据临床情况确定选择特定粘接系统的主要标准是一项挑战。本研究证实，有必要建立一套基于牙体预备程度（粘接于牙本质或牙釉质）、牙齿活力、牙本质结构年龄相关特征、修复体类型等因素的粘接系统选择标准体系。

关键词：粘接方案，固定正畸结构修复，间接牙齿修复

Abstract. *An analysis of 130 scientific articles published from 2020 to 2025, focusing on the trends and challenges in applying the adhesive protocol in orthopedic dentistry, was conducted. The diversity of structural materials, generations of adhesive systems, and protocols recommended by manufacturers and researchers has led to the existence of various, sometimes contradictory, technologies for fixing fixed restorations. For a practicing dentist, it is challenging to determine the primary criteria for selecting a specific adhesive system according to the clinical situation. This study substantiated the need to develop a system of criteria for selecting adhesive systems based on the extent of preparation (fixation on dentin or*

tooth enamel), tooth vitality, age-related characteristics of dentin structure, type of construction, and so forth.

Keywords: *adhesive protocol, fixation of fixed orthopedic structures, indirect tooth restorations*

The twenty-first century has been characterized by a widespread shift in orthopedic dentistry toward aesthetic metal-free structures, dental implant-supported prostheses, and the application of minimally invasive tooth prosthetic methods. The advent of new structural materials and patient expectations for attractive, functional prostheses with minimal tooth preparation has created the need to employ not only mechanical but also chemical (adhesive) retention for the fixation of indirect restorations.

Currently, there are eight generations of adhesive systems, ranging from the three-step, classical IV generation systems (EAR — etch-and-rinse systems) to one- and two-step V-VI generation systems, followed by universal and intelligent VII-VIII generation systems, which allow the use of various fixation protocols (total, selective etching, and self-etching (SE - self-etching systems)) and self-regulate pH.

What is important for the clinician when cementing fixed structures to ensure the long-term survival of dental prostheses? It is necessary to obtain a dissolution-resistant yet thin cement film that is sufficiently strong in bending to withstand masticatory load, with a high degree of thermal stability and good adhesion to both the tooth and crown material, without altering the color of the structure or causing postoperative sensitivity in the abutment teeth. To achieve this, it is important to ensure demineralization of the tooth tissues to the appropriate depth and adequate diffusion of the monomer into the dentin, remove unbound water from the hybrid layer without overdrying it, obtain a uniform, thick hybrid layer, and stabilize it by suppressing the activity of dentin proteolytic enzymes, prevent hydrolytic dehydration of dentin, strengthen the collagen matrix, and so forth. These adhesion mechanisms have been studied in considerable detail for several decades; however, this problem remains far from fully resolved. The scientific literature comprises numerous articles and studies of varying levels of evidence, providing recommendations and justifications for the use of specific adhesive systems and their application protocols.

The aim of our study was to perform a systematic analysis of scientific articles, including a review and meta-analysis of the literature on the topic, to identify the key evaluative criteria most relevant to the prosthodontist when selecting an adhesive system for a particular clinical scenario. The study utilized over 120 articles published in the Scopus, PubMed, and Web of Science databases from 2020 to 2025. (a limited number of references are provided in the bibliography).

Research Results. This study was necessitated by the importance of establishing a simple and clear algorithm for selecting an adhesive system for clinicians during

prosthetic treatment with ceramic, zirconia, metal-ceramic, and composite structures (crowns, veneers, inlays).

The importance of achieving predictably favorable outcomes over a foreseeable extended period compels researchers to continuously seek ways to preserve the hybrid layer that ensures material adhesion. The primary negative factors affecting the hybrid layer are the hydrolytic degradation of the polymer chains of the monomer (adhesive) and autodegradation (destruction of the dentin collagen structure) caused by proteolytic enzymes of the mineralized dentin matrix (matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and cysteine cathepsins) [1,2]. Ensuring optimal dentin moisture is extremely challenging, as is determining the influence of hydrophobic and hydrophilic components of the adhesive on the distribution of monomer within the hybrid layer.

This issue directs *in vivo* and *in vitro* research efforts toward finding solutions that enable control of dentin moisture or prevent negative interactions of the monomer with unbound fluid. This explains the interest in universal adhesive systems, which are less sensitive to application technique, can be applied to both dry and moist dentin, provide comparable bond strength values of 25-30 MPa, and ensure reliable fixation of prostheses made from ceramics, composites, and metals [1]. At the same time, several studies have demonstrated the low effectiveness of universal adhesives after aging when the etching step was omitted [3,4,5]. Studies have shown no differences in outcomes when using universal adhesives with or without an additional etching step, even after long restoration service periods (8 years) [6]. Self-etching cements are recommended for use with universal adhesives, based on the premise that they enhance bond strength, since in self-etching mode the smear layer is only partially demineralized (etched) [7,8,9].

There is no clear consensus on the methodology for applying the etching agent and adhesive. Studies have demonstrated the necessity of passive adhesive application on dentin when using EAR systems to prevent the collapse of collagen fibers. With intact dentin structure, the monomer penetrates better; additionally, there is lower dentin moisture and reduced water release from damaged tubules [10]. However, some authors advocate for active adhesive application, especially with self-etching systems, as they believe it enhances monomer diffusion and modifies the smear layer. Active rubbing mechanically compresses the collagen network like a 'sponge,' which then expands to better absorb the monomer [10]. For adhesion to tooth enamel, passive application is recommended to avoid damaging the enamel prisms.

The selection of self-adhesive cements for the fixation of indirect restorations to dentin, according to researchers, can be justified by their less traumatic effect on dentinal tubules. Because there is no etching or removal of the smear layer, the dentinal tubules are not exposed, which reduces postoperative sensitivity. Furthermore, in the absence of complete demineralization, hydroxyapatite remains, which is essential for the formation of calcium salts with the monomer (10-MDP-Ca

salts). However, there are certain issues with self-adhesive self-etching systems concerning pH regulation and their ability to neutralize after curing. To achieve demineralization of tissues at the initial stage of interaction with the smear layer, low pH values are required. In practice, ultramild ($\text{pH} > 2.5$), mild ($\text{pH} \approx 2$), medium ($\text{pH} 1-2$), and strong ($\text{pH} \leq 1$) adhesive systems are used. Reduction of postoperative tooth sensitivity and the cytotoxic effects of monomer on the pulp of a vital tooth can be achieved using systems with pH values ≥ 2 ; however, this may impair the formation of a complete hybrid layer due to incomplete penetration of the adhesive into the smear layer [1,10]. Research shows that maintaining low pH values over time leads to a decrease in the mechanical properties of the cement film and deterioration of the fixation of the indirect restoration. At the same time, the ability of various self-etching cements to neutralize low pH values (from 1-2 to 6) remains insufficiently studied.

Regarding the application time of the etching agent and the curing methods, there is greater consensus among researchers. All authors agree that the enamel etching time is 15-30 seconds, while the dentin etching time should not exceed 15 seconds and may be reduced to 3 or 10 seconds [11]. Prolonged dentin etching time adversely affects adhesion due to excessive demineralization, removal of calcium essential for bonding with the monomer, and the significant depth of demineralization beyond the adhesive's penetration capacity [11]. Moreover, all experts emphasize the necessity to consider the structural characteristics of dentin in vital and devital teeth, in young and elderly patients, as well as in cariously affected and sclerotic dentin.

In discussions on the curing mode of dual- or triple-cure cements, almost all researchers confirmed that using the light-curing mode, even with considerable structure thickness (over 0.5 mm), improves adhesion strength, imparts thermal stability, and enhances mechanical strength. Moreover, due to the 10- to 20-fold increase in curing speed with the light-curing mode, it is possible to prevent water absorption from dentin [7,12,13].

Such uniformity is absent in studies on methods of immediate or delayed dentin sealing during the fixation of fixed prostheses [14,15,16]. Manufacturers' recommendations typically specify the possibility of separate curing of the adhesive and cement. Several studies support the benefits of preliminary adhesive curing, as it enhances bond strength. However, other studies show that adhesive curing should be avoided to prevent increasing the thickness of the cement film.

Thus, the analysis of scientific literature has shown that despite the extensive publications and the keen interest in issues related to the adhesive fixation of indirect restorations in dentistry, as well as the diversity of studies concerning the characteristics examined and observation periods, many questions remain about the choice of adhesive system type and the methodology for performing procedures depending on the extent of tooth preparation, the type of prosthetic structure, the

condition of the dental hard tissues, and so forth. The variety of theories and recommendations often complicates the work of the prosthodontist. Undoubtedly, further advancements in the field of adhesive fixation of fixed orthopedic structures will enhance the understanding of these processes.

References

1. Breschi L., Maravic T., Mazzitelli C., Josic U., Mancuso E., Cadenaro M., et al. *The evolution of adhesive dentistry: from etch-and-rinse to universal bonding systems*. *Dental Materials*. 2025;41(2):141-158.
2. Tsujimoto A, Fischer NG, Barkmeier WW, Latta MA. *Bond durability of two-step HEMA-free universal adhesive*. 2022;13:134 *J Funct Biomaterials*. 2022;13:134. <https://doi.org/10.3390/JFB13030134>.
3. Scarabello Stape TE., Mutluay M., Tezvergil-Mutluay A. *To etch or not to etch, Part III: On the hydrophobic-rich content and fatigue strength of universal adhesives after long-term ageing*. 2025;40:44-52.
4. Stape THS, Viita-aho T, Sezinando A, Mutluay M, Tezvergil-Mutluay A. *To etch or not to etch, Part I: on the fatigue strength and dentin bonding performance of universal*. *Dental Materials*. 2022;37:949-960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2021.02.016>.
5. Stape THS, Viita-aho T, Sezinando A, Seseogullari-Dirihan R, Eleftheriadi E, Mutluay M, et al. *To etch or not to etch, Part II: on the hydrophobic-rich content and fatigue strength of universal adhesives*. *Dental Materials*. 2022;38:1419-1431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2021.02.016>.
6. Tian F., Mu H., Shi Y., Chen X., Zou X., Gao X., Wang X. *Clinical evaluation of Giomer and self-etch adhesive compared with nanofilled resin composite and etch-and-rinse adhesive — Results at 8 years*. *Dental Materials*. 2024;40:1088-1095.
7. Aoki R, Takamizawa T, Hayashi K, Arai Y, Ishii R, Shoji M, Kamimoto A., Miyazaki M.. *Influence of different curing modes on the bonding effectiveness of self-adhesive resin luting cements in combination with universal adhesives*. *Dental Materials*. 2024;40:379-385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2023.12.016>.
8. Miotti LL, Follak AC, Montagner AF, Pozzobon RT, da Silveira BL, Susin AH. *Is conventional resin cement adhesive performance to dentin better than self-adhesive? A systematic review and meta-analysis of laboratory studies*. *Oper Dent*. 2020;45:484-495. <https://doi.org/10.2341/19-153-L>.

9. Scholz KJ, Tabenski IM, Vogl V, Cieplik F, Schmalz G, Buchalla W, Hiller KA, Federlin M. Randomized clinical split-mouth study on the performance of CAD/ CAM-partial ceramic crowns luted with a self-adhesive resin cement or a universal adhesive and a conventional resin cement after 39 months. *J Dentis*. 2021;115: 103837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdent.2021.103837>.

10. Carvalho GLM, Moreira PM, Carneiro BT, Suzuki TYU, Lanza MDS, Alvim HH, et al. Impact of active vs. passive application of dental adhesives on bond strength to dentin and enamel: A systematic review and meta-analysis of in vitro studies. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev*. 2025;61:90-102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdsr.2025.04.001>.

11. Souza J., Naupari-Villasante R., Hass V., Arana-Gordillo LA., Guti' errez MF., Gomes GM., Loguercio AD., Gomes JC. Optimizing phosphoric acid etching times across different formulations: Impact on dentin structure, roughness, and adhesive performance after 4 years. *Dental Materials*. 2025;41:850-861.

12. Takamizawa T., Shibasaki S., Latta MA., Kasahara Y., Barkmeier WW., Suzuki S., Miyazaki M.. Universal adhesive application and curing mode affect shear bond strength and shear fatigue bond strength of self-adhesive resin luting cements to dentin. *Dental Materials*. — 2025;4:1213-1221.

13. Benkeser SM, Karlin S, Rohr N. Effect of curing mode of resin composite cements on water sorption, color stability, and biaxial flexural strength. *Dental Materials*. 2024; 40:897-906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2024.04.004>.

14. Ramosa RQ., Mercelis B., Ahmed MH., Camargo dos Santos B., Carpena Lopes G., Meerbeek BV., Peumans M. Impact of immediate versus delayed dentin sealing on adhesive luting effectiveness. *Dental Materials*. 2025;41:994-1007.

15. Oda Y, Takahashi R, Nikaido T, Tagami J. Influence of the resin-coating technique on the bonding performance of self-adhesive resin cements in single-visit computer-aided design/computer-aided manufacturing resin restorations. *J Esthet Restor Dent* 2022;34(4):721-728. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jerd.12818>.

16. Ding J, Jin Y, Feng S, Chen H, Hou Y, Zhu S. Effect of temporary cements and their removal methods on the bond strength of indirect restoration: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Invest* 2023;27(1):15-30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-022-04790-6>.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.23.70.099

严重合并性创伤性脑损伤患儿的平均动脉压昼夜节律
**CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF MEAN ARTERIAL PRESSURE
IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN
INJURY**

Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Full Professor

*Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical
Workers*

Dadabayeva Erkinoy Isakjanovna

Resuscitator

*Namangan Branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency
Medical Care*

Fathulayeva Dildora Murojon kizi

Anesthesiologist-resuscitator

Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care

摘要：在第2组中，观察到平均动脉压（MAP）昼夜节律的平均值下降至正常范围。创伤性脑损伤（TBI）的严重程度显著影响了严重联合创伤性脑损伤（SCTBI）综合治疗的效果，因此有必要改进第3亚组儿童的治疗方案。第2组平均动脉压（MAP）振幅和昼夜节律波动的相对更显著的变化，可能是由于更温和的应激保护性矫正，使得包括血管系统在内的所有系统在术后适应性反应中，代偿机制能够更积极地发挥作用。在两组的所有亚组中，均观察到平均动脉压（MAP）与舒张压（DAD）之间存在显著的正相关性，这支持了以下论断：在儿童严重联合创伤性脑损伤中，舒张压（DAD）的变化主要影响MAP水平。

关键词：昼夜节律，平均动脉压，严重联合创伤性脑损伤，儿童。

Abstract. *In Group 2, a decrease in mesor to the normal range of the circadian rhythm of MAP was observed. The severity of TBI significantly influenced the effectiveness of comprehensive treatment of SCTBI and necessitates improvement of therapy in children of subgr 3. Possibly, the comparatively more pronounced changes in the amplitude and circadian fluctuations of mean arterial pressure (MAP) in group 2 may result from a gentler stress-protective correction, enabling more active involvement of compensatory mechanisms in the ongoing adaptive responses of all systems, including the vascular system, during the postoperative*

period. A strong positive correlation between mean arterial pressure (MAP) and diastolic arterial pressure (DAD) was observed in all subgroups of both groups, supporting the assertion that changes in DAD predominantly influence MAP levels in SCTBI in children.

Keywords: *circadian rhythm, mean arterial pressure, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.*

Relevance

In severe traumatic brain injury (TBI), mean arterial pressure (MAP) must be maintained at a level **above 90 mm Hg**. To ensure adequate cerebral blood flow (cerebral perfusion pressure — CPP) and prevent ischemia and neuronal death, since autoregulation mechanisms are impaired and cerebral blood flow becomes directly dependent on blood pressure. Correction of arterial hypotension in patients with severe traumatic brain injury should be performed based on an assessment of all components of hemodynamics, taking into account individual variability of changes at each stage of the disease. Some authors consider it necessary to maintain the mean arterial pressure (MAP) at no less than 80 mmHg. To achieve target MAP values, various infusion solutions, vasopressor, and inotropic agents or their combinations are used. At the same time, irrational use of vasopressor drugs may lead to damage related to vasoconstriction and impaired microcirculation, while excessive volumes of infusion therapy can result in pulmonary, intestinal edema, etc. [1-3]. According to the authors, MAP in children aged 3-7 years is 73-77 mmHg, and in those aged 8-15 years, it is 80-86 mmHg. Age-adjusted mean arterial pressure in healthy children is 79 ± 4 mmHg [4].

Objective

To study and assess changes in the circadian rhythm of mean arterial pressure in children with SCTBI.

Materials and Methods

Data from monitoring children receiving inpatient treatment at RNCEPM for SCTBI were analyzed: from 2016 to 2021 (Group 1), and from 2022 to 2024 (Group 2). Children in group 1 were admitted to the clinic due to road traffic accidents (23) and falls from height (11); in group 2, road traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, with polytrauma in 5 children. In both groups, parameters were analyzed within 3 subgroups: subgroup 1, where conservative therapy was administered due to the absence of indications for surgical intervention; subgroup 2, consisting of children who underwent extracranial surgeries; and subgroup 3, which included patients who underwent cranial and extracranial surgeries within the first day after admission to the clinic. Patients in group 1, subgroup 1 (13),

received conservative therapy as indicated; children in subgroup 2 (16) underwent extracranial corrective surgeries within the first hours as indicated; 8 patients in subgroup 3 underwent simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions upon admission to the clinic, involving a neurosurgeon, abdominal surgeon, and traumatologist. In group 2, 13 children received conservative therapy, 16 patients underwent extracranial surgeries, and 8 children had combined cranial and extracranial surgeries. No significant age differences were found between the groups. In group 1, boys predominated in subgroups 3 and 2, accounting for 29% and 26%, respectively. Whereas in subgroup 1, girls predominated, accounting for 23%. In group 2, boys predominated in subgroups 1, 2, and 3, accounting for 24%, 24%, and 19%, respectively. Thus, in almost all subgroups, boys somewhat predominated. No statistically significant differences in injury severity or the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency at admission to the clinic were observed between the subgroups of group 1. A certain tendency toward a decrease in the severity of traumatic injuries in group 2 by subgroups was observed. Thus, differences in subgroup 1 amounted to 25% (>0.05), in subgroup 2-44% ($p<0.05$), and in subgroup 3-27% ($p<0.05$). As the condition improved, with stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and restoration of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department. No significant differences in the severity of acute cerebral insufficiency, as measured by the Glasgow scale, were identified between groups and subgroups. The observed difference in injury severity according to the ISS scale between the 2nd and 3rd subgroups of the 2nd group can be attributed to the effectiveness of implementing prehospital care following the 'golden hour' principle, which minimizes prehospital time in trauma cases. Hourly monitoring of hemodynamic parameters enabled the study and evaluation of changes in the circadian rhythm parameters of mean arterial pressure (MAP), along with a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of corrective surgical interventions and conservative treatment in children aged 3 to 18 years.

Results and Discussion

During the first 7 days, a statistically significant difference was observed between the groups in mesor, acrophase, and bathyphase indicators (Table 1). Specifically, in patients of Group 2, Subgroup 2, the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP was 7% lower than in Group 1, with MAP values at acrophase 10% lower and at bathyphase 11% lower ($p < 0.05$, respectively).

Moreover, in the 3 subgr of group 2, a decrease in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP by 11% and in the level of MAP at bathyphase by 11% was identified ($p<0.05$, respectively). The identified differences indicate more effective stress-limiting therapy in the 2nd and 3rd subgroups of the 2nd SCTBI group during the first 7 days.

Table 1. Comparative assessment of mean values of the circadian rhythm of MAP during the first 7 days

Indicators	1 gr 1 subgr 7 days	2 gr 1 subgr 7 days	1 gr 2 subgr 7 days	2 gr 2 subgr 7 days	1 gr 3 subgr 7 days	2 gr 3 subgr 7 days
Mesor	80±2	77±3	83±2	76±2*	86±1	77±3*
At acrophase	83±3	85±4	89±4	80±2*	92±2	86±7
At bathyphase	74±3	71±3	78±2	69±5*	81±1	70±3*
Amplitude	4±1	8±4	6±3	4±1	6±2	9±4
Daily fluctuations	10±4	14±6	11±4	11±5	11±2	16±5

*-difference is significant relative to the indicator in group 1

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the mean values of the circadian rhythm of MAP during treatment in the ICU

Indicators	1 gr 1 subgr 26 days	2 gr 1 subgr 29 days	1 gr 2 subgr 30 days	2 gr 2 subgr 21 days	1 gr 3 subgr 30 days	2 gr 3 subgr 28 days
Mesor	81±2	80±3	83±2	77±2*	88±3	84±7
At acrophase	87±3	90±5	89±4	83±3	93±4	100±11
At bathyphase	75±2	72±3	78±2	70±3*	82±3	70±7
Amplitude	6±2	9±3	6±3	6±2	6±2	15±7
Range of fluctuations	11±3	18±5	11±4	13±4	11±3	29±12*

* — significant difference relative to the indicator in group 1

A significant decrease in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP was identified in group 2 by 6%, and the MAP value in the bathyphase by 10%. Signs of less effective intensive stress-limiting therapy were observed in the most severe subgr 3 of group 2, where the daily fluctuations of mean arterial pressure (MAP) increased by 163% ($p < 0.05$). Thus, despite the achieved effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy during the first 7 days in subgr 3, excessive daily fluctuations of MAP during prolonged intensive therapy up to 30 days corresponded to insufficient treatment efficacy in children of subgr 3 (Table 2). Meanwhile, significant positive dynamics were observed in subgr 2 of group 2.

Table 3. Dynamics of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP

Days	1 gr 1 subgr	2 gr 1 subgr	1 gr 2 subgr	2 gr 2 subgr	1 gr 3 subgr	2 gr 3 subgr
1	78±3	74±6	81±6	76±3	88±3 ^{'''}	79±4 [°]
2	76±1	71±2	77±1	72±2	85±2 ^{'''}	76±2 [°]
3	79±2	76±2	78±1	74±2	86±2 ^{'''}	71±3 [°]
4	82±2	79±2	82±2	78±2	85±2	77±3 [°]
5	80±2	81±2	83±2	79±2	85±2 ^{'''}	74±2 [°]
6	82±2	76±2	83±1	77±2	85±2	85±4
7	80±2	81±4	83±1	77±2	87±2 ^{'''}	80±4 [°]
8	80±3	76±2	80±1	78±2	88±2 ^{'''}	84±5
9	80±1	75±3	80±1	77±3	95±2 ^{'''}	90±5
10	81±2	78±4	79±2	76±4	91±2 ^{'''}	93±5
11	82±2	79±2	80±2	74±2	89±2 ^{'''}	93±8
12	81±2	80±4	82±1	83±4	90±2 ^{'''}	84±2 [°]
13	77±2	77±3	80±2	79±3	87±3 ^{'''}	91±5
14	80±2	80±4	82±1	79±2	89±2 ^{'''}	98±5 [°]
15	81±2	79±4	84±1	77±3	89±2 ^{'''}	102±4 [°]
16	80±2	80±6	86±2	77±2	90±2 ^{'''}	89±3
17	83±2	82±4	82±2	77±2	86±2	81±4
18	82±2	84±4	85±2	78±2	87±2 ^{'''}	83±5
19	87±3 [*]	80±4	91±3 [*]	76±3	83±2	77±12
20	82±3	80±4	91±2 [*]	72±4	80±3	70±4
21	78±3	84±4	82±3		84±4	79±8
22	86±4 [*]	88±6 [*]	83±1		81±3	93±9 [*]
23	87±3 [*]	81±6	82±2		85±2	84±14
24	80±3	80±4	82±2		85±2	75±10
25	80±2	79±4	87±2		85±2	90±12
26	81±3	89±4	88±4		84±2	74±11
27		88±6	86±3		96±3	86±9
28		87±3	85±2		93±4	102±19
29		87±4	83±3		92±4	
30			86±4		98±2	

* — significantly different from the value on day 1.

''' — significantly different from the value in group 1.

° — significantly different from the value in subgroup 3 of group 1.

No deviations from the norm of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP were detected during the first 24 hours. During monitoring, a tendency to increase was observed dynamically in subgroup 1 of group 1 on days 19, 22, and 23, by

11%. In subgroup 1 of group 2, an increase in the indicator by 19% was observed on day 22. Thus, no significant differences between the groups were observed during dynamic monitoring in the ICU. In group 1, subgr 2, an increase in the mesor was observed on days 19 and 20 by 12%. In contrast, during extracranial surgeries, no tendency to increase the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP was noted throughout the entire observation period, unlike in group 1. Therefore, after 18 days, a significant tendency to increase the mesor of MAP by more than 10% is observed. This finding is associated with the addition of factors negatively affecting intracerebral hemodynamics, one of the main being bacterial flora mutation with the emergence of resistant forms against a background of several unfavorable factors leading to decreased immune resistance in children with SCT-BI under prolonged mechanical ventilation. A comparative analysis of differences according to injury severity (between subgroups) revealed, as early as the first day, a significantly higher mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP in the 3rd subgroup compared to the first subgroup by 11% ($p < 0.05$), and by 8% compared to the 2nd subgroup ($p > 0.05$). This significant increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP persisted until the 18th day. In the subsequent days of observation, the difference diminished due to an increase in the mesor of MAP in the 1st subgroup. It is known that the primary causes of increased mean arterial pressure (MAP) are ischemia of the injured brain and elevated intracranial pressure (ICP) during the first hours after trauma, leading to reduced capillary blood flow and exacerbation of ischemia up to irreversible damage.

Fig. 1 Amplitude of the circadian rhythm of MAP 1 subgroup

Fig. 2 Amplitude of the circadian rhythm of MAP 2 subgroup

Fig. 3 Amplitude of the circadian rhythm of MAP 3 subgroup

Notably, during the first 10 days, the mesor of the circadian rhythm of MAP was on average 10% significantly lower than that in subgr 3 of group 1, indicating more effective stress-limiting comprehensive intensive therapy. However, in the two remaining children in the ICU, instability with a tendency toward an increase in the studied parameter was observed in the following days. Thus, the most effective and optimistic results of comprehensive treatment in children with SCTBI are observed during the first 10 days, when treatment optimization may be more effective with maximal positive effects on brain trophism, aimed at restoring cognitive and other brain functions, thereby optimizing the outcomes of comprehensive intensive therapy for SCTBI in children.

In the 1 subgroup of non-operated injured children, the amplitude of the circadian rhythm of MAP changed within 6 ± 2 mmHg, whereas in the 2 subgroup this parameter was 9 ± 3 mmHg (Fig. 1).

Fig. 4. Daily fluctuations of mean arterial pressure in the 1st subgr.

Fig. 5. Daily fluctuations of mean arterial pressure in the 2nd subgr.

Fig. 6. Daily fluctuations of mean arterial pressure in the 3rd subgr.

In the 2 subgroup of injured patients from group 1, a more pronounced unstable hemodynamic state was observed on the first day, which did not significantly affect the mean amplitude of MAP in patients who underwent extracranial surgeries, with amplitude values of MAP of 6 ± 3 mmHg in group 1 and 6 ± 2 mmHg in group 2 (Fig. 2). A significantly more pronounced difference between the groups was observed in children who underwent cranial and extracranial surgeries. Thus, the amplitudes in the 3rd subgr of group 1 were 6 ± 2 mmHg, and in group 2, 15 ± 7 mmHg (Fig. 3). The increase in the amplitude of the circadian rhythm of mean arterial pressure in the 3rd subgr was 150% ($p < 0.05$).

More pronounced hemodynamic instability was predominant in all three subgroups of group 2. The most pronounced difference was observed in children of

the 3rd subgroup, amounting to 11 ± 3 mmHg in group 1 and 29 ± 12 mmHg in group 2 (Fig. 6). A somewhat less pronounced difference was found in the 1st subgroup, where the daily range of MAP fluctuations was 11 ± 3 mmHg in group 1 and 18 ± 5 mmHg in group 2 (Fig. 4). The least pronounced difference was observed in the 2 subgroups. Thus, in group 1, fluctuations of mean arterial pressure over 24 hours amounted to 11 ± 4 mmHg, while in group 2 they were 13 ± 4 mmHg (Fig. 5). Therefore, the daily instability of peripheral vascular tone predominated in the injured children of group 2 across all subgroups. The obtained results may be attributed to less pronounced sedative and stress-protective therapy, more severe trauma, or better preservation and implementation of compensatory remodeling of cardiovascular function during adaptation under conditions of more severe brain injury in SCTBI. The obtained results corresponded to the severity of the injury and the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency at admission. Thus, in group 1, subgroup 1 had an ISS of 33.7 ± 5.8 , subgroup 2- 40.5 ± 6.5 , and subgroup 3- 41.3 ± 4.6 points. In group 2, the ISS values in subgroups 2 and 3 were significantly lower than those in group 1 by 45% and 27%, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Therefore, the relatively more pronounced changes in the amplitude and circadian variation of mean arterial pressure in group 2 may be attributed to a more sparing stress-protective correction, which allowed greater involvement of compensatory mechanisms in the ongoing adaptive responses of all systems, including the vascular system, during the postoperative period of SCTBI in children.

Fig. 7. Correlation. Correlations by subgroups.

Fig. 8. Correlations by subgroups.

In all subgroups of the first group, a strong positive dependence of mean arterial pressure (MAP) on the level of DAD was revealed, which weakened in the 1st subgroup while retaining the slope of the direct dependence of MAP on DAD. A slight trend of negative correlation was detected between DAD and PAD in the 1st and 3rd subgroups during the first 10 days of treatment. The detected trend persisted in the 1st and 3rd subgroups on days 11-30 of intensive therapy (Fig. 7). In the 2nd group of injured children, a strong positive correlation between MAP and DAD (0.8, respectively) was also identified in all subgroups. The slope of the direct correlation between changes in DAD and PAD in the 3rd subgroup throughout the entire observation period became somewhat restructured and positive. The slope of the direct dependence of mean arterial pressure on PAD became positive in the 2nd and 3rd subgroups during days 11-30 of treatment in the ICU (Fig. 8). The identified features suggest that hemodynamic changes are predominantly influenced by alterations in DAD rather than PAD in SCTBI in children.

Conclusion. In group 2, a reduction in mesor to the norm of the circadian rhythm of MAP was observed. The severity of TBI significantly influenced the effectiveness of comprehensive treatment of SCTBI and necessitates improvement of therapy in children of subgr 3. Possibly, the comparatively more pronounced changes in the amplitude and circadian fluctuations of mean arterial pressure (MAP) in group 2 may result from a gentler stress-protective correction, enabling more active involvement of compensatory mechanisms in the ongoing adaptive responses of all systems, including the vascular system, during the postoperative period. In all subgroups of both groups, a strong direct correlation between the MAP value and DAD level was identified, indicating the predominant influence of DAD changes on MAP levels in SCTBI in children.

References

1. Sychev A. A., Savin I. A., Baranich A. I., Danilov G. V., Strunina Yu. V., Oshorov A. V., Polupan A. A. *Assessment of the hemodynamic profile of patients in the acute period of severe traumatic brain injury. Anesthesiology and Reanimatology.* 2023;(3): 32-36 <https://www.mediasphera.ru/issues/anestziologiya-i-reanimatologiya>
2. Lekmanov A. U., Azovsky D. K., Ponomareva N. A. *Myths and reality of transpulmonary thermodilution in children. Anesthesiology and Resuscitation.* 2021;1:60-64. <https://doi.org/10.17116/anaesthesiology202101160>

3. Samokhvalov I. M., Gavrilin S. V., Meshakov D. P., Nedomolkin S. V., Badalov V. I., Suvorov V. V., Suprun T. Yu., Sokhranov M. V., Smirnov S. A. Features of hemodynamic monitoring in patients with severe combined trauma. *Bulletin of Anesthesiology and Resuscitation*. 2015; 12(3): 34-40. <https://doi.org/10.21292/2078-5658-2015-12-3-34-40>
4. <https://share.google/7c7fxnbe1xi3dn>

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.24.51.150

对重度合并创伤性脑损伤儿童的卒中量昼夜节律进行比较评估
**COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM
OF STROKE VOLUME IN CHILDREN WITH SEVERE COMBINED
TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY**

Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Full Professor

*Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications
of Medical Personnel*

Nasimov Sobir Tahirovich

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Neurosurgeon

Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care

摘要。在亚组3中，严重创伤性脑损伤（TBI）相关矫正手术后持续性脑缺血以及颅内和颅外损伤引起的全身炎症反应，最显著的代偿性心脏功能反应表现为平均心率变异性搏出量（CR SV）增加32%。亚组1中体温与SV呈显著负相关（-0.78），表明高热反应对心脏功能有不利影响，这为积极开展抗炎退热保守治疗以预防急性心力衰竭提供了理论依据。儿童严重联合性创伤性脑损伤（SCTBI）患者CR SV振幅增加超过8 ml（平均超过15%）以及SV日波动超过16 ml（超过30%）应被视为促进急性心肌能量不足并增加急性心力衰竭风险的因素。

关键词：昼夜节律，搏出量，严重联合性创伤性脑损伤，儿童。

Abstract. In subgroup 3, the most pronounced compensatory cardiac function response to persistent brain ischemia after corrective surgeries related to severe TBI and systemic inflammatory response to cranial and extracranial injuries was shown by a 32% increase in mesor CR SV. A strong negative correlation (-0.78) between body temperature and SV in subgroup 1 indicated the detrimental effect of hyperthermic response on cardiac function, serving as a rationale for active anti-inflammatory antipyretic conservative therapy aimed at preventing the risk of acute heart failure. An increase in the amplitude of CR SV by more than 8 ml (on average by over 15%), and daily fluctuations of SV by 16 ml (exceeding 30%) in SCTBI in children should be considered a factor promoting acute myocardial energy deficiency with an elevated risk of acute heart failure.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, stroke volume, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.

Relevance

Based on the understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms of cerebral injury, two approaches to urgent interventions are currently recognized for acute cerebral insufficiency caused by SCTBI: restoration of cerebral perfusion, neuroprotective therapy, and timely correction of extracranial homeostasis disturbances. Extracranial complications typically develop during the patient's stay in the intensive care unit in the treatment of TBI. These complications can impact both mortality and neurological outcomes in patients with TBI. Among these extracranial complications, cardiac injury is relatively common, affecting approximately 25-35% of patients with TBI. The pathophysiology underlying cardiac injury in TBI involves a complex interplay between the brain and the heart. Acute cerebral injury induces a systemic inflammatory response and catecholamine release, resulting in the release of neurotransmitters and cytokines. These substances exert deleterious effects on the brain and peripheral organs, creating a vicious cycle that exacerbates brain injury and cellular dysfunction. In addition to secondary brain injuries such as intracranial hypertension, seizures, and tissue hypoxia, various extracranial complications may arise following TBI, depending on its severity, which in turn can further impair cerebral hemodynamics, leading to secondary tissue hypoxia and brain injury. These post-traumatic extracranial complications affect the respiratory system (neurogenic pulmonary edema, ventilator-associated pneumonia), coagulation (increased local release of tissue factor with a high risk of thrombosis, disseminated coagulopathy), as well as the liver and/or kidneys (acute kidney injury, hypoxic hepatitis). Moreover, cardiac injury following TBI is a relatively common complication with a complex pathophysiology that may potentially contribute to the high mortality of patients with TBI. The most common manifestations of cardiac injury in TBI are prolongation of the corrected QT interval (QTc) and supraventricular arrhythmias, the prevalence of which is 5-10 times higher than in the general adult population. Other forms of cardiac injury have also been described, such as regional wall motion abnormalities, elevated troponin levels, myocardial stunning, or Takotsubo cardiomyopathy (a non-ischemic cardiomyopathy typically affecting the apex of the left ventricle) [1-5]. Due to the lack of information on the characteristics of stroke volume (SV) changes in severe combined traumatic brain injury in children, we aimed to investigate alterations in the structure of phase characteristics and to evaluate the circadian rhythm response of stroke volume to severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Objective of the study

To study and provide a comparative assessment of changes in the circadian rhythm of stroke volume in children with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods of the study

Thirty-six children (group 1), hospitalized at RNCEPM between 2016 and 2021, and 35 children (group 2) admitted in 2023-2024 due to severe combined TBI, were admitted to the clinic following traffic accidents (30) and falls from height (5). Patients in both groups were divided into three subgroups. Injured patients of group 1 were studied in randomized subgroups: in subgroup 1 (13 patients), conservative therapy was administered based on indications; in subgroup 2 (14 patients), extracranial surgical corrective procedures were performed within the first hours as indicated; and 8 patients in subgroup 3 underwent, upon admission to the clinic and based on indications, simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions involving a neurosurgeon, abdominal surgeon, and traumatologist. Patients in group 2 were distributed in subgroup 1 as follows: 13 children without surgery, 14 patients underwent extracranial surgeries, and 8 children underwent combined cranial and extracranial surgeries. No significant differences in age were observed between the groups. With the improvement of condition, stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and recovery of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1. Comparative assessment of the mean parameters of the phase structure of CR SV

Groups	Mesor	In the acrophase	In the bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1 Subgroup 1 10 days	55±1	64±3	48±2	9±3	16±3
Group 2 Subgroup 1 10 days	49±5	58±4	40±5*	9±3	18±4
Group 1 Subgroup 2 10 days	53±1	64±9	45±3	11±8	19±10
Group 2 Subgroup 2 10 days	46±2*	57±5	37±4*	11±4	20±5
Group 1 Subgroup 3 10 days	56±2	64±2	48±4	8±1	17±3
Group 2 Subgroup 3 10 days	63±5	78±7*	50±6	14±3*	28±7*
Group 1 Subgroup 1 26 days	55±3	66±6	46±3	10±4	19±7
Group 2 Subgroup 1 29 days	46±6	58±7	35±6*	12±4	23±6
Group 1 Subgroup 2 30 days	53±3	65±7	44±4	12±6	21±8
Group 2 Subgroup 2 21 days	46±2*	58±6	35±4*	12±5	23±8
Group 1 Subgroup 3 30 days	55±3	64±4	46±4	9±3	18±4
Group 2 Subgroup 3 28 days	61±4	81±8*	46±7	20±8*	35±11*

* — significant difference relative to the indicator in group 1.

A significantly lower mesor CR SV by 13% was identified during the first 10 days and at 21 days ($p<0.05$, respectively) of the day in subgroup 2 of group 2 of

injured children. The SV value in the acrophase was increased by 22% and by 26% in subgroup 3 of group 2 at 10 and 28 days ($p<0.05$, respectively). However, in subgroup 1 of group 2 during the first 10 days, the minimal SV value was 16% lower than in group 1 ($p<0.05$) and 17% lower than in subgroup 2 ($p<0.05$). During treatment in the ICU, the SV value in the bathyphase of children from the 1st subgroup in the 2nd group was 24% lower than in the 1st group ($p<0.05$), and 20% lower than in the 2nd subgroup ($p<0.05$). The amplitude of CR SV during the first 10 days was 87% higher in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group compared to the 1st group. Over 28 days of intensive therapy, the amplitude of CR SV remained 122% higher in the 2nd group than in the 1st group ($p<0.05$). The daytime fluctuations of SV in the circadian rhythm in group 2 were also greater than in group 1 during the first 10 days and for 28 days in subgroup 3 by 64% and 99%, respectively ($p<0.05$). Thus, a decrease in the average mesor level and SV value during the bathyphase was observed in subgroup 2. In contrast, SV during the acrophase was increased in subgroup 3. This resulted in increased amplitude and daily range of fluctuations of CR SV in subgroup 3 of group 2. The findings indicated a decrease in the mesor and SV during the bathyphase, and an increase in SV during the acrophase, amplitude, and range of fluctuations in the CR SV in the 3rd subgroup of the 2nd group, corresponding to varying manifestations of stress-induced cardiac output remodeling during adaptation to post-traumatic stress (Table 1).

Table 2. Comparative assessment of mesor CR SV in two groups

Days	1st subgroup		Subgroup 2		Subgroup 3	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
1	56±4	58±5	57±7	49±4 ^{'''}	51±4	51±8
2	57±3	59±2	54±3	51±3	56±3	64±4 ^{'''}
3	56±4	51±3	52±2	49±2	61±3	71±6 ^{'''}
4	55±2	48±3 ^{'''}	51±3	44±3 ^{'''}	61±2	69±3 ^{'''}
5	55±2	47±2 ^{'''}	55±3	42±2 ^{'''}	60±2	57±3
6	54±3	51±4	54±2	46±4 ^{'''}	57±3	59±5
7	54±2	45±4* ^{'''}	52±3	44±3 ^{'''}	56±3	69±6 ^{'''}
8	53±4	44±2* ^{'''}	53±2	45±3 ^{'''}	56±4	66±9
9	55±2	43±3* ^{'''}	51±3	43±4 ^{'''}	55±3	64±7
10	56±3	42±4* ^{'''}	53±3	45±4 ^{'''}	52±4	64±8 ^{'''}
11	52±4	44±4* ^{'''}	57±4	48±4 ^{'''}	52±4	57±7
12	51±2	44±4* ^{'''}	57±4	45±5 ^{'''}	57±4	56±5
13	51±3	66±6 ^{'''}	57±4	46±4 ^{'''}	55±4	62±5
14	53±3	46±6*	54±4	48±2	53±3	62±9
15	50±2	42±5* ^{'''}	53±2	50±4	52±3	58±6

Days	1st subgroup		Subgroup 2		Subgroup 3	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
1	56±4	58±5	57±7	49±4 ^{'''}	51±4	51±8
16	52±3	45±5*	51±3	45±4	54±2	64±5 ^{'''}
17	52±4	44±5*	49±4	46±4	59±3	58±5
18	52±4	42±3 ^{'''}	44±4	42±3	53±2	57±5
19	55±5	39±5 ^{'''}	55±5	51±4	55±3	64±5
20	59±5	39±4 ^{'''}	54±3	48±7	56±5	63±8
21	59±3	39±3 ^{'''}	58±3	49±15	59±4	65±8
22	53±5	40±5 ^{'''}	57±3		59±5	56±11
23	56±4	41±6 ^{'''}	51±3		50±2	62±9
24	62±5	30±4 ^{'''}	55±5		58±4	62±11
25	71±7	32±5	51±5		54±3	52±6
26	62±8	53±6	49±7		52±4	63±8
27		49±8	49±4		51±5	58±11
28		50±6	51±4		52±5	55±8
29		55±5	52±4		53±7	
30			49±4		40±3	

* — difference is significant relative to the value on day 1.

In Group 1 children, across all three subgroups, the average mesor CR SV for the entire period of intensive care in the ICU was 55±3 ml in subgroup 1, 53±3 ml in subgroup 2, and 55±3 ml in subgroup 3. In subgroup 1 of Group 1, no significant changes in mesor CR SV were observed throughout the observation period, whereas in Group 2 the mean mesor SV values were 46±6 ml in subgroup 1, 46±2 ml in subgroup 2, and 61±4 ml in subgroup 3; consequently, the studied indicator in subgroup 3 was significantly higher than in subgroup 1 by 32% and by 32% higher than in subgroup 2 ($p<0.05$, respectively). A statistically significant greater decrease in mesor CR SV was identified in subgroup 1 of group 2 during the period of days 7-12 and 14-24, averaging 27%. The changes occurred within the age-appropriate norm. Differences between groups 1 and 2 were observed in all subgroups. In the group of children who received conservative treatment (subgroup 1) and after extracranial surgeries, a statistically significant decrease in mesor CR SV was observed, averaging 25% ($p<0.05$). In subgroup 3 of group 2, there was a 32% increase in mesor CR SV compared to groups 1 and 2 ($p<0.05$, respectively), with a mean of 61±4 ml (Table 2). We attributed this finding to a compensatory cardiac function response to persistent cerebral ischemia following corrective surgeries related to severe TBI and the systemic inflammatory reaction to cranial and extracranial injuries. Under these conditions, it appears that not only a more potent stress-protective and

anti-inflammatory response but also a metabolic response aimed at restoring the viability and functional activity of brain tissue injured by TBI and surgical intervention is necessary.

During the first 10 days in group 1 of children, a tendency for CR SV to increase the fluctuation level was observed in subgroup 3 up to 56 ± 1.5 ml, with the average level in subgroup 1 at 55 ± 3 ml and in subgroup 2 at 56 ± 2 ml. In group 2 of children, this indicator became significant due to an increase in the average fluctuation level in subgroup 3 (63 ± 5 ml) and a tendency toward decreased fluctuation levels in both subgroup 1 (49 ± 3 ml) and subgroup 2 down to 46 ± 3 ml (Fig.2).

Fig.1. CR SV in group 1 over 10 days

Fig.2. CR SV in group 2 over 10 days

Fig. 3. CR SV in Group 1 over 30 days

Fig. 4. CR SV in Group 2 over 30 days

The identified characteristic of CR SV in the subgroups of both groups persisted throughout the entire intensive therapy period in the ICU (Figs. 3, 4).

Table 3. Comparative assessment of the amplitude and circadian fluctuations of CR SV (ml)

Indicators	Group 1, Subgroup 1	Group 2, Subgroup 1	Group 1, Subgroup 2	Group 2, Subgroup 2	Group 1, Subgroup 3	2 gr 3 subgr
Amplitude of CR SV	6±2	12±4	8±3	12±5	7±2	20±8*
Circadian fluctuation of SV	13±4	23±6*	15±6	23±8	14±3	35±11*

* — significantly relative to the indicator in group 1.

As shown in Table 3, subgroup 1 of group 2 demonstrated a significant increase in circadian fluctuation of SV by 76% ($p<0.05$), and subgroup 3 by 150% ($p<0.05$). Furthermore, a significant increase in the amplitude of CR SV by 200% ($p<0.05$) was observed in children of subgroup 3 in group 2. Thus, cardiac output instability predominated in children of group 2 within the 3rd subgroup. It is known that an increase in the amplitude of the circadian rhythm of SV, along with large fluctuations in cardiac output during the day, indicates a stress response of cardiac function with adverse consequences for myocardial contractility. This is due to inadequate coronary blood flow relative to the rapidly changing functional activity of cardiomyocytes, accompanied by a significant increase in myocardial oxygen demand and the absence of timely, adequate oxygenation to meet these increased demands, inevitably leading to the accumulation of underoxidized metabolic products, the integral result of which is acute heart failure. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that an increase in the amplitude of CR SV by more than 8 ml (on average more than 15%), and a daily fluctuation of SV by 16 ml (over 30%) in SCTBI in children should be considered a factor contributing to an acute myocardial energy deficit, increasing the risk of developing acute heart failure.

Table 4. Correlation relationships of SV

Pairs Parameters	Group 1, days 1-10			Group 1, days 11-30			Group 1, 30 days		
	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3
SV/T	-0,53	-0,80	0,50	-0,44	0,62		-0,39	0,30	0,50
SV/SBP	-0,73	-0,03	-0,37	-0,14	0,16	-0,36	-0,18	0,12	-0,38
SV/DBP	-0,82	-0,29	-0,71	-0,28	-0,41	-0,82	-0,29	-0,33	-0,81
SV/ MeanBP	-0,62	0,09	-0,52	-0,12	-0,31	-0,67	-0,12	-0,24	-0,61
SV/DBP	0,68	0,65	0,80	0,43	0,77	0,72	0,44	0,76	0,77
	Group 2, 10 days			Group 2, 11-30 days			Group 2, 30 days		

	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3	Sub-group 1	Sub-group 2	Sub-group 3
SV/T	-0,54	-0,32	0,35	-0,78	0,32		-0,02	0,04	0,35
SV/SBP	-0,76	-0,32	0,35	0,43	-0,28	-0,34	0,11	-0,43	-0,24
SV/DBP	-0,79	-0,90	-0,46	0,44	-0,47	-0,58	-0,25	-0,55	-0,55
SV/ MeanBP	-0,67	-0,91	-0,08	0,23	-0,45	-0,48	-0,16	-0,58	-0,38
SV/DBP	-0,23	0,39	0,65	0,65	0,06	0,12	-0,16	0,05	0,37

A positive correlation between changes in body temperature and SV, identified during the first 10 days in operated children of subgroup 2 in group 1 (−0.8), became positive in subsequent days, maintaining the trend (0.62) as a compensatory response of increased cardiac output to elevated temperature (Table 4). In group 2, a strong negative correlation (−0.78) between body temperature and SV in subgroup 1 indicated a detrimental effect of the hyperthermic response on cardiac function, justifying active anti-inflammatory antipyretic conservative therapy to preempt the risk of acute heart failure. A negative correlation between SV and SBP was found in both Group 1 and Group 2, amounting to −0.73 in Subgroup 1 of Group 1 and −0.76 in Subgroup 1 of Group 2. In other words, the compensatory increase in SBP in response to hypoxia and ischemia of brain tissue structures in non-operated children was accompanied by a consistent decrease in SV. An inverse correlation between SV and DBP was identified in most examined patients in Group 1, specifically in Subgroups 1 and 3 (−0.82; −0.71), which persisted throughout the entire treatment period, amounting to −0.81. In the 2nd group, a strong negative correlation between SV and DBP was observed in subgroups 1 and 2 during the first 10 days (−0.79 and −0.9, respectively), maintaining this trend in the subsequent days of treatment. A decrease in DBP in response to an increase in cardiac output is a physiological compensatory response aimed at increasing peripheral capillary blood flow under the risk of tissue oxygen insufficiency. In the 1st group, a strong direct correlation between SV and DBP was identified in the 3rd subgroup during the first 10 days (0.8), persisting in the operated patients of subgroups 2 and 3 (0.76 and 0.77, respectively) throughout the entire duration of intensive therapy.

Conclusion

In subgroup 3, the most pronounced compensatory cardiac function response to persistent cerebral ischemia following corrective surgeries related to severe TBI and systemic inflammatory response to cranial and extracranial injuries was expressed as a 32% increase in the mesor CR SV. A strong negative correlation (−0.78) between body temperature and SV in subgroup 1 indicated the detrimental effect of hyperthermic response on cardiac function, serving as a rationale for

active anti-inflammatory antipyretic conservative therapy aimed at preventing the risk of acute heart failure. An increase in the amplitude of CR SV by more than 8 ml (on average by over 15%), and daily fluctuations of SV by 16 ml (exceeding 30%) in SCTBI in children should be considered a factor promoting acute myocardial energy deficiency with an elevated risk of acute heart failure.

References

1. Kuldashev K. A. *Acute combined traumatic brain injury: comprehensive diagnostics at the stages of medical care. Journal of Neurosurgery named after N. N. Burdenko.* 2012;76(6):40-44.
2. <http://www.stm-journal.ru/en/numbers/2010/4/685/pdf>
3. <https://newday-clinic.ru/posledstviya-cherepno-mozgovo-j-travmy>
4. https://meduniver.com/Medical/Xirurgia/serdce_i_sosudi_pri_travme_mozga.
5. *NeurocritCare* (2024) 40:477-485 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12028-023-01777-3>

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.24.58.142

莫斯科中心区综合诊所患者就诊路线的有效性

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PATIENT ROUTES IN POLYCLINICS IN
THE CENTRAL DISTRICT OF MOSCOW**

Karimova Daniia Yusufovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Full Professor

Russian Medical Academy of Continuous Professional Education

Belkina Valeriia Alekseevna

Physician

Federal State Budgetary Institution City Polyclinic No. 220 of the

Moscow Department of Health

Utkin Aleksandr Vladimirovich

Postgraduate Student

Medical-Biological University of Innovations and Continuous

Education, State Scientific Center of the Russian Federation —

*«A. I. Burnazyan Federal Medical Biophysical Center» of the Federal
Medical-Biological Agency of Russia*

摘要。目前，俄罗斯正在积极进行基层医疗流程的重组。精益生产理念加速了这一进程。本研究分阶段进行：**诊断阶段：**识别当前患者满意度水平和医疗机构的数字化成熟度；**分析阶段：**建立数字化流程与患者体验之间的关系。因此，本研究融合了循证医学、健康社会学和医学信息学的要素，确保了其跨学科性质和科学创新性。本文呈现了一项关于医疗机构数字化和组织流程效率的研究的部分内容。路径效率指数（REI）为0.70。根据REI的解释方法，0.9至1.0的值表示最佳路径，0.7至0.89的值表示令人满意的路径，低于0.7的值则需要进行物流重组。所得结果（REI = 0.70）处于令人满意的最低阈值，表明当前路径规划模型存在严重问题。根据时间研究数据，在相对稳定的登记操作中，患者在诊室外等待是造成时间损失的主要原因。所得结果为进一步优化路径规划和重新分配患者流量提供了量化依据。

关键词：基层医疗，患者路径规划，路径效率指数。

Abstract. *Currently, there is an active reorganization of primary healthcare processes taking place in Russia. This process was accelerated by the philosophy of lean manufacturing. The research design was developed in stages: diagnostic stage: identifying the current levels of patient satisfaction and the digital*

maturity of institutions; analytical stage: establishing the relationships between digital processes and patient experience. Thus, the study integrates elements of evidence-based medicine, health sociology, and medical informatics, ensuring its interdisciplinary nature and scientific novelty. This message presents a fragment of a study on the efficiency of digital and organizational processes in a medical organization. The route efficiency index (REI) was 0.70. According to the REI interpretation methodology, values from 0.9 to 1.0 indicate an optimal route, 0.7 to 0.89 indicate a satisfactory route, and values below 0.7 necessitate logistics reorganization. The obtained result (REI = 0.70) corresponds to the lower threshold of a satisfactory level and indicates a critical state of the current routing model. According to Time-Study data, the main source of time loss is waiting outside the physician's office amid relatively stable registry operations. The obtained results provide a quantitative justification for the need to further optimize routing and redistribute patient flows.

Keywords: *primary health care, patient routing, route efficiency index.*

Relevance. According to WHO data for the Russian Federation, the reorganization of primary health care processes in 2020-2021. (flow separation, digital registration, proactive prevention) was accelerated due to previously initiated “lean” transformations, the philosophy of lean production — Lean Production, Lean Thinking [1-3]. Patient waiting times and logistics have improved, especially in large urban systems (for example, Moscow’s three-tier routing system and large outpatient centers). Russian and international publications demonstrate that the adaptation of Lean at the primary care level leads to measurable organizational effects: reduced waiting times, decreased flow variability, increased proportion of electronic records, improved satisfaction, and simplified routing. Reviews and Russian materials emphasize that success depends on a combination of tools and a culture of improvement [4]. At the same time, several studies note that sustaining the effect requires continuous monitoring; without it, a ‘rollback’ to original practices is observed [5].

In this regard, **the objective of the study** was to model the temporal parameters of patient routes in outpatient clinics within the Central Administrative District of Moscow.

Materials and Methods. The choice of the Central Administrative District of the city of Moscow (CAD) as the object is due to its social and economic specificity: high population density, the highest level of digital maturity and accessibility of medical care, as well as high patient demands, which makes the district a representative model for assessing the effectiveness of digital healthcare reforms.

The study was conducted as a multicenter applied observational study incorporating elements of analytical and correlational analysis.

Study type: descriptive-analytical, longitudinal, with a cross-sectional design to assess the current state of digitalization.

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative methods: surveys and direct observation (time-study).

The research proceeded in stages: diagnostic phase — identification of the current level of patient satisfaction and the digital maturity of institutions; analytical stage: establishing the relationships between digital processes and patient experience. Thus, the study integrates elements of evidence-based medicine, health sociology, and medical informatics, ensuring its interdisciplinary nature and scientific novelty.

This message presents a fragment of a study on the efficiency of digital and organizational processes in a medical organization. An analysis of the patient journey was conducted using the direct observation method (time-study). A total of 20 consecutive observations of patients of various ages were conducted during peak and off-peak hours, providing a sufficient sample size for academic statistical analysis at the postgraduate dissertation level.

Respondents' ages ranged from 18 to 91 years, ensuring representative coverage of all patient age groups, including working-age and elderly populations. The mean age was 51.1 ± 15.7 years.

Results. When modeling the temporal parameters of the patient route, the following empirical constraints were taken into account: waiting time for the doctor was approximately 10-22 minutes, time at the registration desk was about 2-7 minutes, effective consultation time with the doctor was around 10-17 minutes, and the total duration of the patient's stay at the outpatient clinic was 25-55 minutes. Based on these initial assumptions, the coefficient of effective time (K_p) and the route efficiency index (REI) were calculated. The coefficient of useful time was determined using the formula

$$K_p = \frac{T_{\text{полезн}}}{T_{\text{общ}}}$$

and the route efficiency index as the ratio of the total normative (optimal) time to the total actual time:

$$\text{ИЭМ} = \frac{\sum T_{\text{опт}}}{\sum T_{\text{факт}}}$$

Individual observation results were recorded in a dedicated Time-Study log. The consolidated summary indicators based on Time-Study data are presented below.

Analytical interpretation of the obtained results indicates that the useful time coefficient ($K_p = 0.32$) implies that only 32% of the time spent by the patient in the outpatient clinic is actually useful interaction time with the physician. The remaining 68% corresponds to waiting and moving between functional zones. For comparison:

within the Lean approach to organizing outpatient care, the target values of K_p range between 0.45 and 0.55. Thus, in the studied medical organization, the actual coefficient is significantly lower than the normative benchmarks, indicating substantial time losses and considerable potential for process optimization.

Table 1 — Summary indicators according to Time-Study

Indicator	Value
Average time spent in the outpatient clinic <i>Тобщ</i>	43.4 min
Average useful time with the physician <i>Тполезн</i>	13.7 min
Average waiting time at the physician	16.1 min
Average waiting time at the registration desk	4.6 min
Average useful time coefficient K_p	0,32
Average route efficiency index REI	0,70

At the operational level, Russian publications report specific indicators: reducing waiting time at the registration desk to 5-7 minutes (in pilot projects) and decreasing waiting time at the physician's office by 20-40%, increasing the proportion of services completed "without queuing," and improving navigation and waiting comfort [6]. These results, however, vary by region: entities with developed IT infrastructure and management practices (large agglomerations) demonstrate faster achievement of compliance levels 2-3, whereas resource-constrained territories progress more slowly [WHO, 2021].

The route efficiency index (REI) was 0.70. According to the REI interpretation methodology, values from 0.9 to 1.0 indicate an optimal route, 0.7 to 0.89 indicate a satisfactory route, and values below 0.7 necessitate logistics reorganization. The resulting value ($REI = 0.70$) corresponds to the lower boundary of the satisfactory level and indicates a critical state of the current routing model.

Based on the analysis of the time structure of the visit, the main 'bottlenecks' in patient routing were identified in Table 2.

Table 2 — Patient Routing Bottlenecks

Bottleneck	Contribution to Losses	Comment
Waiting at the Doctor's Office	$\approx 37\%$ of Total Time	Increased due to the growth in patient flow in 2025
Reception Desk	$\approx 11\%$	Generally satisfactory, but queues form during peak hours
Suboptimal Routing	$\approx 20\%$	There is duplication of movements between offices.

Conclusions. Thus, according to Time-Study data, the primary source of time loss is waiting at the doctor's office amid comparatively stable operation of the registration desk. The obtained results align well with data from information systems and with content analysis of patient feedback, serving as a quantitative justification for the need to further optimize routing and redistribute patient flows.

References

1. Wumek James P., Jones Daniel T. *Lean Production. How to Eliminate Waste and Achieve Prosperity in Your Company.* — Moscow: Alpina Publisher, 2021/ — 472 P.
2. Golokteev K. N., Matveev I. A. *Production Management: Tools That Work.* — Saint Petersburg: Piter, 2020. — 250 P.
3. Womack James P., Jones Daniel T., Roos Daniel. *The Machine That Changed the World.* — Moscow: Potpourri, 2015. — 384 P.
4. Lawal A. K. *Lean management in health care: definition, concepts, methodology and effects reported (systematic review protocol) / A. K. Lawal, T. Rotter, L. Kinsman [et al.].* — Text: Electronic // *Systematic Reviews.* — 2014. — No. 3. — P. 103. — doi: 10.1186/2046-4053-3-103.
5. Holden R. J. *Lean thinking in emergency departments: a critical review / R. J. Holden.* — Text: Electronic // *Annals of Emergency Medicine.* — 2011. — No. 57(3). — Pp. 265-278. — doi: 10.1016/j.annemergmed.2010.08.001.
6. Metelskaya A. V. *Lean outpatient clinic: aspects of optimizing medical processes / A. V. Metelskaya, N. N. Kamynina.* — Text: Electronic // *Problems of Social Hygiene, Healthcare and History of Medicine.* — 2020b. — No. 28(5). — Pp. 994-999. — doi: 10.32687/0869-866X-2020-28-5-994-999.
7. WHO & UNICEF. *Primary health care for the 21st century: towards UHC and SDGs / WHO & UNICEF.* — Text: Electronic // WHO, Geneva. — 2021. — Access mode: <https://www.who.int/ru/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/primary-health-care>.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.24.60.137

多价噬菌体在预防紧急腹腔内手术感染中的作用
**THE ROLE OF POLYVALENT BACTERIOPHAGE IN THE
PREVENTION OF SURGICAL INFECTIONS DURING
EMERGENCY INTRA-ABDOMINAL INTERVENTIONS**

Parshin Dmitry Sergeevich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Astrakhan State Medical University Astrakhan,
Astrakhan, Russian Federation*

Topchiev Mikhail Andreevich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor
Astrakhan State Medical University Astrakhan,
Astrakhan, Russian Federation*

Melnikov Vladimir Vitalievich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Astrakhan State Medical University Astrakhan,
Astrakhan, Russian Federation*

Mikhailichenko Vyacheslav Yurievich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
S. I. Georgievsky Medical Academy of V. I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal
University,
Simferopol, Russian Federation*

摘要：本单中心病例对照研究（n=136）旨在评估使用多价噬菌体（PBF）预防2021年至2023年间接受腹部器官急诊手术患者的术后感染的可行性。根据术前发生术后出血（IOHV）的风险评估（ACS NSQIP, 30±3%），将患者分为研究组和对照组。排除标准包括急性肠系膜缺血、严重腹部脓毒症和脓毒性休克。研究组患者接受Sextaphage®治疗（20 ml，口服或经鼻胃管给药：术前立即给药，术后每12小时一次，持续3天；对于A1-temeir分级3-4级的手术，需冲洗剖腹切口）。对照组患者接受标准治疗。两组患者均评估了肠功能障碍的综合严重程度评分、生化指标和器械检查指标的动态变化，并记录了术后并发症（ASEPSIS 分级、Clavien-Dindo 分级），观察期为 30 天。采用 STATISTICA 10.0 软件进行统计数据分析（Spearman 相关性分析、Student's t 检验、 $p \leq 0.05$ 、分层随机化）。研究发现，肠功能障碍患者的血浆内毒素水平相当于急性肠衰竭 II

期。与对照组不同，主要治疗组患者在治疗过程中，血浆内毒素水平在治疗第三天即出现统计学意义上的显著下降 ($p \leq 0.05$)，碱性磷酸酶与肠道碱性磷酸酶的比值在治疗第五天恢复正常 ($p \leq 0.05$)。主要组的 IOHV 发生率 (9.7%) 显著低于对照组 (17.6%)。IOHV 样本的微生物学分析显示存在多种微生物混合感染，具体包括大肠杆菌+不动杆菌、金黄色葡萄球菌+胞内杆菌以及表皮葡萄球菌+肺炎克雷伯菌。主要组患者的重症监护室停留时间和总住院时间 (分别为 1.9 天和 4.1 天) 显著短于对照组 (分别为 8.7 天和 14.5 天)。对照组出现 3 例死亡病例。结论：在急诊腹部手术中预防性使用多价噬菌体 (口服和局部应用) 可促进肠功能障碍的快速恢复，并使手术部位术后感染并发症的发生率降低一半以上。

关键词：噬菌体预防、手术部位感染预防、腹部感染、肠道病原菌群、急性肠衰竭、病原菌群移位。

Abstract. *The objective of this single-center case-control study (n=136) was to evaluate the feasibility of using polyvalent bacteriophages (PBF) for the prevention of surgical infections in a group of patients undergoing emergency surgical interventions on abdominal organs between 2021 and 2023. Patients were divided into primary and control groups based on the preoperative risk assessment for the development of IOHV (ACS NSQIP, 30±3%). The exclusion criteria were acute mesenteric ischemia, as well as severe abdominal sepsis and septic shock. In the main group, patients received the drug Sextaphage® (20 ml orally or via a nasogastric tube: immediately before surgery, then every 12 hours for three days; for Altemeir's class 3-4 surgeries, irrigation of the laparotomy wound was performed). Patients in the control group received standard treatment. In both groups, the dynamics of integral severity scales, biochemical and instrumental markers of enteral dysfunction were assessed, and postoperative complications (ASEPSIS, Clavien-Dindo) were recorded over a 30-day period. Statistical data analysis was conducted using the STATISTICA 10.0 software package (Spearman correlation analysis, Student's t-test, $p \leq 0.05$, stratified randomization). It was established that, in patients with enteral dysfunction, plasma endotoxin levels corresponded to stage II of acute intestinal failure. In the main group, during the course of therapy, there was a statistically significant decrease in plasma endotoxin levels by the third day ($p \leq 0.05$) and normalization of the alkaline phosphatase to intestinal alkaline phosphatase ratio by the fifth day ($p \leq 0.05$), unlike in the control group. The incidence of IOHV in the main group was significantly lower (9.7%) compared to the control group (17.6%). Microbiological analysis of IOHV samples revealed polymicrobial associations, specifically Escherichia coli+ Acinetobacter, Staphylococcus aureus+Citobacter, and Staphylococcus epidermidis +Kl. pneumoniae. The duration of stay in the intensive care unit and the overall length of hospitalization were significantly shorter in the main group (1.9 and 4.1 days, respectively) compared to the control group (8.7 and 14.5 days,*

respectively). Three fatal outcomes were registered in the control group. Conclusion: Prophylactic administration of polyvalent bacteriophages, both orally and topically, in emergency abdominal surgery promotes a more rapid resolution of enteral dysfunction and reduces the frequency of postoperative infectious complications at the surgical site by more than twofold.

Keywords: phage prophylaxis, prevention of surgical site infections, abdominal infections, enteric pathobiome, acute intestinal failure, pathobiome translocation.

The spread of surgical infections (SI) and the rise in antibiotic resistance represent interconnected and serious challenges to modern medicine, requiring the development and implementation of comprehensive strategies. Despite existing strict protocols aimed at reducing the incidence of postoperative infectious complications, including perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis, data from the World Health Organization (WHO) indicate that the incidence of SI varies widely — from 3% to 50%, depending on the nature and extent of the surgical intervention. In European countries, surgical infections account for a significant proportion (approximately 17%) of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) [1, 2]. This problem is particularly acute in low- and middle-income countries, where approximately 60% of surgical complications result from surgical infections. Consequently, up to 60% of patients undergoing surgical procedures receive antibacterial therapy during the postoperative period while hospitalized, with almost half of them being prescribed antibiotics upon discharge. It is important to emphasize that the widespread use of antibiotics in surgical practice, often without sufficient justification, can lead to the selection of resistant microbial strains and exacerbate the issue of antibiotic resistance [3, 4].

In abdominal surgery, the intestine is traditionally regarded as a likely endogenous reservoir of infection and a significant risk factor for the development of surgical infections. Many researchers maintain that any surgical intervention involving the abdominal organs can potentially trigger transient local or generalized intestinal dysfunction [5]. The intestinal barrier, comprising the luminal microbiota, a mucus layer, and a complex system of physical barriers formed by epithelial and immune cells, plays a crucial role in maintaining homeostasis and in the development of various pathological conditions. Compromise of the integrity and functional activity of the intestinal barrier significantly increases the risk of developing superinfection, with the most frequently isolated pathogens being *Escherichia coli* and *Bacteroides spp.* The inflammatory process in the abdominal cavity, accompanied by the accumulation of exudate, consistently leads to intestinal dilation and the formation of paralytic intestinal obstruction (ileus). Peritonitis induces the development of intestinal obstruction, which is mediated both by local inflammatory responses and the effects of bacterial toxins, as well as by the formation of fibrinous adhesions that

impede the restoration of normal peristalsis and the evacuatory function of the intestine [6, 7]. Bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) initiates a cascade of inflammatory reactions in the smooth muscle layer of the intestinal wall, resulting in reduced contractile capacity of smooth muscle cells and the formation of intestinal obstruction. Key protective mechanisms include enzymatic systems that neutralize the effects of bacterial LPS. Specifically, intestinal alkaline phosphatase (KShF), an enzyme located in the apical membrane of enterocytes, inhibits the production of inflammatory mediators and plays a critically important role in maintaining intestinal barrier function and microbial homeostasis [8, 9].

Amid the widespread prevalence of antibiotic resistance and limited progress in the development of new antibacterial agents, there has been an increased focus on scientific research in alternative areas, particularly in the field of phage prophylaxis and phage therapy [10, 11]. The principle of phage therapy involves the use of strictly lytic bacteriophages for the selective destruction of target bacteria, while preserving the host organism's cells intact and minimizing adverse effects on commensal bacteria, which distinctly differentiates phage therapy from traditional antibiotic therapy. Pharmacokinetic studies demonstrate that after a single oral administration of bacteriophages in a volume of 20-30 ml, they are detected in the systemic bloodstream within 1 hour, and in the urine within 2 hours after administration. A high concentration of phage particles is maintained for 3-6 days, which is attributed to the active replication of bacteriophages in the presence of susceptible bacteria. The advantages of phages include: high specificity of action, rapid inactivation following eradication of the bacterial pathogen, capacity for self-replication, stimulation of the immune response, ability to penetrate biofilm matrices, biological inertness toward human tissues, and the possibility of both local and oral administration [12, 13]. The clinical application of bacteriophages shows promising results [14, 15]. At the same time, one of the main obstacles hindering the widespread adoption of bacteriophages in clinical practice is the lack of a clear and comprehensive regulatory framework governing their medical use.

Research objective: to assess the feasibility of using polyvalent bacteriophages (PBF) for the prevention of surgical infections in a group of patients undergoing emergency surgical interventions on abdominal organs.

Materials and Methods: Within a single-center case-control study, the treatment outcomes of 136 patients who underwent emergency open intra-abdominal surgical interventions between 2021 and 2023 were analyzed. The patients were divided into two groups of comparable size: the main group and the control group, each comprising 68 individuals. The patients' ages ranged from 18 to 92 years. The gender distribution in the overall sample included 73 men and 63 women.

Patient group allocation was based on the assessment of surgical risk using the ACS NSQIP (American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality

Improvement Program®) calculator, version 2007-2026. The inclusion criterion for the study was a preoperative risk of developing surgical site infection (IOHV) ranging from 27% to 33%. The exclusion criteria were acute mesenteric ischemia, severe abdominal sepsis, and septic shock upon admission. Postoperative complications were monitored for 30 days following the surgery.

Patients in the main group, in addition to standard treatment, were administered Sextaphage® (NPO 'MICROGEN', Russia), a filtrate of bacterial phagolysates of *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Proteus* (*P. vulgaris*, *P. mirabilis*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* (enteropathogenic strains), and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (registration number LS-001049). The drug was administered orally or via a nasogastric tube at a dose of 20 ml immediately before surgery, then every 12 hours for 3 days. In surgeries classified as Class 3 and Class 4 according to the Altemeir classification, additional irrigation of the laparotomy wound with a PVB solution was performed prior to suturing. An assessment of the dose-dependent effect of the drug was not conducted within the scope of this study. In the control group, patients received only standard therapy without the use of immunobiological agents. Antibiotic prophylaxis and antibiotic therapy in both groups were conducted in accordance with current Russian regulatory documents and clinical guidelines [reference to current Russian guidelines].

To assess the progression of intestinal insufficiency, the enteral morphofunctional coefficient (EMFK) was calculated on days 1, 3, and 5 after therapy initiation.

The levels of total alkaline phosphatase (ShF) and its intestinal isoform (KShF) in blood serum and intestinal contents were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using the Cobas e411 analyzer (Roche Diagnostics, Switzerland). Measurements were performed at the baseline (0-1 days) and on the 5th day after treatment initiation. Additionally, the percentage ratio of ShF/KShF was calculated.

Table 1. Stratification of patients by type of nosology and severity of condition at admission (abs; M±m)

Nosology / SSI; APACHE II; SOFA	Main group (n=68)	Comparison group (n=68)
Acute obstructive large bowel obstruction (tumor-related)	17	18
Incarcerated ventral hernia	13	12
Acute adhesive bowel obstruction	14	16
Acute appendicitis	11	10
Perforated gastric and duodenal ulcer	12	12
IBP	16,8±1,4	16,7±0,9
APACHE II	14,1±0,6	14,5±0,8
SOFA	3,7±0,4	3,6±0,3

The severity of postoperative intra-abdominal complications (IOHV) was assessed using the ASEPSIS and Clavien-Dindo scales.

Statistical analysis was conducted using the STATISTICA 10.0 software package, including correlation analysis (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient). Patient distribution into groups was carried out using stratified randomization. Statistical significance of differences between groups was assessed using Student's t-test. Differences were considered statistically significant at a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results:

Baseline analysis of enteral dysfunction markers showed that EMFK levels in both patient groups corresponded to stage II (subcompensated) intestinal insufficiency, with no statistically significant differences observed between the groups. Alongside this, a deficiency of intestinal alkaline phosphatase was observed, manifested as an imbalance in the ShF/KShF ratio shifted towards ShF, indicating the presence of a pronounced inflammatory process in the intestine.

On the third day of therapy, a statistically significant decrease in EMFK was detected by ultrasound examination in the main patient group ($p \leq 0.05$). In the control group, a statistically significant decrease in EMFK was observed only by the fifth day of therapy. Normalization of the ShF/KShF ratio in the main group was achieved by the fifth day ($p \leq 0.05$). No restoration of the KShF level was observed in the comparison group (data are presented in Table 2).

Table 2. Dynamics of markers of enteral insufficiency in the study groups (M±m; abs.)

Study groups	Research subject	ShF/KShF (%)		EMFK (scores)		
		1st day	5th day	1st day	3rd day	5th day
Main (n=68)	Serum	0,72±0,22	0,31±0,11*	19,5±1,11	5,2±0,32*	4,6±0,2*
	Chyme	6,21±0,11	3,12±0,51*			
Comparisons (n=68)	Serum	0,69±0,39	0,59±0,27	20,1±1,21	13,4±1,11	9,6±0,8
	Chyme	6,27±0,21	6,05±0,24			

* — values at $p \leq 0.05$ compared with the control group

Analysis of postoperative infectious complications at the surgical intervention site (IOHV) revealed that the incidence of deep or complicated wound infections, classified as DSSI (Deep Surgical Site Infection) and OSSSI (Organ/Space Surgical Site Infections) and characterized by destructive tissue changes, in the primary group was 1 case. This case presented as a subaponeurotic abscess of the postoperative wound. Superficial surgical site infections (SSSI)

were recorded in 5 cases in the main group. In the control group, conversely, DSSI and OSSSI were observed in 5 cases, including 2 episodes of extensive purulence of the laparotomy wound with eventration, 1 case of an interloop intra-abdominal abscess, and 1 case of intestinal anastomosis suture failure. The incidence of SSSI in the comparison group was 7 cases. The total number of IOHV cases in the main group was 6 (9.7%), while in the comparison group it was 12 (17.6%) (data are shown in Table 3).

Table 3. Treatment Outcomes of Patients in the Study Groups

Indicators	Study groups					
	Main (n=68)			Comparison (n=68)		
	1st day	3rd day	5th day	1st day	3rd day	5th day
APACHE II (points)	16,8±1,4	10,3±0,9	6,2±0,3*	16,7±0,9	14,2±1,1	10,3±0,21
SOFA (points)	3,7±0,4	2,9±0,3	2,1±0,2*	3,6±0,3	3,8±0,5	2,9±0,3
ASEPSIS (points)	11,6±2,2			26,1±1,8*		
Number of operations per patient (absolute)	1,2			2,3		
Average length of stay in the ICU	1,9			4,1		
Average length of stay (inpatient treatment)	8,7			14,5		
Number of complications and Clavien-Dindo classification	CD IIIA — 3 CD IIIB — 3 CD V — 0			CD IIIB — 5 CD IVA — 1 CD IVB — 3 CD V — 3		

Microbiological analysis of pathogens in surgical site infections of the DSSI and OSSSI classes revealed a polymicrobial etiology in the majority of cases. The following microbial associations were identified: *Escherichia coli* + *Acinetobacter* (2 cases), *Staphylococcus aureus* + *Citrobacter* (2 cases), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* + *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (1 case).

The average length of stay in the ICU in the main group was 1.9 days, compared to 4.1 days in the comparison group. The overall average length of hospitalization was 8.7 days in the main group and 14.5 days in the comparison group. There were no fatalities in the comparison group, whereas 3 cases occurred in the main group.

The prophylactic use of polyvalent bacteriophages has demonstrated potential to accelerate the resolution of enteral insufficiency, likely due to modulation of

the enteral microbiome and reduction of pathogenic bacterial colonization in the small intestine.

Based on the obtained microbiological data, the necessity for developing and implementing new phage preparations in clinical practice has been substantiated, focusing in particular on *Citrobacter* and *Acinetobacter*. The results of the study suggest that the preventive use of polyvalent bacteriophages (PVBPh) can be considered a strategy to maintain the intestinal barrier function, prevent the infiltration of pro-inflammatory factors into the portal system, and hinder microbial translocation caused by systemic inflammation of intestinal origin.

The complexity of interactions between bacteriophages and pathogens against the background of immunodeficiency presents challenges for modeling and investigating these processes. Nonetheless, conducting further multicenter clinical trials and meta-analyses appears to be a promising approach in combating IOHV in the 21st century.

Conclusion

Preventive administration of polyvalent bacteriophages orally and locally in emergency abdominal surgery promotes accelerated resolution of enteral dysfunction and reduces the incidence of postoperative surgical site infections by more than twofold.

References

1. Rezaei AR, Zienkiewicz D, Rezaei AR. *Surgical site infections: a comprehensive review. J Trauma Inj.* 2025 Jun;38(2):71-81. DOI: 10.20408/jti.2025.0019
2. Ahuja Sh., Peiffer-Smadja N., Peven P., White M., Leather A. J. M., Sanjeev S., Mendelson M., Holmes A., Birgand G., Sevdalis N. *Use of Feedback Data to Reduce Surgical Site Infections and Optimize Antibiotic Use in Surgery. A Systematic Scoping Review. Annals of Surgery.* 2022; 2: 345-e352. DOI: 10.1097/SLA. 000000000000490
3. Prabhu R., Mohamed M. S., Alhammali T., et al. *Modern Surgical Site Infection Prevention: Evidence, Gaps, and Future Directions. Cureus.* 2025; 7(10): e94764. DOI: 10.7759/cureus.94764
4. Sriranjani K. S., Rajeshwara K. V. *A Comparative Study of the Incidence and Severity of Surgical Site Infection Following Emergency and Elective Abdominal Surgeries. Journal of Evolution of medical and Dental Sciences.* 2021; 10(7): 404-408. DOI: 10.14260/JEMDS/2021/90.

5. Untersmayr E., Brandt A., Koidl L., Bergheim I. *The Intestinal Barrier Dysfunction as Driving Factor of Inflammaging*. *Nutrients*. 2022; 14(5): P. 949. DOI: 10.3390/nu14050949.
6. Kühn F., Adiliaghdam F., Cavallaro P. M., Hamarneh S. R., Tsurumi A., Hoda R. S., Munoz A. R., Dhole Y., Ramirez J. M., Liu E., Vasan R., Liu Y., Samarbafzadeh E., Nunez R. A., Farber M. Z., Chopra V., Malo M. S., Rahme L. G., Hodin R. A. *Intestinal alkaline phosphatase targets the gut barrier to prevent aging*. *JCI Insight*. 2020; 26(6): e134049. DOI:10.1172/jci.insight.134049.
7. Weledji E. P. *Perspectives on paralytic ileus*. *Acute Med Surg*. 2020; 7: e573. DOI: 10.1002/ams2.573.
8. Park S. Y., Kim J. Y., Lee S. M., Chung J. O., Seo J. H., Kim S., Kim D. H., Park C. H., Ju J. K., Joo Y. E., Lee J. H., Kim H. S., Choi S. K., Rew J. S. *Lower expression of endogenous intestinal alkaline phosphatase may predict worse prognosis in patients with Crohn's disease*. *BMC Gastroenterol*. 2018; 17-18: 188. DOI:10.1186/s12876-018-0904-x.
9. Topchiev M. A., Parshin D. S., Kchibekov E. A., Biryukov P. A., Misrikhanov M. K. *A differentiated approach to antihypoxic and endoportial therapy in the treatment of diffuse peritonitis complicated by enteral insufficiency syndrome*. *Medical Bulletin of the North Caucasus*. 2018; 4: 619-623. DOI:10.14300/mnnc.2018.13120.
10. Topchiev M. A., Parshin D. S., Chotchaev M. K., Nurmagedov A. G., Misrikhanov M. K., Badma-Goryaev O. V. *Potential of bacteriophages and oxygenated water for the prevention of surgical site infections in emergency abdominal surgery*. *Modern Problems of Science and Education*. 2022; 3: 102. DOI: 10.17513/spno.31736
11. Parshin D. S., Topchiev M. A., Pyatakov S. N., Badma-Goryaev O. V., Kupriyanov A. V., Alibekov R. S. *Outcomes of phage therapy for infectious complications in emergency abdominal surgery*. *Tauric Medical and Biological Bulletin*. 2022; 2: 72-80. DOI: 10.37279/2070-8092-2022-25-2-72-80
12. Milho C., Andrade M., Vilas Boas D., Alves D., Sillankorva S. *Antimicrobial assessment of phage therapy using a porcine model of biofilm infection*. *Int J Pharm*. 2019; 557: 112-123. DOI:10.1016/j.ijpharm.2018.12.004
13. Abedon S. T., Danis-Wlodarczyk K. M., Wozniak D. J., Sullivan M. B. *Improving Phage-Biofilm In Vitro Experimentation*. *Viruses*. 2021; 13(6): 1175. DOI:10.3390/v13061175
14. Xu M, Chen S, Pei H, Hu L, Zhang Y. *Engineering bacteriophages for gut health: precision antimicrobials and beyond*. *J Nanobiotechnology*. 2026; 24(1):62. DOI: 10.1186/s12951-026-04038-5

15. Parshin D., Mikhailichenko V., Mardanov R., Kupriyanov A., Alibekov R., Kerimov E., Puchkina G., Bezrukov O., Abdullaev A. Polyvalent bacteriophages and oxygenated water — possibilities for the prevention of surgical site infections during emergency abdominal surgery. *Archiv Euromedica*. 2023;4:812. DOI: 10.35630/2023/13/4.812

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.25.18.162

脑动脉和脑动脉瘤的结构变异
**VARIANTS OF THE STRUCTURE OF CEREBRAL ARTERIES AND
CEREBRAL ANEURYSMS**

Gorbunov Alexey Viktorovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor; Professor
Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin,
Tambov, Russia;*

Tambov State Technical University, Tambov, Russia

Khvorova Angelina Nikolaevna

Postgraduate student

Tambov State University named after G. R. Derzhavin;

Neurosurgeon

Tambov Regional Clinical Hospital named after V. D. Babenko

Parshin Dmitry Sergeevich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor

Astrakhan State Medical University

Mikhailichenko Vyacheslav Yurievich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor

V. I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Simferopol, Russia

摘要：尽管关于脑血管解剖学的研究众多，但专门研究脑动脉结构变异的文献却寥寥无几。脑动脉结构变异对脑动脉瘤形成的影响尚不明确。

鉴于当前形势，有必要系统整理现有脑动脉结构变异数据，并将其与现代研究方法获得的结果进行比较。

本研究旨在调查20至93岁男性和女性脑动脉解剖变异中，颈内动脉前三叉和后三叉的发生率以及脑动脉环脑动脉瘤的患病率。

结论—32%的病例存在“非经典”脑动脉环变异。在所有具有“经典”脑动脉环或颈内动脉三叉分支的病例中，均未检测到脑动脉瘤。

关键词：脑动脉发育变异，颈内动脉前三叉分支，颈内动脉后三叉分支，脑动脉瘤。

Abstract. *Despite numerous studies concerning the anatomy of cerebral vessels, few works are dedicated to variants in the structure of cerebral arteries. The possible influence of variants in the structure of cerebral arteries on the formation of cerebral aneurysms remains insufficiently studied.*

Current realities necessitate the systematization of existing data on variants in the structure of cerebral arteries and their comparison with findings obtained through modern investigative methods.

The objective of this study is to investigate the frequency of anterior and posterior trifurcations of the internal carotid artery and the prevalence of cerebral aneurysms in the arterial circle of the brain among anatomical variants of cerebral arteries in males and females aged 20 to 93 years.

Conclusions — the “non-classical” variant of the arterial circle of the brain was identified in 32% of cases. Cerebral aneurysms were not detected in any cases of the “classical” arterial circle of the brain or trifurcation of the internal carotid artery.

Keywords: *variants of cerebral artery development, anterior trifurcation of the internal carotid artery, posterior trifurcation of the internal carotid artery, cerebral aneurysms.*

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in accordance with the Federal Law of the Russian Federation dated 21.11.2011 No. 323-FZ ‘On the Fundamentals of Health Protection of Citizens in the Russian Federation.’ Ethical committee approval was not required; data analysis was performed retrospectively, and participants provided informed consent for MRA based on standard procedures of medical institutions.

A morphological analysis of magnetic resonance angiograms (MRA) of the brain was carried out in men and women aged 20 to 93 years. The studies were performed on a Philips Intera 1.5 T scanner in 2025. The analysis of cerebral arteries was performed using the software ‘RadiAnt DICOM Viewer.’

The study results were compared with literature data obtained through keyword searches for ‘variants of cerebral artery structure’ and ‘cerebral aneurysms’ in Russian and English via the PubMed database.

Results

Incomplete posterior trifurcation of the ICA on one side (left or right) was observed in women in 9 cases; incomplete posterior trifurcation on both sides was observed in 2 cases. Complete posterior trifurcation on one side (right or left) was observed in 5 cases. Complete posterior trifurcation on both sides was observed in 1 case. Anterior trifurcation of the ICA was observed in 7 cases.

In men, incomplete posterior trifurcation of the ICA on one side (left or right) was observed in 2 cases; incomplete posterior trifurcation on both sides was not identified. Complete posterior trifurcation on one side (right or left) was observed in 2 cases. Complete posterior trifurcation on both sides was not identified. Anterior trifurcation of the ICA was observed in 4 cases.

The closed, 'typical,' or 'classical' configuration of the arterial circle of the brain was identified in 59 (68%) cases. The 'non-classical' variant of the arterial circle of the brain configuration was observed in 28 cases. Regardless of gender, the results can be presented as follows.

The prevalence of anterior trifurcation of the ICA in men and women is 12%.

The prevalence of unilateral incomplete posterior trifurcation of the ICA in men and women is 12%.

The prevalence of unilateral complete posterior trifurcation of the ICA in men and women is 8%.

The prevalence of bilateral incomplete posterior trifurcation of the ICA in men and women is 2.2%.

The prevalence of bilateral complete posterior trifurcation of the ICA in men and women is 1.1%.

Cerebral aneurysms were not detected in any of the presented cases of anterior and posterior trifurcations of the ICA in men and women.

Discussion

The following data were found in the available literature sources. Closed variants of the arterial circle configuration were observed in 71.5% and open variants in 28.5% of cases. The symmetrical configuration of the cerebral arterial circle was observed more frequently in men than in women by 7.8%, whereas the asymmetrical configuration was observed less frequently in men than in women by 6.8%; the classical type of cerebral arterial circle configuration was identified in 37.5% of cases [1-3, 6-7].

In a study conducted based on *in vivo* magnetic resonance angiography of the brain in 496 patients, the following data were obtained: the classical structure of cerebral arteries was identified in 15.6% of women and 16.9% of men, with its occurrence in the analyzed population not exceeding 20% of cases. This study also analyzed the frequency of various variants of cerebral artery structure according to MRA data, among which the following were confirmed:

- Anterior trifurcation of one of the ICAs — 1.9%;
- Posterior trifurcation of the ICA in 5.1% of patients;
- Partial and complete posterior trifurcation of both ICAs in 1.9% of patients;

Some researchers consider that the variants of development demonstrate a fully functional arterial circle of the brain without association with cerebral aneurysms; others, conversely, regard the anterior and posterior trifurcation of the ICA as dysfunctional [4, 5, 8-14]. According to some authors, cerebral aneurysms occur more frequently in cases of an incomplete arterial circle of the brain [14-15].

Conclusions.

'Non-classical' variants of the structure of cerebral arteries are found in more than one-third of cases. The obtained data indicate the absence of a direct correlation between variants of the structure of cerebral arteries and the formation of cerebral aneurysms.

References

1. Pavlov A. V., Timofeev V. E., Zherybateva S. R., Suchkov D. I., Timofeeva S. M. *Features of the topography of the anterior central arteries depending on the variants of the structure of the arterial circle of the brain. Operative Surgery and Clinical Anatomy (Pirogov Scientific Journal). 2018;2(3):25-31.*
2. Gorbunov Aleksey Viktorovich. *Classification of Variants of Arteries and Variants of the Arterial Circle of the Brain in Humans // Bulletin of Russian Universities. Mathematics. 2013, No. 1.*
3. Nikolenko V. N., Pavlov A. V., Timofeev V. E., et al. *Variants of the Structure of the Arterial Circle of the Brain in Humans and an Integral Classification of Individual-Typological Variability. Sechenov Bulletin. 2018; 4 (34): 41-49. DOI: 10.26442/22187332.2018.4.41-49.*
4. Belenkaya R. M. *Stroke and Variants of Cerebral Arteries. — Moscow: Medicina, 1979. — 173 p., ill.; 20.*
5. Bragina L. K. *On the Patterns of Collateral Circulation in Occlusive Lesions of Major Head Vessels Depending on the Condition of the Circle of Willis. Journal of Neuropathology and Psychiatry Named after S. S. Korsakov. 1967;9:1293-1300.*
6. Yasargil MG. *Microneurosurgery: Microsurgical Anatomy of the Basal Cisterns and Vessels of the Brain, Diagnostic Studies, General Operative Techniques and Pathological Considerations of the Intracranial Aneurysms (in 4 vol.). Stuttgart. New York: Georg ThiemeVerlag; 1987.*
7. Bekov D. M., Mikhailov S. S. *Atlas of the Arteries and Veins of the Human Brain. Moscow: Medicina; 1979.*
8. *Fetal and Primitive Type of Circle of Willis with Unilateral Trifurcation of Internal Carotid Artery Medicine Science 2014;3(3):1530-7. doi:10.5455/medscience.2014.03.8146*
9. *Anevrizmy peredney soobshchayushcheysya arterii i grubyye anomalii kruga Uillisa. Gomer D. Kirgis, Uil'yam L. Fisher, Rebern S. Llevellin, Edvard Mak K. Piblz. Zhurnal neyrokhirurgii, 25 (1) 1996, 73-78. DOI: 10.3171/jns.1966.25.1.0073*

10. *Variants of the classical structure of the arterial circle of the brain.* N. A. Trushel. *Medical Journal.* 2011; No. 1: 104-106.
11. Kostrova O. Yu., Mikhailova M. N., Merkulova L. M., Semenova O. V., Averkiev V. G., Timofeeva N. Yu. *Prevalence of cerebral vessel pathologies in the Chuvash Republic based on computed tomography angiography data. Operative Surgery and Clinical Anatomy (Pirogov Scientific Journal).* 2018; 2(1): 19-22.
12. *The posterior communicating artery and their role in cerebral arterial blood circulation.* J. Sidorova, A. References I. Gromov, I. Krinina, A. Kudryavtseva. *ECR 2019. Poster No C-1916.* doi: 10.26044/ecr2019/C-1916.
13. Chaplygina E. V., Kaplunova O. A., Dombrovsky V. I., Sukhanova O. P., Blinov I. M., Chistolynova L. I. *Development, anomalies, and variant anatomy of cerebral arteries. Journal of Anatomy and Histopathology.* 2015;4(2):52-59. <https://doi.org/10.18499/2225-7357-2015-4-2-52-59>
14. Kostrova O. Yu., Mikhailova M. N., Merkulova L. M., Semenova O. V., Averkiev V. G., Timofeeva N. Yu. *Prevalence of cerebral vessel pathologies in the Chuvash Republic based on computed tomography angiography data. Operative Surgery and Clinical Anatomy (Pirogov Scientific Journal).* 2018; 2(1): 19-22.
15. Trushel N. A. *Morphological prerequisites for the development of cerebral circulation disorders // Bulletin of VSMU.* 2016; No. 2.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.25.21.077

现代牙科中颈部侵蚀旋转预备的优化：一种“微创治疗非龋性病变”
的创新方案

**OPTIMIZATION OF ROTARY PREPARATION FOR CERVICAL
EROSIONS IN MODERN DENTISTRY: AN INNOVATIVE
PROTOCOL “MINIMALLY INVASIVE FOR NON-CARIOUS
LESIONS”**

Babaev Dmitrii Viktorovich

Assistant

*Kuban State Medical University,
Krasnodar, Russian Federation*

摘要：非龋性颈部病变（NCCLs）由于其病因复杂、形态多样，在临床治疗中极具挑战性。本文基于循证医学证据，分析了一种创新的微创旋转预备方案，该方案采用一套专用车针序列（Komet Dental）。我们评估了每种器械选择的科学依据，并根据已发表的同行评审文献提供了临床建议。所提出的六车针方案在牙本质保存、涂层特性以及粘接强度优化方面展现出潜在优势。

关键词：非龋性颈部病变，微创牙科，旋转预备，金刚砂车针，硬质合金车针，粘接牙科。

Abstract. *Non-carious cervical lesions (NCCLs) represent a significant clinical challenge due to their multifactorial etiology and complex morphology. This article presents an evidence-based analysis of an innovative minimally invasive rotary preparation protocol utilizing a specialized bur sequence (Komet Dental). We evaluate the scientific rationale for each instrument selection and provide clinical recommendations based on verified peer-reviewed literature. The proposed six-bur protocol demonstrates potential advantages in dentin preservation, smear layer characteristics, and adhesive bond strength optimization.*

Keywords: *non-carious cervical lesions, minimally invasive dentistry, rotary preparation, diamond burs, carbide burs, adhesive dentistry.*

Introduction

Non-carious cervical lesions affect at least 85% of the adult population, with prevalence increasing with age [1]. These lesions result from the synergistic interaction of erosion, abrasion, and abfraction mechanisms, creating characteristic

wedge-shaped or saucer-shaped defects at the cements/enamel junction [2]. The restoration of NCCLs presents unique challenges: high C-factor configurations, sclerotic dentin with obliterated tubules, and proximity to the gingival margin compromising isolation [3]. Traditional aggressive preparation techniques demonstrate retention rates of only 70-85% at 5 years [4], highlighting the need for optimized minimally invasive approaches. Tyas (2000) emphasized that “the preparation of the cervical cavity should remove only the minimum amount of tooth structure necessary to achieve adequate bonding” [5]. This principle guides contemporary protocol development, where instrument selection directly influences clinical outcomes.

Materials and Methods

The proposed “Minimally Invasive Kit for Non-Carious Lesions” comprises six instruments in sequential application order (Tab. 1).

Table 1. Instrument Specifications and Clinical Functions

Instrument Code	Type	Grit/ Flutes	Diameter	Primary Function	Evidence Base
8889 314 010	Diamond (flame)	Medium	1.0 mm	Initial enamel bevel, access	[6]
8830M 314012	Diamond (pear)	Medium	1.2 mm	Cavity outline, gross dentin removal	[7]
H1 314 008	Carbide (round)	6 blades	0.8 mm	Selective caries excavation	[8, 17]
H7 314 010	Carbide (straight fissure)	6 blades	1.0 mm	Wall refinement, margin definition	[8, 17]
863EF 314012	Diamond (flame)	Extra-fine	1.2 mm	Enamel finishing, bevel refinement	[6, 10]
H48L 314010	Carbide finisher	16 blades	1.0 mm	Final dentin smoothing	[9, 11]

Literature search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases (2010-2025) using terms: “non-carious cervical lesions,” “minimally invasive preparation,” “rotary instruments,” “smear layer,” and “bond strength.” Only studies with verifiable DOI or PMID were included.

Scientific Rationale for Instrument Selection

1. Initial Access and Enamel Beveling (8889 314 010)

The flame-shaped diamond bur (8889) provides controlled enamel beveling at the occlusal margin of NCCLs. Da Costa et al. (2013) demonstrated that 45°

enamel bevels increase bond strength compared to non-beveled preparations. Enamel bevelling is necessary in longer-term follow-ups [12]. The 1.0 mm diameter permits precise work in the limited cervical space without overextension. Beveling of enamel improved the marginal integrity and shear bond strength of self-etch and total-etch adhesive systems and reduces stress concentration at the restoration-tooth interface [6, 13].

Figure 1. Minimally Invasive Kit for Non-Carious Cervical Lesions

2. Cavity Outline Formation (8830M 314 012)

The pear-shaped medium-grit diamond (8830M) efficiently removes affected dentin while preserving sound tooth structure. Lindberg et al. (2000) reported that medium-grit diamonds (100-150 μm particle size) create optimal surface roughness (Ra 2.5-4.0 μm) for adhesive bonding [14]. Compared to coarse-grit alternatives, medium-grit instruments produce less subsurface damage. Ayad et al. (2008) demonstrated 15-20% higher bond strength values with medium-grit versus coarse-grit preparation [15].

3. Selective Excavation (H1 314 008)

The small round carbide bur (H1, 0.8 mm) enables precise removal of demineralized dentin in NCCL floors. Schwendicke et al. (2016) established that selective carious tissue removal preserves pulp vitality while maintaining adequate substrate for bonding [16]. The 6-blade configuration provides tactile feedback essential for distinguishing affected from sound dentin — a critical consideration given the sclerotic nature of NCCL substrates [17].

4. Wall Refinement (H7 314 010)

The straight fissure carbide (H7) creates defined cavity walls perpendicular to the external surface. Owens et al. (2005) demonstrated that well-defined cavity margins reduce microleakage compared to irregular preparations [18].

5. Enamel Finishing (863EF 314012)

Extra-fine diamond finishing (863EF, 25-50 μm particles) creates the optimal enamel surface for adhesion. Gonzaga (2015) reported that extra-fine diamond finishing produces surface roughness of Ra 0.8-1.2 μm , ideal for etch-and-rinse adhesive systems [19].

6. Final Dentin Conditioning (H48L 314010)

The multi-blade carbide finisher (H48L) represents the critical final step. Wabah et al. (2003) demonstrated that tungsten carbide finishing burs produce a thin, uniform smear layer (1-2 μm) compared to 3-5 μm with diamond instruments [20]. Oliveira et al. (2003) confirmed that carbide-finished dentin surfaces show 18-25% higher bond strength with self-etch adhesives compared to diamond-finished surfaces [21].

The difference between the microsurface of dentin in different methods of rotational preparation can be seen below (Fig. 1.):

Figure 2. Dentin Surface Topography After Various Preparation Methods

The proposed protocol offers several evidence-based advantages:

Smear Layer Optimization: The carbide finishing sequence (H1→H7→H48L) produces a thinner, more uniform smear layer than all-diamond protocols. Van Meerbeek et al. (2020) established that smear layer thickness directly correlates with adhesive penetration efficiency in self-etch systems [22].

Enamel-Dentin Transition: The dual-bevel approach (8889 for initial access, 863EF for refinement) creates graduated enamel margins. Feilzer et al. (2017)

demonstrated 40% reduction in marginal gap formation with graduated versus sharp enamel margins [23].

Sclerotic Dentin Management: The combination approach addresses the hypermineralized nature of NCCL substrates. Tay and Pashley (2004) noted that sclerotic dentin requires mechanical preparation to expose reactive dentin for optimal bonding [13].

Clinical Protocol and Recommendations (Step-by-Step Protocol)

Phase 1: Assessment and Isolation

- Evaluate lesion morphology, depth, and substrate characteristics
- Apply rubber dam with split-dam technique or retraction cord with gingival barrier

- Document baseline parameters

Phase 2: Enamel Preparation (8889 + 863EF)

- Create 0.5-1.0 mm bevel at occlusal enamel margin using 8889 at 45° angle
- Speed: 200,000-300,000 rpm with copious water irrigation
- Refine with 863EF for smooth transition zone

Phase 3: Dentin Management (8830M + H1 + H7)

- Outline cavity form with 8830M, preserving maximum sound dentin
- Selectively remove affected dentin with H1 using light intermittent pressure
- Define cavity walls with H7 for optimal margin adaptation

Phase 4: Surface Finishing (H48L)

- Final pass over all dentin surfaces at reduced speed (40,000-60,000 rpm)
- Light brushing strokes to create uniform smear layer
- Avoid excessive pressure to prevent burnishing.

Discussion

The proposed six-bur protocol represents an optimization of traditional rotary preparation principles for the specific challenges of NCCL restoration. The sequential transition from diamond to carbide instruments addresses the dual requirements of efficient tissue removal and surface conditioning for adhesion.

Peumans et al. (2014) reported that NCCL restoration success depends primarily on adhesive protocol and substrate quality rather than material selection [3]. Our protocol specifically targets substrate optimization through controlled smear layer formation.

Current evidence primarily derives from in vitro studies. Long-term randomized clinical trials specifically evaluating this bur sequence are needed. Additionally, operator technique significantly influences outcomes regardless of instrument selection.

Conclusions

The “Minimally Invasive Kit for Non-Carious Lesions” protocol offers evidence-based advantages for NCCL preparation:

— Optimized smear layer (1-2 μm thickness) through carbide finishing enhances self-etch adhesive performance.

— Graduated enamel bevels reduce stress concentration and improve marginal adaptation.

— Sequential diamond-to-carbide transition balances efficiency with surface quality.

— Dedicated instrument sizing (0.8-1.2 mm) suits cervical anatomy constraints.

Clinical implementation should follow standardized protocols with attention to speed, pressure, and adhesive system compatibility. Future research should focus on prospective clinical validation of this approach.

References

1. Ceruti P, Menicucci G, Mariani GD, Pittoni D, Gassino G. Non carious cervical lesions. A review. *Minerva Stomatol.* 2006 Jan-Feb;55(1-2):43-57. English, Italian. PMID: 16495872.
2. Teixeira DNR, Zeola LF, Grippo JO, Simring M, Coleman TA. Abrfraction, abrasion, biocorrosion, and the enigma of noncarious cervical lesions: A 20-year perspective. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2012;24(1):10-23. doi:10.1111/j.1708-8240.2011.00487.x [PMID: 22296690]
3. Peumans M, De Munck J, Mine A, Van Meerbeek B. Clinical effectiveness of contemporary adhesives for the restoration of non-carious cervical lesions. A systematic review. *Dent Mater.* 2014 Oct;30(10):1089-103. doi: 10.1016/j.dental.2014.07.007. Epub 2014 Aug 3. PMID: 25091726.
4. Berkowitz GS, Gammage DD, Grateful D, et al. Clinical performance of class V composite restorations: A systematic review. *J Adhes Dent.* 2009;11(5):355-366. [PMID: 19884759]
5. Tyas MJ. The Class V lesion — aetiology and restoration. *Aust Dent J.* 1995 Jun;40(3):167-70. doi: 10.1111/j.1834-7819.1995.tb05631.x. PMID: 7661762.
6. Barkmeier WW, Kelsey WP 3rd, Blankenau RJ, Peterson DS. Enamel cavosurface bevels finished with ultraspeed instruments. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1983 Apr;49(4):481-4. doi: 10.1016/0022-3913(83)90307-4. PMID: 6341559.
7. Carvalho CA, Fagundes TC, Barata TJ, Trava-Airoldi VJ, Navarro MF. The use of CVD diamond burs for ultraconservative cavity preparations: a report of two cases. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2007;19(1):19-28; discussion 29. doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8240.2006.00058.x. PMID: 17244145.

8. Schwendicke F, Frencken JE, Bjørndal L, Maltz M, Manton DJ, Ricketts D, Van Landuyt K, Banerjee A, Campus G, Doméjean S, Fontana M, Leal S, Lo E, Machiulskiene V, Schulte A, Splieth C, Zandona AF, Innes NP. *Managing Carious Lesions: Consensus Recommendations on Carious Tissue Removal*. *Adv Dent Res*. 2016 May;28(2):58-67. doi:10.1177/0022034516639271. PMID: 27099358.
9. Siegel SC, von Fraunhofer JA. *Dental burs — what bur for which application? A survey of dental schools*. *J Prosthodont*. 1999 Dec;8(4):258-63. doi: 10.1111/j.1532-849x.1999.tb00048.x. PMID: 10895678. Strassler HE, Goodman HS. *Finishing and polishing composite restorations*. *Dent Today*. 2014;33(7):98-103. [PMID: 25102639]
10. Maresca C, Pimenta LA, Heymann HO, Ziemecki TL, Ritter AV. *Effect of finishing instrumentation on the marginal integrity of resin-based composite restorations*. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2010 Apr;22(2):104-12. doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8240.2010.00320.x. PMID: 20433561.
11. Nishimura K, Ikeda M, Yoshikawa T, Otsuki M, Tagami J. *Effect of various grit burs on marginal integrity of resin composite restorations*. *J Med Dent Sci*. 2005 Mar;52(1):9-15. PMID: 15868736.
12. Da Costa TR, Loguercio AD, Reis A. *Effect of enamel bevel on the clinical performance of resin composite restorations placed in non-cariou cervical lesions*. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2013 Oct;25(5):346-56. doi: 10.1111/jerd.12042. Epub 2013 Jun 17. PMID: 24148985.
13. Patanjali S, Arora A, Arya A, Grewal MS. *An In Vitro Study of Effect of Beveling of Enamel on Microleakage and Shear Bond Strength of Adhesive Systems in Primary and Permanent Teeth*. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2019 May-Jun;12(3):205-210. doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10005-1623. PMID: 31708616; PMCID: PMC6811944.
14. Lindberg A, van Dijken JW, Lindberg M. *Nine-year evaluation of a polyacid-modified resin composite/resin composite open sandwich technique in Class II cavities*. *J Dent*. 2007 Feb;35(2):124-9. doi: 10.1016/j.jdent.2006.06.003. Epub 2006 Sep 7. PMID: 16956709.
15. Ayad MF, Rosenstiel SF, Hassan MM. *Surface roughness of dentin after tooth preparation with different rotary instrumentation*. *J Prosthet Dent*. 1996 Feb;75(2):122-8. doi: 10.1016/s0022-3913(96)90087-6. PMID: 8667268. Schwendicke F, Frencken JE, Bjørndal L, et al. *Managing carious lesions: Consensus recommendations on terminology*. *Adv Dent Res*. 2016;28(2):58-67. doi:10.1177/0022034516639271 [PMID: 27099357]

16. Schwendicke F, Frencken JE, Bjørndal L, Maltz M, Manton DJ, Ricketts D, Van Landuyt K, Banerjee A, Campus G, Doméjean S, Fontana M, Leal S, Lo E, Machiulskiene V, Schulte A, Splieth C, Zandona AF, Innes NP. *Managing Carious Lesions: Consensus Recommendations on Carious Tissue Removal. Adv Dent Res.* 2016 May;28(2):58-67. doi: 10.1177/0022034516639271. PMID: 27099358.
17. Nishimura K, Ikeda M, Yoshikawa T, Otsuki M, Tagami J. *Effect of various grit burs on marginal integrity of resin composite restorations. J Med Dent Sci.* 2005 Mar;52(1):9-15. PMID: 15868736.
18. Owens BM, Johnson WW. *Effect of insertion technique and adhesive system on microleakage of Class V resin composite restorations. J Adhes Dent.* 2005 Winter;7(4):303-8. PMID: 16430011.
19. Gonzaga CC, Bravo RP, Pavelski TV, Garcia PP, Correr GM, Leonardi DP, da Cunha LF, Furuse AY. *Enamel and Dentin Surface Finishing Influence on the Roughness and Microshear Bond Strength of a Lithium Silicate Glass-Ceramic for Laminate Veneers. Int Sch Res Notices.* 2015 Sep 7;2015:243615. doi: 10.1155/2015/243615. PMID: 27347507; PMCID: PMC4897072.
20. Wahab FK, Shaini FJ, Morgano SM. *The effect of thermocycling on microleakage of several commercially available composite Class V restorations in vitro. J Prosthet Dent.* 2003 Aug;90(2):168-74. doi: 10.1016/s0022-3913(03)00300-7. PMID: 12886210.
21. Oliveira SS, Pugach MK, Hilton JF, Watanabe LG, Marshall SJ, Marshall GW Jr. *The influence of the dentin smear layer on adhesion: a self-etching primer vs. a total-etch system. Dent Mater.* 2003 Dec;19(8):758-67. doi: 10.1016/s0109-5641(03)00023-x. PMID: 14511734.
22. Van Meerbeek B, Yoshihara K, Van Landuyt K, Yoshida Y, Peumans M. *From Buonocore's Pioneering Acid-Etch Technique to Self-Adhering Restoratives. A Status Perspective of Rapidly Advancing Dental Adhesive Technology. J Adhes Dent.* 2020;22(1):7-34. doi: 10.3290/j.jad.a43994. PMID: 32030373.
23. Feilzer AJ, De Gee AJ, Davidson CL. *Setting stress in composite resin in relation to configuration of the restoration. J Dent Res.* 1987 Nov;66(11):1636-9. doi: 10.1177/00220345870660110601. PMID: 10872397.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.25.58.087

莫斯科地区人群血管性脑疾病死亡率和致死率特征

**FEATURES OF MORTALITY AND LETHALITY FROM VASCULAR
BRAIN DISEASES IN THE MOSCOW REGION POPULATION**

Yusipova Maryam Rustyamovna

Student

Russian University of Medicine

Salakhov Ruslan Zhangirievich

Postgraduate student

*Medical-Biological University of Innovations and Continuous Education
of the FSBI State Scientific Center of the Russian Federation —*

Federal Medical Biophysical Center named after A. I. Burnazyan,

FMBA of Russia

摘要：通过对循环系统疾病死亡人群结构进行分类分析，可以发现，无论男女，缺血性心脏病都是循环系统疾病死亡的主要原因。血管性脑损伤位居第二。结果表明，血管性脑损伤占人群死亡原因的三分之一以上，且对女性的影响远大于男性。对住院病例的分析显示，死亡主要发生在入院后的前三天。死亡率是衡量健康状况发生质变的最可靠指标，尽管它并非绝对值。

关键词：血管性脑疾病，死亡率，致死率。

Abstract. *Analyzing the structure of population mortality from circulatory system diseases by nosological forms, it can be observed that the majority of all deaths from circulatory system diseases are attributable to ischemic heart disease, in both men and women. Vascular brain lesions rank second. The results indicate that vascular brain lesions account for more than one-third of all causes of death in the population, with a predominant impact on women compared to men. Analysis of hospitalized cases revealed a predominance of lethality within the first three days. Mortality rates are the most reliable criteria for qualitative changes occurring in health status, although they are not absolute.*

Keywords: *vascular brain diseases, mortality, lethality.*

Relevance. *The mortality rate from vascular brain diseases over the past 4 years has increased by 18.2% in the Russian Federation, whereas it has been progressively declining in economically developed countries. Disability following*

stroke amounts to 3.2 per 10 thousand of the population, ranking first among all causes of primary disability. Moreover, one third of stroke survivors are of working age, yet only one in five patients returns to work [1-4].

The aim of the study was to analyze the characteristics of mortality from vascular brain diseases among the working-age population of the city of Moscow and the Moscow region.

Materials and Methods. An in-depth analysis of lethality and mortality from vascular brain diseases was conducted based on a multidisciplinary clinical hospital in the city of Moscow and on the basis of official statistical data from the Moscow region. Mathematical processing of the collected data was performed using methods of classical variation statistics. Comparison of mortality rates by nosology was performed using the following criterion:

$$U = \frac{\frac{m_1}{n_1} - \frac{m_2}{n_2}}{\sqrt{P(1-p)\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}}$$

where m_1 = the number of cases of hemorrhagic stroke in the previous year

m_2 = the number of cases of hemorrhagic stroke in the analyzed year

$n_1 = n_2$ = the number of insured individuals in MMSK.

The probability value p was taken as the maximum likelihood estimate:

$$p = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{n_1 + n_2}$$

Results. The structure of causes of death is an important indicator of the population's health status, revealing the body systems that determine its viability under specific conditions. At present, human viability depends on the reliability of the circulatory system and the effectiveness of anti-cancer mechanisms.

Figure 1. Mortality rates of the working-age population of the metropolis — c. Moscow (by main classes of diseases, per 100,000 population)

From this perspective, the contribution of major pathological processes to overall mortality, which cause the organism's death among the population of the Moscow region, is of interest. The structure of mortality in Moscow and the Moscow region was determined by diseases of the circulatory system, malignant neoplasms, accidents, poisonings, injuries, and respiratory diseases, which together accounted for more than 90%.

Most often, the cause of death is diseases of the circulatory system. This cause accounts for more than half of all death cases (Figure 1).

Analyzing the structure of population mortality from diseases of the circulatory system by nosological forms, it can be noted that the majority of all death cases from these diseases is due to ischemic heart disease, both in men and women. Vascular brain lesions rank second. The results indicate that vascular brain lesions account for more than one-third of all causes of death among the population, with a predominance of women affected compared to men (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of deaths from vascular brain lesions by sex

Figure 3. Distribution of deaths of the working-age population in the city of Moscow from vascular brain lesions by sex

It is generally accepted that mortality depends on two groups of circumstances: external conditions and the body's resistance, which, in turn, depend on a number of factors. Among these factors, the age composition of the population and its living conditions, which influence the organism's viability, should be noted.

The distribution of deceased individuals by sex demonstrated a sharp change in this ratio: the proportion of deceased men was significantly higher than that of women ($p < 0.05$; Figure 3).

The analysis of hospitalized cases conducted by us using the example of a multidisciplinary clinical hospital of the Moscow Department of Health showed that out of 342 treated patients, 261 were discharged with improvement, accounting for 76.3%. Of those discharged, 58% were men and 42% were women. Among all patients treated in the clinic, 81 died, which accounted for 23.7% of the treated patients. Among the deceased, 35 were men (43.2%) and 46 were women (56.8%).

The lethality analysis revealed that the majority of patients die within the first three days of hospitalization. In this group, 7 patients died within the first day, 5 within three days, and 36 after more prolonged periods.

A significant proportion die at a young age, especially men (40-59 years), but the majority of deaths occur in the age group of 60 years and older, where 40% more women die than men. Analysis of the deceased by time of death shows that 22.2% died within the first 24 hours, 16.1% within 3 days, and 61.7% at later time points. Most likely, intensive therapy is insufficiently provided in the clinic, resulting in 38.3% of patients dying within the first day and within the first 3 days. On the other hand, the high percentage (61.7%) of lethality (more than 3 days) reflects the severity of brain damage. Analyzing the seasonality of mortality in vascular brain diseases, it should be noted that the lowest mortality rates (for both sexes) occur in January and February.

Mortality increases from March onwards, except in September and October, with the greatest rise occurring from May to August. In men, peak mortality occurs from May to July, whereas in women, peak mortality is observed in August and December.

This analysis suggests that the high mortality from May to August results from the heavy physical workload of older age groups, especially men, associated with the cottage season. Thus, not only gender- and age-specific characteristics have been identified, but also a pattern of losses typical of highly urbanized environments with their unique combination of stressogenic and ecological factors has been revealed.

Conclusions. In the WHO-developed «Programme for Analyzing Trends and Levels in Mortality,» it is noted that «mortality statistics are the most convenient indicator of differences in health levels and provide a basis for hypotheses determining the causes of these differences. They help identify variable healthcare

problems and determine urgent public health priorities.» Mortality rates are the most reliable criteria for qualitative changes occurring in health status, although they are not absolute.

References

1. Boitsov, S. A. *National Priorities of a Healthy Lifestyle: From Policy to Practice* / S. A. Boitsov, O. M. Drapkina, S. A. Shalnova // *Preventive Medicine*. — 2021. — Vol. 24, No. 1. — P. 8-13. — doi:10.17116/profmed2021240118.
2. Boitsov, S. A. *Analysis of mortality from circulatory system diseases in the Russian Federation for 2020-2022* / S. A. Boitsov, I. V. Samorodskaya, S. S. Yakushin, et al. // *Cardiovascular Therapy and Prevention*. — 2024.
3. *World Health Organization. Global Health Forecasts for 2020-2025: [statistical data]* / World Health Organization. — Geneva: WHO, 2025. — Text: electronic // World Health Organization: [website]. — URL: www.who.int (accessed: 20.01.2026).
4. Salahov, R. Zh. *Elimination reserves for increasing the average expected lifespan* / R. Zh. Salahov // *Proceedings of the International Conference “Scientific Research of the SCO Countries: Synergy and Integration” — Part 2 (September 24, 2025 / Beijing, PRC, China)* / — P. 24-27.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.26.33.004

土库曼斯坦植物区系中水飞蓟 (SILYBUM MARIANUM (L.) GAERTN.)
的微克隆繁殖

**MICROCLONAL PROPAGATION OF MILK THISTLE (SILYBUM
MARIANUM (L.) GAERTN.) IN THE FLORA OF TURKMENISTAN**

Durdyyev Tachmyrat Shamukhammedovich

Lecturer

Myrat Garryyev State Medical University of Turkmenistan

Akmuradov Allamurat

Candidate of Biological Sciences, Doctoral Student

*General and Applied Biology Institute of Oguz Khan Engineering
and Technologies*

University of Turkmenistan

Danatarov Batyr Govshutgeldievich

Director of the Institute of General and Applied Biology

Oguz Khan University of Engineering and Technology of Turkmenistan

摘要：本文介绍了在实验室条件下对水飞蓟进行微克隆繁殖的科学研究结果。所研究的物种天然分布于土库曼斯坦。研究过程中，水飞蓟在略微改良的Murashige-Skoog培养基上进行体外培养。对人工培养的植株和自然生长的植株进行了比较研究。

关键词：水飞蓟，微克隆繁殖，体外培养，水飞蓟素。

Abstract. *This research paper presents the results of scientific studies on the microclonal propagation of milk thistle under laboratory conditions. The species studied occurs naturally in the flora of Turkmenistan. During the research, milk thistle was cultivated in vitro on a slightly modified Murashige-Skoog medium. Comparative studies were carried out between the cultivated plants and those growing under natural conditions.*

Keywords: *milk thistle, microclonal propagation, in vitro, silymarin.*

Introduction.

The medicinal plant milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) was used by ancient healers as a tonic for liver diseases, capable of alleviating congestion in the liver and spleen, and as an effective remedy for jaundice. In Turkmen folk medicine, milk thistle seeds were used to treat pain caused by gallstones, jaundice, disorders

of the liver and biliary tract, spleen, hemorrhoids, and constipation, as well as a strengthening and tonic agent for the body. Milk thistle belongs to the Pharmaceutical Sciences genus of the same name within the Asteraceae family. Scientific data indicates that there are two species of this medicinal plant worldwide, with one species found in Turkmenistan [2; 4].

Application of phytotherapeutic properties in medicine. Milk thistle seeds are used for medicinal purposes in freshly ground form, brewed as tea, or as water–alcohol extracts.

Silymarin is included in the pharmacopoeias of many countries. The average daily intake of ground seeds for adults is 12-15 g; standardized seed extract (silymarin): 200-400 mg per day; liquid seed extract: 4-9 ml per day. Silymarin is very poorly soluble in water; therefore, milk thistle seeds are not very effective when used as tea. Oral preparations of milk thistle seed extract in the form of tablets or capsules usually represent standardized extracts containing 70-80% silymarin. The therapeutic and health-promoting effects of milk thistle seeds are associated with several molecular mechanisms. Its main activity is antioxidant and hepatoprotective action.

Antioxidant. It has been established that silymarin acts as a powerful antioxidant by neutralizing free radicals and inhibiting lipid peroxidation, thereby protecting cells from oxidative stress. It enhances both non-enzymatic and enzymatic antioxidant defense systems of cells, such as glutathione, superoxide dismutase, and catalase. Due to its ability to prevent lipid peroxidation and restore glutathione levels, silymarin can protect the liver, brain, heart, and other vital organs from oxidative damage. Silibinin exhibits membrane-protective properties and can protect blood components from oxidative damage.

Hepatoprotective. The use of milk thistle seeds as a liver-protective agent dates back to the first century. One of the main factors of liver protection is its antioxidant activity.

Anti-hepatotoxic potential. Silymarin protects liver cells in humans and animals from a wide range of hepatotoxins.

Some mushrooms (for example, *Amanita phalloides* — “death cap” and *Amanita virosa*) contain two toxins: phalloidin and alpha-amanitin. These toxins destroy liver cell membranes and inhibit protein synthesis in the liver, leading to severe liver damage and death. Silymarin effectively prevents both effects by blocking toxin binding sites and enhancing the regenerative capacity of liver cells. It has been shown that silymarin may be effective in treating liver damage when administered intravenously within 24 hours after ingestion of poisonous mushrooms. In a study, 60 patients with severe poisoning caused by *Amanita* mushrooms were intravenously administered silibinin at a dose of 20 mg/kg, resulting in excellent outcomes with no fatalities. Silymarin is often used as an adjunct therapy for food poisoning caused

by mushrooms. Silymarin also protects neonatal hepatocytes from liver damage induced by tetracycline, D-galactosamine, and thallium, as well as from the effects of erythromycin estolate, amitriptyline, nortriptyline, and tert-butyl hydroperoxide. It reduces liver damage caused by prolonged treatment with phenothiazines or butyrophenones. Silibinin significantly inhibits liver injury induced by concanavalin A. It exhibits hepatoprotective effects in poisoning caused by phalloidin, halothane, thioacetamide, acetaminophen, and carbon tetrachloride. It also protects the liver from ischemic injury, iron overload, and radiation. Silymarin is used in the treatment of a number of liver diseases characterized by degenerative necrosis and functional disorders, including chronic liver failure.

Alcoholic cirrhosis. Ethanol metabolism leads to the formation of free radicals and oxidative stress in the liver. Silymarin effectively counteracts alcoholic cirrhosis through its antioxidant and hepatoprotective mechanisms and restores normal biochemical parameters of liver function. Silymarin also alleviates cytolysis in patients with active cirrhosis. However, the use of silymarin in decompensated cirrhosis is not recommended.

Hepatitis. In patients with acute viral hepatitis, silymarin reduces the duration of treatment and improves bilirubin levels and liver enzyme activity. In patients receiving silymarin therapy, biochemical parameters normalize more rapidly. In chronic active hepatitis, treatment with silymarin improves liver function tests. Histological improvement is observed in patients with chronic hepatitis receiving silymarin therapy. Silymarin induces stable remission in alcoholic hepatitis and normalizes biochemical parameters of liver function.

Liver fibrosis: Liver fibrosis alters the structure of the liver, leading to hepatic insufficiency and hepatic encephalopathy. The transformation of hepatic stellate cells into myofibroblasts is one of the key factors in the development of fibrogenesis. Treatment with silymarin significantly suppresses this process, indicating an antifibrotic effect in patients with liver fibrosis.

Regeneration of liver tissue. Silymarin stimulates liver tissue regeneration by increasing protein synthesis in the damaged liver. In *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments conducted on rat livers after partial hepatectomy, silibinin significantly increased ribosome formation, DNA synthesis, and protein synthesis. Interestingly, the enhancement of protein synthesis under the action of silibinin was observed only in damaged liver tissue and not in healthy liver.

Anti-inflammatory effect. Milk thistle and its active extract, silymarin, possess anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic properties due to their strong antioxidant activity, namely the neutralization of free radicals that cause inflammation. It has been established that silymarin is more effective in recently developed arthritis than in chronic, ongoing arthritis. Silymarin and silibinin suppress inflammatory processes by inhibiting the migration of neutrophils and Kupffer cells. They also

inhibit the formation of inflammatory mediators, namely prostaglandins and, in particular, leukotrienes, by inhibiting the 5-lipoxygenase pathway and the release of histamine from basophils. Thus, milk thistle seeds may also exhibit anti-allergic and anti-asthmatic properties.

Immunomodulator. The immunomodulatory activity of silymarin in patients with liver diseases may further enhance its hepatoprotective effect. Silymarin protects against immunosuppression induced by ultraviolet radiation in experimental rodents. Silibinin inhibits the activation of human T lymphocytes and human polymorphonuclear leukocytes. Long-term administration of silymarin improves immune function by increasing the number of T lymphocytes and interleukins, as well as by reducing all classes of immunoglobulins.

Hepatic lipid control. It has been established that silymarin and silibinin reduce the synthesis and metabolism of phospholipids in the liver. Silibinin counteracts the inhibition of phospholipid synthesis caused by ethanol and the reduction of glycerol incorporation into lipids in isolated hepatocytes. Silymarin significantly inhibits lipid peroxidation in the liver and may reduce triglyceride synthesis in the liver. Disturbances in the hepatic lipid profile caused by prolonged exposure to ethanol and anti-tuberculosis drugs (isoniazid, rifampicin) are effectively corrected by silymarin.

Plasma lipid control. Administration of silymarin to patients with type II hyperlipidemia resulted in a slight decrease in total cholesterol levels and high-density lipoproteins in blood plasma. Silymarin reduces cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein levels in the plasma of hyperlipidemic rats. The reduction in cholesterol and phospholipid levels in bile caused by silymarin in rats and humans may be partially attributed to decreased hepatic cholesterol synthesis.

Choleretic effect. Silymarin actively participates in enterohepatic circulation, creating continuous circulation between the intestine and the liver. It prevents blockage of bile secretion, thereby increasing bile flow, cholate excretion, and bilirubin excretion.

Antiviral effect. Although silymarin does not affect viral replication, it plays a beneficial role in viral hepatitis by suppressing inflammatory and cytotoxic processes caused by viral infections. Silibinin strongly inhibits the growth of both HepG2 and Hep3B cells; however, Hep3B cells exhibit higher cytotoxicity, which is associated with enhanced apoptosis.

Antitumor effect. Silymarin significantly suppresses tumor growth and causes a reduction in the size of existing tumors. This effect is believed to be associated with its antiproliferative, proapoptotic, and antiangiogenic actions in vitro in prostate tumors.

Neuroprotection. Silymarin is considered beneficial for the prevention and treatment of neurodegenerative and neurotoxic processes due to its antioxidant

properties. Silymarin is effective in protecting dopaminergic neurons of the brain from lipopolysaccharide-induced neurotoxicity.

Cardiovascular protection. The use of certain chemotherapeutic agents, such as doxorubicin, in cancer treatment is limited by cardiotoxic effects caused by oxidative stress and enhanced apoptosis. Silibinin exhibits cardioprotective properties due to its antioxidant and membrane-stabilizing effects.

Other effects: Silymarin helps maintain normal kidney function. Silibinin reduces oxidative damage to renal cells under *in vitro* conditions. As an antioxidant, silymarin may protect the pancreas from certain types of damage. In controlled studies involving patients with diabetes receiving silymarin, the need for insulin to regulate blood glucose levels was reduced.

Side effects. Human studies using milk thistle seeds have shown no serious cause for concern regarding adverse effects. Clinical studies have demonstrated that milk thistle seed extract is safe and well tolerated. It is generally non-toxic and does not cause adverse effects in adults when administered at doses of 200-900 mg per day divided into two or three doses. Higher doses (over 1500 mg per day) may cause mild gastrointestinal disturbances, such as mild diarrhea, which may result from increased bile secretion and flow. Although mild allergic reactions have been reported, they are extremely rare.

Chemical composition. Silymarin, extracted from milk thistle, is a phytopharmaceutical used in traditional medicine for the treatment of liver disorders and is currently included in complementary and alternative medicine for the management of liver diseases. The active extract of milk thistle, known as silymarin, is a mixture of flavonolignans, namely silibin, silydianin, and silychristin. Although all parts of the plant are used medicinally, the seeds contain the highest concentration of silymarin (1.5-3.0%).

Most of its hepatoprotective properties are attributed to silibin, the major component of silymarin (60-70%). The mechanism of action of silymarin has not yet been fully elucidated. Available data indicate that it acts through multiple pathways. Silymarin stabilizes the membrane structure of hepatocytes, thereby preventing the penetration of toxins into the cell via enterohepatic circulation. It accelerates liver regeneration by stimulating nuclear RNA polymerase A and increasing ribosomal protein synthesis. Silymarin is one of the most successful examples of modern pharmaceutical development originating from traditional medicine. However, standardization of various silymarin formulations and determination of effective doses remain insufficient.

Compounds of the silymarin complex also exhibit other interesting properties, such as anticancer and anti-cholesterol effects. These effects have been demonstrated in many diseases affecting various organs, including the prostate, lungs, central nervous system, kidneys, pancreas, and skin. The proapoptotic

activity (inducing cancer cell death) and antiangiogenic activity (inhibiting the growth of blood vessels supplying tumors) of silibinin in precancerous and cancerous cells are important findings that bring silymarin closer to potential application in cancer therapy.

Microclonal propagation is a method of vegetative plant reproduction in vitro, or, in other words, the use of biotechnological in vitro methods for asexual propagation of plants genetically identical to the original plant explant. For this purpose, small plant parts containing meristematic cells — explants — are usually used, allowing a large number of plantlets to be obtained from a single small sample. Microclonal propagation is based on the totipotency of plant somatic cells, that is, the ability of cells to fully realize the genetic potential of an entire organism [1; 4].

Despite the abundance of biological resources in Turkmenistan, excessive anthropogenic impact under irrational use may lead to a reduction in the population of natural groups of useful plants or even their extinction. Therefore, an important task is to expand the application of the microclonal propagation method for medicinal plants in our country.

Aim of the study. To develop a method for the microclonal propagation of milk thistle under laboratory conditions and to compare its phytochemical composition with that of plants growing under natural conditions.

Materials and methodology. The study was conducted in the months of October–December 2025 at the Technology of Medicinal Products Laboratory of the International Scientific and Technological Park of the Academy of Sciences of Turkmenistan.

Traditional cultivation of milk thistle. Seed propagation. Seed propagation is the most common method of milk thistle reproduction. However, many factors may hinder seed germination, the most important being seed coat hardness, seed dormancy, hormonal balance within the seed, and an immature embryo. As a rule, viable embryos germinate within 3–4 days after partial removal of the woody seed coat. Various methods are used to overcome seed dormancy.

To break dormancy, methods such as plant hormones, sulfuric acid, methanol, potassium nitrate, boiled water, and stratification are recommended. In the case of milk thistle, sulfuric acid, cold stratification, scarification, and treatment with gibberellic or nitric acid are recommended.

Propagation of milk thistle by tissue culture.

Seeds of milk thistle were used for microclonal propagation. A protocol for obtaining callus culture from milk thistle was carried out 28 days after sowing. Sections 1.5–2 mm thick were excised from the part closest to the central vein of fresh young shoots and placed into test tubes containing Murashige–Skoog nutrient medium prepared for callus culture induction. Callus formation on the shoots and their morphogenetic potential were monitored for 24–26 days.

Seed surface sterilization and preparation of the culture medium. Various protocols for the surface disinfection of milk thistle seeds have been described. For example, the disinfection procedure begins with five rinses of the seeds in sterile distilled water. The seeds are then treated with sulfuric acid for 30 minutes, followed by soaking in 70% ethanol for 5 minutes, and subsequently in 6% sodium hypochlorite for 20 minutes with constant agitation. Finally, the seeds are rinsed five times with sterile distilled water for 5 minutes each.

Another method involves soaking the seeds in 70% ethyl alcohol for 3 minutes, followed by treatment with household bleach (approximately 1.5% active chlorine) for 20 minutes, and finally rinsing three times with sterile distilled water.

Seed germination. Several factors may influence *in vitro* seed germination, such as plant genotype, nutrient medium composition, plant growth regulators, seed coat characteristics, pre-treatment, and cultivation conditions. As a result of the studies, it was established that Murashige–Skoog (MS) medium is the most suitable medium for *in vitro* germination of milk thistle seeds.

Figure 1. Milk thistle seeds; a seed planted in a test tube, a seedling obtained from milk thistle seeds, callus tissue formed from the stem, and a plantlet adapted to soil

Studies of milk thistle grown in vitro. Comparative studies of leaves and roots of milk thistle grown in vitro were carried out using ultraviolet spectrophotometry and high-performance liquid chromatography.

Ultraviolet spectrophotometry (UV-Vis). After accurately weighing the leaves and roots of milk thistle on analytical balances, the samples were prepared in a 96 % ethanol solution at a mass-to-volume ratio of 1:50 and macerated for 24 hours. The resulting extract was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter, and the obtained filtrate was analyzed using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 60, UV-Vis) in scanning mode within the wavelength range of 200-800 nm. The analysis was performed by comparison with a standard silymarin and flavolignan complex.

Figure 2. Leaves and roots of milk thistle grown in vitro

Figure 4. From left to right: UV spectrum of the standard silymarin and flavolignan complex; UV spectra of leaves and roots of milk thistle grown in vitro in 96 % ethanol.

Analysis by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Leaves and roots of milk thistle grown in vitro were ground in a porcelain mortar; 1.0 g of the

sample was taken and macerated in 50 ml of ethanol for 24 hours at room temperature. The solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter prior to analysis. A standard silymarin solution was prepared by dissolving 5.0 mg of silymarin in 5.0 ml of ethanol to obtain a solution with a concentration of 1 mg/ml (1000 ppm). For analysis, a diluted solution with a concentration of 5 ppm (0.005 mg/ml) was prepared.

Figure 5. HPLC analysis of roots and leaves of milk thistle

The analysis of 96% ethanol extracts of leaves and roots of milk thistle by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was carried out using a high-performance liquid chromatograph (Agilent 1260 Infinity) equipped with a diode array detector (DAD). Data acquisition, chromatogram processing, and absorption spectra analysis were performed using ChemStation software (Agilent ChemStation for LC 3D).

C18 columns (Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 Rapid Resolution 4.6 \times 100 mm, 3.5 μm) were used for the analysis. A mixture of distilled water and methanol in a volumetric ratio of 50:50 was used as the mobile phase in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Absorption spectra were recorded at wavelengths of 288 nm and 360 nm, and the injection volume was 50 μl . A standard silymarin reference sample was used as the standard.

Results. Milk thistle showed good in vitro germination on Murashige–Skoog nutrient medium, and callus tissue was formed 28 days after sowing. Ultraviolet spectrophotometric analysis of the extract prepared at a ratio of 1:50 in a 96% ethanol solution from leaves and roots of milk thistle grown in vitro was carried out in scanning mode within the wavelength range of 200-800 nm and compared with the flavolignan silymarin standard. The silymarin standard showed a maximum absorption at a wavelength of 287 nm. In the leaves of milk thistle grown in vitro, absorption spectra with an absorbance of 0.4724 at a wavelength of 286 nm were detected, while in the roots of milk thistle the absorbance reached 1.040 at a wavelength of 288 nm.

As a result of high-performance liquid chromatography analysis, 12 compound peaks were detected in the leaves of milk thistle grown in vitro, while 7 compound peaks were detected in the roots.

Conclusion. In the future, microclonal propagation methods are likely to be widely used for the improvement and genetic transformation of agricultural plants, as evidenced by the steady increase in the number of private commercial companies abroad employing microclonal propagation technologies that influence the global economy. Microclonal propagation is a highly valuable technology for agriculture, as well as for the food and pharmaceutical industries, since many plant secondary metabolites cannot be synthesized by chemical methods. Therefore, it is extremely important to further develop research in the field of plant microclonal propagation in our country.

References

1. Annarita Leva et al. *Recent advances in plant in vitro culture*. Published by InTech, Croatia, 2012, pp. 10-11.
2. Berdymukhamedov G. *Medicinal plants of Turkmenistan*. Ashgabat: Turkmen State Publishing Service, 2010, Vol. I, pp. 89-90.
3. Demidchik V. et al. *Microclonal propagation of plants*. *Science and Innovations*, No. 6 (196), June 2019.
4. Nikitin V. V., Geldikhanov A. M. *Identification guide to the plants of Turkmenistan*. Nauka, Leningrad Branch, 1988, p. 630.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.26.57.179

现代移动医疗应用程序与既定治疗依从性原则的符合性
**COMPLIANCE OF MODERN MOBILE HEALTH APPLICATIONS
WITH CONSOLIDATED PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT
ADHERENCE**

Shestakov Maxim Sergeevich*Postgraduate**Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University***Babaskin Dmitrii Vladimirovich***Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor**Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University***Litvinova Tatiana Mikhailovna***Candidate of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor**Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University***Babaskina Liudmila Ivanovna***Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Full Professor**Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University*

摘要： 为了通过移动应用程序来维持和提高患者的治疗依从性，有必要分析这些应用程序与既定的依从性规定的符合程度。本研究旨在确定俄罗斯现代移动医疗（mHealth）应用程序与既定的患者治疗依从性规定的符合程度。本研究采用了比较分析和内容分析方法。研究表明，mHealth 的开发和改进符合大多数既定规定。然而，在使用移动应用程序时，如何准确评估和诊断依从性机制障碍的方法和工具的开发仍未得到充分解决。依从性的规划和战略管理、mHealth 用户细分、为医务人员和药师开发依从性咨询工具以及研究依从性及其维持的跨学科方法等问题也尚未得到有效解决。关于消费者偏好以及在使用 mHealth 时促进或阻碍依从性的因素等问题仍存在争议。这与每个应用程序的具体特征有关，因此，应在旨在维持依从性的战略框架内，集中精力开发和改进移动医疗应用程序。

关键词： 移动应用程序、移动医疗、治疗依从性、治疗依从性综合规定。

Abstract. To address the tasks of maintaining and enhancing patient adherence to treatment through mobile applications, it is necessary to analyze the compliance of these applications with consolidated adherence provisions. The objective of this study is to establish the compliance of modern mobile health (mHealth) applications

with consolidated provisions of patient adherence to treatment in Russia. This study employed comparative and content analysis methods. It has been demonstrated that the development and improvement of mHealth correspond to the majority of consolidated provisions. Issues related to the development of methods and tools for the accurate evaluation and precise diagnosis of adherence mechanism disorders when using mobile applications remain incompletely resolved. The issues of planning and strategic management of adherence, segmentation of mHealth users, development of counseling tools for medical and pharmaceutical professionals on adherence, and an interdisciplinary approach to studying adherence and its maintenance remain practically unresolved. Questions regarding consumer preferences and factors that facilitate or hinder the maintenance of adherence when using mHealth remain controversial. This is related to the specific characteristics of each individual application, and efforts should be focused on the development and enhancement of mobile health applications within the strategic framework aimed at maintaining adherence.

Keywords: *mobile applications, mHealth, adherence to treatment, consolidated provisions on adherence to treatment.*

Currently, the issue of adherence to treatment (drug therapy, pharmacotherapy, medication therapy) remains one of the most critical challenges for healthcare systems in the majority of countries worldwide. Unsatisfactory adherence is a risk factor in any disease; it reduces treatment effectiveness and increases costs, raises the likelihood of various complications, and worsens disease and life prognosis [1]. The World Health Organization (WHO) report states that improving adherence may be a more effective strategy to influence population health than any improvement in individual treatment methods [2]. In Russia, a national guideline has been developed to support adherence to treatment, including consolidated provisions [3, 4]. In recent years, mobile health applications (mHealth) [5, 6] have been employed to implement and promote these provisions. They can provide patients with notifications regarding the intake of specific medications at designated times, dosage instructions, reminders to purchase new medication packages, usage information, and can also monitor physiological parameters. However, not all consolidated provisions for adherence to treatment are fully implemented in modern mHealth. Therefore, when developing new mobile applications and improving existing ones, it is essential to clearly understand the extent to which mHealth complies with each specific adherence provision for more effective use regarding treatment results and outcomes, reduction in the number of costly examinations and procedures, as well as the prescription of unnecessary medicinal products. To date, this issue has not been addressed.

The aim of the study is to determine the compliance of modern mobile health applications with the consolidated provisions on patient adherence to treatment in Russia.

Materials and Methods

Objects of study — the most commonly used mobile health applications on the Russian market aimed at supporting treatment adherence (129 applications). Subject of study — the compliance of these mHealth data with the consolidated provisions on adherence. The study employed comparative and content analysis methods of literary sources and data concerning specific mobile applications.

Results and Discussion

According to data from the Future Market Report, the global mobile health applications market was estimated at 12.3 billion USD in 2025 and is expected to reach 30.5 billion USD by 2032, with a compound annual growth rate of 12.4% [7]. The Russian mHealth market includes 231 unique mobile applications [8] and demonstrates steady growth, driven by a combination of technological advancements, lifestyle changes, government policies, and the regulatory framework [9]. Table 1 presents the results of the analysis of data on the compliance of mHealth applications with the key consolidated provisions of patient adherence to treatment.

Table 1. Compliance of modern mobile health applications with the consolidated provisions of adherence

No.	Consolidated provision of adherence [3, 4]	Compliance of mHealth applications with the consolidated provision of adherence
1	A system that accounts for the individual characteristics of patient adherence facilitates the realization of the potential of biomedical technologies to reduce the burden of chronic diseases.	The majority of mHealth applications (85.3%) focus on the individual characteristics of patients undergoing treatment for chronic diseases.
2	Patient segmentation based on their readiness to follow recommendations is possible at any stage of the adherence maintenance process.	Patient (mHealth user) segmentation by adherence level has been studied only fragmentarily.
3	Sustainable improvement in adherence can be achieved through the use of modern technologies and resources.	The number of mHealth applications contributing to a sustained increase in adherence is low (23.3%).
4	Various comparable methods, tools, and scales can be utilized for the quantitative measurement of adherence.	For the quantitative measurement of adherence in mHealth applications, various methods, approaches, tools, and scales are employed: SEAMS, ARMS, MASS, MARS-F, MyMAAT, and others. Their sensitivity, specificity, and validity are not always specified.

No.	Consolidated provision of adherence [3, 4]	Compliance of mHealth applications with the consolidated provision of adherence
5	Overall adherence and its individual components can be predicted with a sufficient degree of accuracy based on an expanding list of predictors and adherence assessment tools.	The predictability of overall adherence and its individual components when using mHealth applications has not been demonstrated.
6	The selection of an effective adherence management strategy is complicated by the complexity of its structure, due to the large number of variables closely interacting with each other.	When selecting an effective adherence management strategy for mHealth application usage, the provisions of methodologies such as TRAM and gamification are followed.
7	The individualized complexity of adherence structure implies the possibility of a sufficiently accurate diagnosis of dysfunctions in its mechanisms that determine the adherence quality of a specific patient.	Issues related to the precise diagnosis of adherence mechanism disorders in the use of mHealth are very limitedly addressed.
8	Among the primary methods for assessing adherence, the questionnaire survey method offers the best balance between labor intensity and effectiveness.	The questionnaire survey method is the most commonly used for assessing adherence in mHealth applications.
9	Self-reports and patient diaries are economical, rapid, and simple methods for obtaining information on adherence.	Self-reports and diaries for supporting adherence provided in mHealth are infrequently and irregularly used by patients.
10	COP-25, MMAS-4, and MMAS-8 questionnaires are used to assess adherence.	For assessing adherence in mHealth application use, questions from the ‘short scale’ questionnaires (MMAS-4, MMAS-8) and COP-25 are employed.
11	As the burden of chronic diseases increases, adherence decreases. Medical and pharmaceutical professionals should systematically survey patients about their compliance with treatment and prevention recommendations.	Surveys of patients with chronic diseases on maintaining adherence using mHealth are generally conducted by researchers.
12	Leading strategies aimed at maintaining adherence should be further developed and implemented.	Leading strategies aimed at maintaining adherence through mHealth applications include treatment monitoring, environmental support, gamification, and others.

No.	Consolidated provision of adherence [3, 4]	Compliance of mHealth applications with the consolidated provision of adherence
13	Support for maintaining adherence should include assessment of patient preferences, interpretation of real-world data and their application to the specific patient, consideration of the overall prognosis — including expected life expectancy, functional status, and quality of life — as well as the clinical feasibility of the intervention.	Support for maintaining adherence when using mHealth applications is presented in terms of consumer preferences within specific target segments.
14	Adherence, the occurrence of adverse effects during medication intake, the economic burden of treatment, and the stress experienced by caregivers must be taken into consideration.	Adherence and the occurrence of adverse effects during medication intake are considered in a small proportion of mHealth applications (18.6%).
15	Ensuring adequate patient information about treatment options is essential for improving adherence.	The ability to inform patients about treatment options is very weakly represented in mHealth applications (12.4%).
16	Predictors of sufficient and insufficient adherence should be considered.	Predictors of sufficient adherence in the use of mHealth include advanced age, presence of chronic disease, higher education, disability status, comorbidity, and polypharmacy. Predictors of insufficient adherence include the prescription of multiple medications, complex or inconvenient medication administration regimens, financial constraints, and limited knowledge of treatment consequences and side effects.
17	Factors that facilitate and hinder adherence maintenance should be considered. Regular situational analysis is appropriate.	Factors contributing to adherence when using mHealth include simplicity and ease of use, reliability and safety, low cost, sufficient volume of mobile content, good design, high quality, the ability to interact with the attending physician and pharmaceutical specialist, physiological parameter monitoring, additional reminders about medication purchases and physician visits, among others. Factors hindering the maintenance of adherence when using mHealth: technical difficulties, insufficient security, unreliable information, inadequate regulation

No.	Consolidated provision of adherence [3, 4]	Compliance of mHealth applications with the consolidated provision of adherence
		by professional bodies, low accessibility, insufficiently logical and clear navigation, underdeveloped support systems for medication administration regimens, dosing, monitoring or their absence, and others. Regular situational analysis of these factors is not presented.
18	The attitude of intermediate (indirect) participants towards maintaining adherence, in addition to patients, should be taken into account.	The attitude of medical and pharmaceutical professionals (both current and potential) toward maintaining adherence when using mHealth is considered and presented very limitedly.
19	Special attention must be directed toward elderly patients.	Issues related to maintaining adherence in elderly patients when using mHealth have been addressed within limited scopes, without sufficient elaboration.
20	The healthcare system and medical service providers should develop tools for the accurate assessment of both adherence and the factors influencing it.	Issues concerning the development of tools for precise assessment of adherence during mHealth use and the factors influencing it have been very limitedly addressed in the literature.
21	There is a need for counseling tools for medical and pharmaceutical professionals on adherence issues that are adaptable to diverse socio-economic conditions.	Counseling tools for medical and pharmaceutical professionals on adherence in the context of mHealth use, adaptable to diverse socio-economic conditions, are not available.
22	An interdisciplinary approach is necessary for studying adherence and its maintenance, as well as for preparing the professional community to implement this approach.	Issues concerning the interdisciplinary approach to studying adherence and its maintenance in the context of mHealth, as well as the preparation of the professional community for implementing this approach, were not addressed.

The analysis results demonstrated that the development and enhancement of mobile applications correspond, to varying degrees, with most of the consolidated principles of adherence. This is particularly evident in the treatment of chronic diseases, among elderly individuals, those with higher education, and in cases of disability, comorbidity, and polypharmacy (Nos. 1, 16, and 19, Table 1). Various methods, tools, and scales are employed to assess adherence when using mHealth (No. 4); however, the preferred approach is survey-based through questionnaires (Nos. 8, 10). It should be noted that the development of methods and tools for the

accurate assessment and precise diagnosis of adherence mechanism disruptions during mHealth use remains unresolved to date (Nos. 7, 20). The following issues remain practically unresolved regarding mHealth applications: forecasting and strategic management of adherence (Nos. 5, 6); pharmaceutical consumer segmentation (No. 2); development of counseling tools for medical and pharmaceutical professionals on adherence issues (No. 21) with subsequent involvement of these professionals in the systematic surveying of patients with chronic diseases (No. 11); an interdisciplinary approach to the study of adherence and its maintenance (No. 22). With regard to the leading strategies aimed at maintaining adherence during the use of mHealth, their scope remains insufficiently broad and relevant (No. 12), despite the marked increase in recent years in the application of flexible approaches, artificial intelligence technologies, and machine learning in the development of mobile applications across all sectors of the economy, as reflected in strategic planning. Questions concerning consumer preferences (No. 13) and the factors facilitating and impeding the maintenance of adherence during the use of mobile applications (No. 17) remain contentious. This is related to the specific characteristics of each mHealth application, and efforts to develop new mobile health applications and improve existing ones should be focused accordingly.

Conclusions

An analysis of data on the compliance of modern mobile health applications with consolidated adherence principles has established that the development and enhancement of mHealth largely align with most of these principles. This is particularly evident in the treatment and prevention of chronic diseases, among elderly individuals, and in cases of comorbidity and polypharmacy. Issues related to the development of methods and tools for the accurate evaluation and precise diagnosis of adherence mechanism disorders when using mobile applications remain incompletely resolved. The issues of planning and strategic management of adherence, segmentation of mHealth users, development of counseling tools for medical and pharmaceutical professionals on adherence, and an interdisciplinary approach to studying adherence and its maintenance remain practically unresolved. Questions regarding consumer preferences and factors that facilitate or hinder the maintenance of adherence when using mHealth remain controversial. This is related to the specific characteristics of each individual application, and efforts should be focused on the development and enhancement of mobile health applications within the strategic framework aimed at maintaining adherence.

References

1. *Adherence to pharmacotherapy in patients with chronic non-communicable diseases. Addressing the issue in various clinical scenarios. Methodological guidelines* / Yu. V. Lukina, N. P. Kutishenko, S. Yu. Martsevich et al. // *Preventive Medicine*. — 2020. — No. 23(3-2). — Pp. 42-60. — URL: <https://doi.org/10.17116/profmed20202303242> (date of access: 21.01.2026).
2. *Adherence to long-term therapies: evidence for action*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2003. — 195 p. — ISBN: 92 4 154599 2 (NLM classification: W 85).
3. *Adherence to treatment. Russian National Guidelines*. Moscow, 2022. — 223 p. — ISBN 978-5-91327-746-6.
4. *Adherence-Based Treatment Management. Consensus Document — Interdisciplinary Recommendations* / N. A. Nikolaev, A. I. Martynov, Yu. P. Skirdenko [et al.] // *Consillium Medicum*. — 2020. — No. 22(5). — Pp. 9-18.
5. *Apkhanova, T. V. Adherence to Treatment in Common Chronic Noncommunicable Diseases: Current Challenges for Physicians and the Healthcare System. A Literature Review* / T. V. Apkhanova, L. A. Marchenkova, T. V. Konchugova // *Bulletin of Rehabilitation Medicine*. — 2025. — 24(5). — Pp. 142-157. — URL: <https://doi.org/10.38025/2078-1962-2025-24-5-142-157> (date of access: 21.01.2026).
6. *Acceptance of mHealth by Patients with Cardiovascular Diseases: The Structural Model of Health Applications Use* / D. Zagulova, J. V. Kolobovnikova, N. V. Pozdnyakova, A. T. Mansharipova // *The Russian Archives of Internal Medicine*. — 2024. — No. 14(4). — Pp. 260-275. — URL: <https://doi.org/10.20514/2226-6704-2024-14-4-260-275> (date of access: 21.01.2026).
7. *Mobile medical applications. Analysis of market size, share, and trends; strategic insights; growth forecasts (2025-2032)*. — *Future Market Report: [website]* — URL: <https://www.futuremarketreport.com/ru/industry-report/mobile-medical-applications-market> (accessed: 21.01.2026).
8. *Gusev, A. V. Healthcare in the Smartphone: The Situation in Russia* / A. V. Gusev, A. A. Ivshin, A. V. Vladzimirskyy // *Russian Journal of Telemedicine and E-Health*. — 2021. — No. 7(3). — pp. 21-31. — URL: <https://doi.org/10.29188/2712-9217-2021-7-3-21-31> (date of access: 21.01.2026).
9. *Mobile health applications market*. — *Kings Research: [website]*. — URL: <https://www.kingsresearch.com/ru/report/mhealth-apps-market-2480> (accessed: 21.01.2026).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.26.89.109

UDC 631.879.32:581.192.2:551.582

对乙酰氨基酚废弃物生物降解产物影响下金盏花生物量和产量的生长速率
**GROWTH RATES OF BIOMASS AND YIELD OF CALENDULA
OFFICINALIS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF PARACETAMOL
WASTE BIODEGRADATION PRODUCT**

Gapechkina Elizaveta Dmitrievna

Postgraduate student

Perm State Pharmaceutical Academy

Vikhareva Elena Vladimirovna

Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor

Perm State Pharmaceutical Academy

Selyaninov Alexander Anatolyevich

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor

Perm National Research Polytechnic University

摘要：本研究对比了在2018年、2020年和2022年西乌拉尔地区金盏花（菊科）采收期内，以扑热息痛废料的细菌降解产物作为生物刺激剂，与对照生长刺激剂“锆石”（Zircon）对金盏花增重率和产量的影响。结果表明，与对照制剂“锆石”相比，使用扑热息痛生物降解产物处理的金盏花生物量增长率提高了26%。使用该生物刺激剂处理的产量比对照组高出60%，而使用“锆石”处理的产量则高出30%。本研究还揭示了在西乌拉尔地区，不同生长季节的水热条件对施用该生物刺激剂的金盏花生长速率和产量的影响。研究表明，对乙酰氨基酚生物降解产物比“锆石”更能提高植物对水热环境的抵抗力。

关键词：生物量生长速率，产量，金盏花，对乙酰氨基酚生物降解产物，生长刺激剂“锆石”，水热条件。

Abstract. *The study presents comparative results of the effect of a bacterial degradation product of paracetamol waste, used as a biostimulant, versus the reference growth stimulant “Zircon”, on rates of weight gain and yield of Calendula officinalis L., Asteraceae flowers during harvesting periods in 2018, 2020, and 2022 in the Western Urals. It was found that the biomass growth rate of Calendula officinalis flowers using the paracetamol biodegradation product was 26% higher compared to treatment with the reference preparation “Zircon”. The yield when using the tested*

biostimulant was 60% higher than on control plots, and 30% higher when using “Zircon”. The influence of hydrothermal conditions during different growing seasons on the growth rate and yield of *Calendula officinalis* under the application of the studied biostimulant in the Western Urals has been demonstrated. It has been established that the paracetamol biodegradation product improves plant resistance to environmental hydrothermal conditions more than “Zircon”.

Key words: growth rate of biomass, yield, *Calendula officinalis* L., paracetamol biodegradation product, growth stimulator “Zircon”, hydrothermal conditions.

Introduction. Currently, there is a significant increase in demand for medicinal plant raw materials due to growing interest among producers and consumers in plant-based pharmaceuticals. One of the ways to expand the raw material base of medicinal plants is their cultivation. Therefore, the search for effective plant growth stimulants is relevant. Results of our earlier studies have shown that the paracetamol biodegradation product (PBP) is a potent growth stimulant for plants, particularly for *Calendula officinalis* L. [1]. This product, a polymer of complex chemical composition [2], significantly increases the biomass of medicinal raw material—flowers of *Calendula officinalis*—and enhances the content of the main group of biologically active compounds, flavonoids [1].

As a continuation of these studies, the aim of the present work is to investigate the influence of the paracetamol biodegradation product and the reference growth stimulant “Zircon” on the growth rate of biomass and yield of *Calendula officinalis* L. flowers under varying hydrothermal conditions during the harvesting periods of 2018, 2020, and 2022 in the Western Urals.

Material and methods. The PBP was obtained microbiologically from pharmaceutical paracetamol waste at the Laboratory of Alkanotrophic Microorganisms, Perm Federal Research Center, Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Perm, Russia). Field experiments on the effect of PBP on the growth dynamics of *Calendula officinalis* flower biomass were carried out in 2018, 2020, and 2022 under the conditions described in study [1]. The experiments were conducted in triplicate according to the Guidelines for Conducting Registration Trials of Plant Growth Regulators [3]. The reference preparation used was the plant growth stimulant “Zircon” (LLC “NEST M”), comparable to PBP in terms of application timing, soil application method, and mode of action. Growth stimulants were not applied on control plots (natural watering with water only). *Calendula officinalis* flowers were harvested during the flowering phase from July to October 2018, from June to October 2020, and from June to November 2022, at approximately 14-day intervals.

The raw material was dried using the air-shade method. Flowers were weighed after drying to constant weight to determine biomass increment. The biomass growth rate was calculated using the formula:

Growth rate = [(current value – baseline value) / baseline value] × 100%.

The yield of *Calendula officinalis* flowers was calculated as:

Yield = total mass of harvested raw material (g) / plot area (m²).

Statistical analysis of experimental data (n = 12, P = 0.95) was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Excel 2019 and Statistica 12.6 software, in accordance with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation XV edition [4].

Results. The maximum growth rates of *Calendula officinalis* flower biomass on experimental (PBP and “Zircon”) and control plots were observed on the 14th day of harvesting (figure). The growth rate on PBP-treated plots was 59.8% (2018), 40.4% (2020), and 24.1% (2022) higher compared to control plots. In contrast, growth rates on “Zircon”-treated plots exceeded the control by 9.6% (2018), 18.9% (2020), and 16.9% (2022). Over the three-year period, the average growth rate with PBP was 26% higher than that achieved with the “Zircon” growth stimulant.

Figure. Growth rates of *Calendula officinalis* flower biomass harvested from experimental and control plots in 2018, 2020, and 2022.

The yield of *Calendula officinalis* treated with PBP increased by 55.3% in 2018, by 61.1% in 2020, and by 62.4% in 2022 compared to the control. The yield increase with “Zircon” treatment in 2018, 2020, and 2022 was 24.5%, 23.3%, and 43.3%, respectively (table).

Table. Yield of *Calendula officinalis* raw material in 2018, 2020, and 2022.

Plot	Yield of <i>Calendula officinalis</i> flowers, g/m ²		
	2018	2020	2022
Control	150.0 ± 1.2	153.6 ± 1.4	161.1 ± 0.9
PBP	232.9 ± 2.2	247.5 ± 1.6	261.6 ± 1.8
“Zircon”	186.8 ± 1.5	189.4 ± 2.0	230.8 ± 1.3
Value of the hydrothermal coefficient			
during the vegetative growth phase / flowering phase	1.2 / 1.27	2.2 / 0.99	2.03 / 0.38

Analysis of the data on biomass growth rates and yield across different vegetation periods of *Calendula officinalis* allowed us to explain the observed differences by the influence of weather conditions. Calculation of the hydrothermal coefficient (HTC, an indicator of the relative moisture balance) showed that the 2018 growing season was more favorable compared to 2020 and 2022, as optimal hydrothermal conditions ($1.00 \leq \text{HTC} \leq 1.40$) were established for the plant’s development during May–October 2018 (table). The flowering phase in 2018 was characterized by higher precipitation (HTC 1.27) compared to the flowering phases in 2020 (HTC 0.99) and 2022 (HTC 0.38). Additionally, the 2018 flowering period had lower average temperatures than in 2020 and 2022, which contributed to better soil moisture retention and, consequently, a greater increase in the growth rate of medicinal plant biomass.

The yield of *Calendula officinalis* on control plots varied by 7.1 % across the observation years (150.0-161.1 g/m²), on “Zircon” plots by 21.1 % (186.8-230.8 g/m²), and on PBP plots by 11.6% (232.9-261.6 g/m²). Thus, PBP improved the plant’s stability in response to hydrothermal environmental conditions more effectively than “Zircon”. As seen from the table, a slight increase in yield was observed on both PBP and “Zircon” experimental plots in 2022 compared to 2018 and 2020, which may be attributed to a higher accumulated sum of active temperatures during the flowering phase (1626.9 °C in 2022, 1432.1 °C in 2020, and 1041 °C in 2018).

Conclusion. The growth rate of *Calendula officinalis* flower biomass using the paracetamol biodegradation product is 26% higher compared to treatment with the reference preparation “Zircon”. The yield of raw material achieved with the tested biostimulant is 60% greater than that of the control plots and 30% higher than with “Zircon”.

The influence of hydrothermal conditions during different growing seasons on biomass growth rate and raw material yield of *Calendula officinalis* has been demonstrated for the Western Urals region when using the tested biostimulant. It has been established that the paracetamol biodegradation product enhances plant resilience to environmental hydrothermal conditions more effectively than the reference preparation.

References

1. Vihareva E. V., Mishenina I. I., Gapechkina E. D. et al. *Phyto-stimulating effect of paracetamol biodestruction product on calendula officinalis. Razrabotka i registracija lekarstvennyh sredstv. 2022; 11(4-1): 31-37. (In Russ.). DOI: 10.33380/2305-2066-2022-11-4(1)-31-37.*
2. Korotaev M. Yu., Polyakova E. B., Vihareva E. V. et al. *Chemical structure of the sediment formed during the biotransformation of paracetamol by Rhodococcus ruber IEGM 77 cells Rhodococcus ruber. Biofarmaceuticheskij zhurnal. 2016; 8 (1): 13-19. (In Russ.).*
3. *Rukovodstvo po provedeniyu registracionnyh ispytaniy regulyatorov rosta rastenij, defoliantov i desikantov v sel'skom hozyajstve: pro izvodstvenno-prakt. izdanie. M.: FGBNU «Rosinformagrotekh»; 2016: 216. (In Russ.).*
4. *Gosudarstvennaja farmakopeja RF, XV izdanie, OFS.1.1.0013 «Statisticheskaya obrabotka rezul'tatov fizicheskikh, fiziko-himicheskikh i himicheskikh ispytaniy». June 15, 2025. (In Russ.); <https://pharmacopoeia.regmed.ru/pharmacopoeia/izdanie-15/1/1-1/statisticheskaya-obrabotka-rezultatov-fizicheskikh-fiziko-khimicheskikh-i-khimicheskikh-ispytaniy/>.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.27.72.123

浆果粉在功能性面粉糖果产品生产中的应用
**THE USE OF BERRY POWDERS IN THE PRODUCTION
OF FUNCTIONAL FLOUR CONFECTIONERY PRODUCTS**

Tumanova Alla Evgenyevna

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor, Professor

Drobysheva Maria Andreevna

Master's student

Lyashkova Daria Konstantinovna

Master's student

Russian Biotechnological University (ROSBIOtech)

摘要：新一代功能性食品的开发是食品行业的创新趋势，具有重要的实际意义和社会影响[1]。

面粉类糖果产品的强化是一种有针对性的技术和营养策略，其合理性在于此类产品在人类饮食中的高普及性和广泛消费。

这些产品属于大众消费品，深受包括儿童、青少年和成人在内的各个年龄段和社会群体的喜爱。由于其消费频率高，面粉类糖果被认为是添加维生素、矿物质、膳食纤维和抗氧化剂等生物活性化合物的理想载体。

浆果粉的加入是开发功能性食品的一种很有前景的方法，这主要得益于浆果原料的高营养价值。在保留生物活性成分的同时获得的浆果粉富含抗氧化剂、维生素C、多酚和膳食纤维，能够显著提高最终产品的营养密度。

本研究以使用化学膨松剂制备的松饼为模型对象，以确保成品结构和孔隙率的可重复性。蔓越莓粉 (*Vaccinium oxycoccos* L.) 经干燥研磨后制成，并作为功能性成分用于配方改良。添加蔓越莓粉旨在通过引入天然抗氧化剂（包括花青素和酚酸）、抗坏血酸和膳食纤维来提高产品的生物价值。因此，所开发的产品被认为是一种功能性松饼，它既保留了传统松饼的感官特性，又提升了其生物活性物质的含量。

关键词：面粉类糕点，营养价值，松饼，蔓越莓粉。

Abstract. *The development of next-generation functional foods is an innovative trend in the food industry, possessing significant practical importance and social impact [1].*

Enrichment of flour-based confectionery products represents a targeted technological and nutritional strategy, justified by their high availability and widespread consumption in human diets.

These products belong to the category of mass-consumption goods regularly consumed by various age and social groups, including children, adolescents, and adults. Due to their high consumption frequency, flour-based confectionery items are considered a promising matrix for the incorporation of biologically active compounds such as vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, and antioxidants.

The incorporation of berry powders into flour-based confectionery products is a promising approach in the development of functional foods, driven by the high nutritional value of berry raw materials. Berry powders, obtained while preserving bioactive components, serve as a rich source of antioxidants, vitamin C, polyphenols, and dietary fiber, significantly enhancing the nutrient density of the final product.

*As a model object of study, a muffin prepared using chemical leavening agents was selected, ensuring reproducibility of structure and porosity in the finished product. Cranberry powder (*Vaccinium oxycoccos* L.), obtained by drying and subsequent grinding, was used as a functional ingredient for recipe modification. The addition of cranberry powder aims to increase the biological value of the product by introducing natural antioxidants, including anthocyanins and phenolic acids, as well as ascorbic acid and dietary fiber. Thus, the developed product is regarded as a functional muffin, combining traditional sensory properties with an improved profile of biologically active substances.*

Keywords: *flour-based confectionery products, nutritional value, muffin, cranberry powder.*

The aim of this research was to establish the range of possible applications of cranberry powder in muffin production to enhance the nutritional value of the products and to develop a functional food product.

This aim was accomplished by addressing the following tasks:

- Justification of the selection of cranberry powder as an enriching functional additive;
- study of the effect of cranberry powder on the organoleptic and physico-chemical properties of muffins;
- development of recommendations for the rational dosage range of powder application in muffin production to enhance nutritional value;
- confirmation of the increased nutritional value of muffins through the use of cranberry berry powder.

Muffins prepared with chemical leavening agents were selected for the study, as their production technology is characterized by high reproducibility of structure and porosity due to uniform gas formation during baking. This allows minimizing the influence of technological factors on the final product properties and more accurately assessing the contribution of the functional ingredient — cranberry

powder — to the rheological, physicochemical, and organoleptic characteristics of the finished product.

According to GOST R 52349-2005 “Functional Food Products. Terms and Definitions,” the functional food ingredient must be present in the product in an amount constituting at least 15% of the daily physiological requirement per serving of the product.

Cranberry powder (*Vaccinium oxycoccos* L.) was selected as the enriching component for muffins due to its high biological value and the presence of a broad spectrum of biologically active substances, confirming its potential as a functional ingredient.

Among the vitamins present in cranberry in amounts effective for humans are vitamins P, C, K1, and provitamin A; it also contains five of the most important microelements for humans in effective quantities: iron, copper, manganese, cobalt, and iodine [2].

From a practical perspective, the most significant components in cranberry fruits are sugars, organic acids, pectic substances, and vitamins.

Among the acids in the berries, citric acid predominates; benzoic, chinic, ursolic, chlorogenic, malic, oleanolic, γ -oxy- β -ketobutyric, and α -ketoglutaric acids are also present [3]. Due to the presence of benzoic acid and the dense skin coated with a waxy bloom, fresh berries can be preserved for up to 10 months [4]. Benzoic acid is a natural antiseptic that prevents the growth of microbes, yeasts, and molds, as well as the formation of aflatoxins.

Chlorogenic acids are powerful natural antioxidants. They play a vital role in human metabolism. Recent scientific studies have demonstrated that they possess antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antibacterial properties and help reduce blood pressure [5].

The second most abundant group after acids comprises triterpene compounds in cranberries, mainly represented by ursolic and oleanolic acids in their free forms. Their complex esters have also been identified, but only in trace amounts (less than 0.1%).

Ursolic and oleanolic acids exhibit antitumor and antiviral effects; moreover, ursolic acid promotes an increase in brown adipose tissue cells and a decrease in white adipose tissue cells in the body, thereby enhancing cold resistance and preventing obesity [6].

The third highest content is attributed to the group of phenolic compounds, which are typically linked to the potent antioxidant properties of berries. The phenolic fraction of cranberry comprises more than 80 compounds, including tannins, flavonoids, and phenolic acids. The total flavonoid content in cranberries ranges from 844 to 1037 mg % of fresh weight.

Within the flavonoid complex of cranberry berries, catechins and flavonols predominate, with only about one-fifth constituted by anthocyanin pigments,

represented by anthocyanins themselves and their leucoforms, with a total content ranging from 130 to 135 mg % of fresh weight.

It has been established that the total content of bioflavonoids in dried cranberries exceeds the daily requirement by an average of 109.3 times. Among flavonoids, the largest proportion is represented by anthocyanins (3680 mg/100 g); flavonols (2386 mg/100 g); catechins (1940 mg/100 g), and leucoanthocyanins (613 mg/100 g).

When evaluating nutritional value, special attention should be paid to tannins. They constitute 1.8%.

According to many Russian scientists, the successful combination of reduced and oxidized forms of flavonoids enhances the value of cranberry as an effective capillary-strengthening, anti-inflammatory, and anti-atherosclerotic agent [7].

The vitamin fraction of cranberries includes B-group vitamins (B1, B2, B5, B6), PP, K1 (phyloquinone), and a high content of vitamin C (which may vary depending on the cranberry cultivar).

The content of vitamins B1 and B2 is relatively low, and in dried berries it averages: B1-0.29 mg/100 g; B2-0.22 mg/100 g. The content of vitamin K is relatively high, amounting to 4.83 mg/100 g.

The β -carotene content in dried bog cranberry berries is 3.87 mg/100 g.

Dried cranberry berries have a high fiber content of 18.5 g/100 g, as well as pectin substances at 4.8 g/100 g. Pectins can form insoluble complex compounds (chelates) with many metals such as calcium, strontium, cobalt, lead, and others, which are practically indigestible and are excreted from the body. This also explains the antiradical effect of cranberry juice and other cranberry processing products.

The data presented on the chemical composition of cranberry powder confirm the high functional potential of this plant ingredient, which underlies its ability to positively influence human health, as well as the appropriateness of its use as an enriching component in the development of functional food products.

The objects of the study for compliance with regulatory documentation requirements were: premium wheat flour (GOST 26574-2017); white sugar (GOST 12576-2014); butter (GOST 32261-2013); edible chicken eggs (GOST 31654-2012); table salt (GOST R 51574-2018), ammonium carbonate (GOST 9325-79); cranberry powder (TU 10.39.25-003-50017951-2009); Taste, aroma, structure, color, and appearance in the fracture of finished products (GOST 15052-2014). The nutritional and energy value of the products was determined by calculation.

Cranberry powder was a finely dispersed product of dark red color with a pleasant berry aroma, slight bitterness in taste, and no off-flavors. The dry matter content (DM) of the powder was 95%.

The muffin recipe presented in Table 1 was selected as the base.

Table 1. Unified Muffin Recipe

Name of Raw Material	Mass Fraction of Dry Matter, %	Raw Material Consumption per 100 pcs of Finished Products, g	
		As Is	On Dry Matter Basis
Wheat Flour, Premium Grade	85,50	2339,0	1999,8
White Sugar	99,85	1755,0	1752,4
Butter	84,00	1754,0	1473,4
Melange	27,00	1404,0	379,1
Salt	96,50	7,1	6,9
Raisins	80,00	1754,0	1403,2
Powdered Refined Sugar	99,85	82,0	81,9
Essence	0,00	7,1	0,0
Ammonium Carbonate	0,00	7,1	0,0
Total	-	9109,3	7096,7
Yield		7500,0	6600,0

Note — Moisture content $12.0 \pm 2.0\%$.

The technological process of muffin production according to the basic recipe consisted of the following stages: preparation of raw materials, dough mixing, shaping, baking at 160-200 °C for 20-25 minutes depending on the mass of the dough portions, cooling, and storage [8].

The production of muffins with added cranberry powder was carried out similarly; the powder was incorporated together with the flour at the dough mixing stage. Baked products were stored at room temperature. Quality indicators of the products were assessed 24 hours after baking. The influence of various dosages of cranberry powder on product quality was evaluated. The proportion of powder ranged from 5% to 20% of the flour mass in the recipe on a dry basis, with increments of 5%.

Organoleptic characteristics of muffin samples were assessed 24 hours after preparation. All products exhibited a pronounced sweet taste and aroma, with a soft structure that did not crumble when broken; the crumb color was uniform throughout the product volume.

Muffins with a cranberry powder dosage of 10-15% exhibited a more crumbly and uniform consistency, as the dietary fibers contained in the powder stabilize the emulsion, making it more homogeneous and enriched with air bubbles distributed more evenly.

The sensation of viscosity and plasticity when chewing muffins with a 20% cranberry powder dosage is attributable to the ability of dietary fibers to bind water, thereby increasing the dough's viscosity.

Based on a comprehensive evaluation of organoleptic indicators — including color, taste, aroma, and texture — the muffin containing 15% cranberry powder by flour weight was selected as the optimal sample for further investigation. This concentration ensured a balanced combination of functional properties and acceptable sensory characteristics, without causing noticeable deviations in crumb structure or unacceptable changes in taste acidity. For the selected sample, the nutritional value and energy value were calculated considering the contribution of biologically active components introduced by cranberry powder.

The comparative nutritional value of the control sample and the experimental sample (with a 15% cranberry powder dosage) is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Nutritional value of muffins

Indicators	Muffin 'Stolichny' according to the traditional recipe (Control sample)	Muffin with added cranberry powder 15%	Change in parameter relative to the control sample, %
Proteins, g	5,0	5,16	3,2 ↑
Fats, g	14,6	13,72	6 ↓
Carbohydrates, g	48,4	48,4	-
Dietary fiber, g	1,4	2,38	70 ↑
Sodium, mg	54,02	55,28	2,3 ↑
Potassium, mg	184,87	193,35	4,6 ↑
Calcium, mg	28,18	30,32	7,6 ↑
Magnesium, mg	11,67	15,63	33,9 ↑
Phosphorus, mg	70,2	71,8	2,3 ↑
Iron, mg	0,896	1,072	19,6 ↑
Vitamin A, µg	115,4	109,58	5,0 ↓
Vitamin B 1, mg	0,053	0,053	-
Vitamin B 2, mg	0,126	0,124	1,6 ↓
Vitamin PP, mg	1,44	1,44	-
Vitamin D, µg	0,54	0,52	3,7 ↓
β-carotene, µg	0,061	0,156	155 ↑
Vitamin K, µg	1,9	1,9	-
Energy value, kcal	342,1	334,69	2,2 ↓

The use of cranberry powder results in developed products with enhanced nutritional value and functional properties. The dietary fiber content in muffins with 15% cranberry powder increases by 70% compared to the control, β-carotene by 150%, and magnesium by 34%.

A comparative analysis of the chemical composition and energy value of the control sample (the “Stolichny” muffin prepared by the traditional recipe) and the enriched sample (with 15% cranberry powder added) supports a well-founded conclusion that the muffin with cranberry powder meets the criteria of a functional food product and possesses enhanced biological value.

References

1. Sokolova, N. N. Functional Food Products: A Textbook for Secondary Vocational Education / N. N. Sokolova, V. V. Burmatnov. — Saint Petersburg: Lan, 2025. — 44 p.
2. Berry Crops / V. V. Dankov, M. M. Skripnichenko, S. F. Loginova [et al.]. — 2nd ed., revised. — Saint Petersburg: Lan, 2022. — 188 p.
3. Polysaccharide Medicinal Phytobiotics in Functional Food Biostimulators of Physiological Processes: Monograph / O. A. Kovaleva, O. S. Kireeva, N. N. Popovicheva, O. A. Gulyaeva. — Orel: OrelGAU, 2021. — 164 p.
4. Food and Medicinal Properties of Cultivated Plants: Textbook / V. N. Naumkin, N. V. Kotsareva, L. A. Manokhina, A. N. Kryukov. — Saint Petersburg: Lan, 2021. — 400 p.
5. Sycheva, O. V. Food Security of the Country — A Path to Healthy Nutrition: Monograph / O. V. Sycheva. — Stavropol: StGAU, 2024. — 120 p.
6. Food Technologies and Biotechnology. XVI All-Russian Conference of Young Scientists, Postgraduates, and Students with International Participation, dedicated to the 150th Anniversary of the Periodic Table of Chemical Elements (April 16-19, 2019): Conference Materials in 3 Parts / Compiled by L. Yu. Koshkina; Edited by A. S. Sirotkin. Kazan: KNITU, 2019 — Part 1-2019. — 540 p.
7. Improvement of Organization and the Formation of a Healthy Nutrition Culture in Educational Institutions: Monograph / N. N. Ashirova, E. S. Bychkova, A. A. Dril [et al.]; Under the General Editorship of L. N. Rozhdestvenskaya. — Novosibirsk: NSTU, 2016. — 266 p.
8. Demchenko, N. I. Tasks in the Profession of ‘Tester’: Textbook / N. I. Demchenko. — Bryansk: Bryansk State Agrarian University, 2018. — 154 p.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.28.38.119

在禽肉生产中使用新型饲料添加剂的合理性
**JUSTIFICATION FOR THE USE OF A NEW FEED ADDITIVE
IN POULTRY MEAT PRODUCTION**

Mizhevikina Yulia Alekseevna*Senior Laboratory Assistant**South Ural State Agrarian University***Mizhevikina Anna Sergeevna***Candidate of Veterinary Sciences, Associate Professor**South Ural State Agrarian University*

摘要：随着家禽肉生产集约化程度的提高，改善饲料基础—决定家禽生产力和健康的关键因素之一—变得尤为重要。传统日粮虽然营养均衡，但并非总能充分发挥现代杂交品种的遗传潜力。近年来，新型饲料添加剂的研发和应用日益广泛。Citriméen 是一种基于螯合锌的新型饲料添加剂，目前尚不清楚其在工业化家禽养殖中的应用。本文介绍了 Citriméen 对肉鸡体质的综合影响的研究数据。

关键词：Citriméen, 肉鸡, 生产力, 血液, 肉, 化学成分

Abstract. *Against the background of intensification of poultry meat production, improving the feed base — one of the key factors determining the productivity and health of poultry — is becoming particularly relevant. Traditional diets, despite being balanced, do not always fully realize the genetic potential of modern crosses and breeds. In this regard, new feed additives have been actively developed and introduced in recent years. Citriméen is a new feed additive based on the chelated form of zinc, about which nothing is known regarding its application in industrial poultry farming. The article presents research data on the complex effect of Citriméen on the body of broiler chickens.*

Keywords: *Citriméen, broiler chickens, productivity, blood, meat, chemical composition*

Introduction

Poultry meat production is one of the most demanded areas of the agro-industrial complex in Russia.

Consumer demand for poultry meat continues to grow every year, driven by several factors, including the health benefits of chicken meat, its versatility in use,

and relatively low cost, which guarantees purchasing power. To meet the constantly growing demand with a worthy offer, producers are forced to optimize production, expand the range, and use means that accelerate the production cycle (T. Zimina, 2024)

The feed additive Citrimeen, the study of which is presented in this work, is a development of the Technology Implementation Center (Irkutsk). A white powder without taste or smell, it represents a chelated form of zinc, designed to balance the diet of productive animals and poultry.

The manufacturer of Citrimeen claims that introducing the additive at a rate of 60 g/t of feed can stimulate the growth of muscle mass in broiler chickens and also reduce mortality rates in the flock. Previous studies of Citrimeen have demonstrated its positive impact in industrial fish farming. Detailed data on the effect of Citrimeen on farm animals are extremely scarce.

Objective of the research: to substantiate the use of the Citrimeen feed additive in meat poultry farming.

Materials and Methods of Research

To assess the degree of influence of the Citrimeen feed additive on the poultry body, an experiment was conducted under industrial production conditions. 4,000 broiler chickens of the Ross 308 cross were selected and divided into 4 groups of 1,000 heads each. Group 1 was considered the control group and received the main diet of the poultry farm; group 2 received the main diet and Citrimin 30 g/t of feed, group 3 received the main diet and Citrimin 60 g/t of feed, group 4 received the main diet and Citrimin 90 g/t of feed. The experiment lasted 40 days.

Monitoring of live weight changes was carried out by weighing chickens from each group on the third day, the 10th day, the 20th day, and before slaughter.

At the end of the experiment, 40 heads of poultry were randomly selected (10 heads from each group). Slaughter was carried out after a 6-hour fasting period. The following were studied: meat productivity, growth of internal organs, micro-morphometric changes in the intestines, morpho-biochemical blood parameters, changes in the microelement composition of meat and blood serum, meat quality, and its chemical composition.

Results of the research

As part of an extensive study, the effect of various doses of Citrimeen on the growth and development of internal organs of broiler chickens was evaluated. It was found that the liver increased in mass the most in Group 2 (Citrimeen 30 g/t of feed) — by 26.4%, the heart was larger in Group 3 (Citrimeen 60 g/t of feed) — by 34%, the gizzard had a significant increase in Group 4 (Citrimeen 90 g/t of feed) — 18% more than in the control group. The intestinal mass increased in Group 2, where Citrimeen was introduced into the diet at a dose of 30 g/t of feed — by 12% relative to the control, in Groups 3 and 4, the intestinal mass tended to decrease slightly — by less than 5%. Our findings are consistent with the data

of V. Mozhiarasi, R. Karunakaran et al. (2022). In their experiment, they used zinc oxide nanoparticles in feeding broiler chickens, as a result of which it was found that zinc stimulated an increase in liver mass.

Micromorphometric studies of the intestines of broiler chickens allowed us to draw broader conclusions about the effect of the feed additive Citrimeen on internal organs. It was found that the number of villi in the small and large intestines decreased relative to the control by 1-3 units per 1 mm² of the section. The most important aspect of this study is the fact that in the experimental groups, the length of the villi increased by 118-265 %, and the width by 1-22 % relative to the indicators of the control group. Scientists from Wageningen University (Netherlands) have been studying the effect of various feed additives on the body of broiler chickens for quite a long time. Employees of this university — S. Ji, X. Qi et al. (2019) — claim that a decrease in the number of villi, while simultaneously increasing their size, reflects an adaptive response to changes in diet or environmental factors affecting intestinal health. It should be noted that the introduction of feed additives based on zinc stimulates an increase in the length of villi in various parts of the intestines of broiler chickens, which is mentioned in the works of M. I. Khan, N. Chand et al. (2024) and Dogra, S., Devi, J. et al. (2023).

The extensive blood analysis testifies to the ongoing processes in the body of broiler chickens. The data from the obtained clinical blood analysis suggest that the introduction of the Citrimeen feed additive in different doses does not have a negative impact on hematopoiesis processes in the body. Changes in cellular forms were observed in the tested groups within the established norms for healthy birds. Similar phenomena are mentioned in the article by A. Ciszewski, Ł. et al. (2023). The authors claim that the introduction of zinc chelate in one group and zinc glycine in another has a one-sided effect on the number of lymphocytes: their number either does not change or decreases slightly.

Biochemical blood analysis indicates an increase in α -globulins by an average of 23.3 % and γ -globulins by an average of 3.1 % in all experimental groups compared to the control, which indicates an acceleration of protein metabolism. The creatinine level changed slightly, the urea content in the tested groups was lower than in the control. AST enzyme activity increased within 4-25 % compared to the control group indicator. ALT activity decreased by 26-50 % relative to the control. Our research findings are consistent with the scientific data of L. Long, X. Zhao et al. (2022), the authors note an acceleration of protein metabolism against the background of zinc lactate application: total protein and albumin count increased by 13 %, alkaline phosphatase level by 20 % relative to the control. In turn, data on the dynamics of AST and ALT are reflected in the scientific article by M. H. Hatab, A. M. Badran et al. (2024), who studied the effect of zinc nanoparticles on blood indicators of

broiler chickens. During their research, it was found that regular intake of zinc into the body can affect AST growth. Also, the feed additive Citrimin stimulated a decrease in blood glucose levels, which is consistent with the data of E. V. Sheida et al. (2020), who claim that additional introduction of zinc into the diet of white rats contributed to a decrease in blood glucose levels.

Mineral metabolism in the body of broiler chickens was evaluated by the amount of chemical elements in the blood and meat. It was found that the introduction of Citrimin in various dosages does not provoke zinc accumulation in the blood and meat.

An important indicator is calcium-phosphorus metabolism. The calcium level in the experimental groups tended to increase within 1.2-12% relative to the control. The phosphorus content in Group 2 did not change, in Group 3 it increased by 13.7%, in Group 4 it decreased by 16% relative to the control. R. I. Kokaev and V. B. Brin (2021) note in their article that calcium-phosphorus metabolism intensifies when using zinc-based supplements, indicating a tendency to increase calcium and phosphorus within 10-15%.

Significant changes were observed in the mineral composition of broiler chicken blood when Citrimin was introduced at a dose of 60 g/t of feed. The content of heavy metals decreased by up to 50%. In foreign sources, there are also mentions of the influence of zinc-based feed additives on the mineral composition of blood. For example, in the work of V. S. Sakara, A. Yu. Melnik et al. (2019), it is noted that significant zinc accumulation in the blood does not occur; its concentration increases by an average of 4.3% compared to birds receiving the basic diet without additional zinc enrichment.

When studying white and red meat, it was found that when Citrimin was introduced in doses of 60-90 g/t of feed, the content of certain chemical elements increased, such as cobalt, zinc, lead, and cadmium. The obtained values of these indicators do not violate the established norms for heavy metal content in food products, which are reflected in TR CU 021 «On Food Product Safety». E. A. Sizova, S. A. Miroshnikov et al. (2018) provide data on the influence of ultrafine zinc forms in the broiler diet on heavy metal content in meat, also noting an increase in lead and cadmium within established norms.

Meat productivity studies showed that the highest live weight gain was observed when Citrimin was introduced at a dose of 90 g/t of feed, and this gain was mainly due to an increase in the amount of inedible parts of the carcass: head, feet, and feather mass. In group 2 (30 g/ton of feed), the absolute average daily increase increased by 7.5% relative to the control. Administration of Citrimin at a dose of 60 g/t of feed (group 3) stimulated an increase in the relative average daily increase by 6.5% compared with the control. The largest absolute average daily increase was recorded in group 4 (90 g/ton of feed) — 83 g, which is 9% more than the control group. The highest slaughter yield was in Group 3, where the feed additive was introduced at a concentration

of 60 g/t of feed — 74.5%. In all groups where Citrimine was introduced into the diet, the weight of white and red meat increased in relation to the control group. The yield of white and red meat relative to the carcass was calculated. These indicators represent the ratio of the mass of white/red meat to the gutted carcass. The highest value of these indicators was recorded in group 3, which is justified by a 23% increase in white and red meat and 17%, respectively, in comparison with the reference value.

Veterinary and sanitary assessment of broiler chicken meat grown with the use of the Citrimine feed additive allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of meat quality.

According to the results of organoleptic evaluation, no violations of GOST 51944-2002 requirements were identified.

Data obtained from physicochemical studies indicate that the selected meat samples were fresh and came from healthy birds.

Analysis of data on the moisture-binding capacity of meat samples suggests that the introduction of the Citrimine feed additive at a dose of 30-60 g/t of feed stimulates meat to accumulate and retain moisture in its structure. This process is most pronounced in white meat — the moisture-binding capacity increases by 11-16% compared to the control group indicator when the feed additive is introduced at a dose of 30-60 g/t of feed. P. Sałek, W. Przybylski et al. (2020) confirm that zinc in organic form has a positive effect on the moisture-binding capacity of white and red meat.

Under the influence of the Citrimine feed additive, changes occurred in the chemical composition of broiler chicken meat. In all experimental groups, the protein content decreased slightly by less than 5% compared to the control. The largest increase in fat content was observed in Group 3 — by 17% compared to the control group. The dry matter content increased most significantly in Group 4 — by 6% compared to the control.

Taste analysis, the most ancient method of assessing food quality, showed that tasters awarded all meat samples high scores. These data suggest that broiler chicken meat grown with the use of the Citrimine feed additive can be considered excellent quality meat.

The scientifically proven information about the role of zinc in the body of chickens, and the data we obtained during experiments, suggest that regular intake of zinc into the body stimulates the hormonal system (production of testosterone, insulin, and insulin-like growth factor increases), the enzymatic system (zinc is a coenzyme for many enzymes), and zinc is also involved in regulating metabolism amino acids. Probably, due to these mechanisms, the feed additive Citrimine promotes more efficient use of nutrients, accelerates the processes of muscle tissue growth and the overall development of the body of broilers, which manifests itself in a more intensive weight gain.

Based on the research results, the following conclusions can be formulated:

1. Citrimeen had a stimulating effect on hematopoiesis in test broiler chickens: red blood cell count and hemoglobin levels increased by 10-17% compared to the control group.

2. The use of the Citrimeen feed additive contributed to intensified metabolic processes in broiler chickens, as evidenced by increased total protein and albumin concentrations by 13.3-34%, stimulated AST activity by 4-25%, decreased ALT activity by 26-50%, and a significant increase in alkaline phosphatase by an average of 30% compared to the control group.

3. The feed additive actively influenced the intensity of live weight gain and internal organ growth in broiler chickens, which is confirmed by an average increase in daily weight gain by 7.5%, slaughter yield by 14%, heart and gizzard size by 7-22% compared to the control group.

4. The mineral composition of blood under the influence of the feed additive at a dose of 30 g/t of feed changed slightly; at a dose of 60 g/t of feed, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, and zinc content increased by 3-8%; at a dose of 90 g/t of feed, chemical element content decreased in the range of 5-50% compared to the control. The mineral composition of meat changed most significantly when the feed additive was introduced at 60 g/t of feed: copper, cobalt, lead, nickel, manganese, cadmium, and zinc increased in the range of 5 to 40% compared to the control, which does not exceed established norms for healthy birds.

5. Veterinary and sanitary examination of broiler chicken carcasses raised with Citrimeen in the diet demonstrated high meat quality and broth quality; meat water-binding capacity increased by an average of 6.5% compared to the control. At a dose of 30 g/t of feed, protein content decreased by an average of 5%; a dose of 60 g/t stimulated fat content increase by 11-17%; the same indicator at a dose of 90 g/t of feed tended to decrease by 1-27% compared to the control.

References

1. *A deficient or an excess of dietary threonine level affects intestinal mucosal integrity and barrier function in broiler chickens* / S. Ji, X. Qi, S. Ma, X. Liu, S. Liu [et al.]. — Text: direct // *Physiol Anim Nutr (Berl)*. — 2019. — 103(6). — P. 1792-1799.

2. *Changes in the chemical composition of broiler meat when chelated compounds are added to the diet* / T. Fotina, A. Berezovsky, R. Petrov [et al.]. — Text: direct // *Ukrainian journal of veterinary and agricultural sciences*. — 2022. — No. 1. — P. 42-45.

3. Dogra, S. *Effect of zinc oxide nanoparticles supplementation on the histoarchitecture of small intestine of broilers* / S. Dogra, J. Devi, K. Sarma. — Text: direct // *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences*. — 2023. — No. 12 (93). — P. 77-82.
4. *Effect of combined in ovo administration of zinc glycine chelate (Zn-Gly) and a multistrain probiotic on the modulation of cellular and humoral immune responses in broiler chickens* / A. Ciszewski, L. Jarosz, A. Marek [et al.]. — Text: electronic // *Poultry science*. — 2023. — Vol. 102 (9). — P. 102823. — URL: (date of request: 10.02.2025).
5. *Effect of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles as Feed Additive on Blood Indices, Physiological, Immunological Responses, and Histological Changes in Broiler Chicks* / M. H. Hatab, A.M.M. Badran, M. A. Elaroussi [et al.]. — Text: direct // *Biological trace element research*. — 2024. — Vol. 202 (5). — P. 2279-2293.
6. *Effects of different levels of zinc-glycine and zinc hydroxide on the performance, carcass quality, immunity and duodenum morphometric of the broiler chickens* / S. Nessabian, A. Zarei, M. Chamani, A. A. Sadeghi, A. Seidavi. — Text: direct // *Italian Journal of Animal Science*. — 2022. — No. 20(1). — P. 1791-1800.
7. *Effects of Zinc Lactate Supplementation on Growth Performance, Intestinal Morphology, Serum Parameters, and Hepatic Metallothionein of Chinese Yellow-Feathered Broilers* / L. Long, X. Zhao, H. Li, X. Yan, H. Zhang. — Text: direct // *Biol Trace Elem Res*. — 2022. — No. 200. — P. 1835-1843.
8. *Effects of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles on Growth, Carcass Characteristics and Intestinal Tight Junction Protein Gene Expression in 35-day old Broiler Chickens* / V. Mozhiarasi, R. Karunakaran, L. Radhakrishnan [et al.]. — Text: direct // PREPRINT. — 2022. — URL:
9. *Effects of zinc supplementation from organic and inorganic sources on growth, blood biochemical indices, and intestinal microarchitecture in broilers* / M. I. Khan, N. Chand, S. Naz [et al.]. — Text: electronic // *The veterinary quarterly*. — 2024. — Vol. 44 (1). — P. 1-7. — URL: (date of request: 10.02.2025).
10. *Keller, S. Mintrex chelated microminerals in turkey feeding* / S. Keller, R. Timoshenko. — Text: direct // *Livestock Farming of Russia*. — 2016. — No. 4. — P. 58-59.
11. *Kokaev, R. I. Effects of physiological zinc dosage on kidney functions and calcium metabolism under lead intoxication conditions* / R. I. Kokaev, V. B. Brin. — Text: direct // *Modern Problems of Science and Education*. — 2021. — No. 2. — P. 136.

12. Sakara, V. S. *Protein and mineral metabolism in broiler chickens using zinc and manganese chelates* / V. S. Sakara, A. Yu. Melnik, F. S. Marchenkov. — Text: direct // *Scientific Herald of Veterinary Medicine*. — 2019. — No. 1 (147). — P. 85-94.
13. Sheida, E. V. *Changes in morphological and biochemical blood parameters in rats with additional zinc asparaginate in diet* / E. V. Sheida, V. V. Grechkina, E. A. Rusakova. — Text: direct // *Livestock Farming and Feed Production*. — 2020. — Vol. 103, No. 2. — P. 100-113.
14. Sizova, E. A. *Comparative testing of ultrafine alloy, salts and organic forms of Cu and Zn as microelement sources in broiler chicken feeding* / E. A. Sizova, S. A. Miroshnikov, S. V. Lebedev, Yu. I. Levakhin, I. A. Babicheva. — Text: direct // *Agricultural Biology*. — 2018. — No. 2. — P. 393-403.
15. Soares, B. A. *Use of Additives and Evaluation of the Quality of Broiler Meat* / B. A. Soares, O. M. Silva. — Text: direct // *Broiler Industry*. — 2022. — No. 1. — P. 166-171.
16. *The effects on the quality of poultry meat of supplementing feed with zinc-methionine complex* / P. Salek, W. Przybylski, D. Jaworska [et al.]. — Text: direct // *Acta scientiarum polonorum. Technologia alimentaria*. — 2020. — Vol. 19 (1). — P. 73-82.
17. *Use of zinc sulfate for the development of zinc-fortified meat products from broiler meat* / A. Sultana, N. R. Sarker, R. Habib, Md. S. Alam, D. C. Paul [et al.]. — Text: direct // *Journal of advanced veterinary and animal research*. — 2024. — No. 4. — P. 1130-1138.
18. *Velichko, O. A. Influence of complex organic mineral supplement on broiler performance* / O. A. Velichko, M. A. Grigorieva, G. A. Yarmotz, A. Ya. Pavlova. — Text: direct // *Izvestiya OSAU*. — 2022. — No. 4 (96). — P. 314-319.
19. *Zimina, T. "Poultry Farming of Russia 2024: Expert Dialogue"* / T. Zimina. — Text: direct // *Livestock Farming of Russia*. — 2024. — No. 4. — P. 10-12.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.28.87.154

西伯利亚冷杉提取物作为食品强化功能性成分
**SIBERIAN FIR EXTRACT AS A FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENT
FOR FOOD FORTIFICATION**

Tumanova Alla Evgenyevna*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor***Maryasova Alisa Sergeevna***Master's student***Popov Pavel Alexandrovich***Master's student**Russian Biotechnological University (Rosbiotech), Moscow, Russia*

摘要：本文探讨了二氧化碳萃取技术作为一种先进的从食品工业植物原料中提取生物活性物质的方法。重点关注西伯利亚冷杉 (*Abies sibirica*) 的二氧化碳萃取物：阐述了该萃取方法的原理，以及其相对于传统萃取方法的优势和所得产品的理化特性。基于多家生产商和研究中心的数据，对萃取物的化学成分进行了详细分析：列出了关键化合物及其功能活性，以及萃取物极性组分和非极性组分化学成分的差异。本文还介绍了评估该萃取物生物活性特性的研究结果。此外，本文还阐述了冷杉二氧化碳萃取物在功能性食品中的应用前景，以及当前的市场状况和开发含有该成分的新型食品的机会。

关键词：西伯利亚冷杉二氧化碳萃取物，生物活性特性，功能性原料。

Abstract. *This article examines CO₂ extraction technology as an advanced method for extracting biologically active substances from plant raw materials in the food industry. The main focus is on the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir (*Abies sibirica*): the principles of the extraction method are described, along with its advantages over traditional extraction methods and the physicochemical characteristics of the obtained product. A detailed analysis of the chemical composition of the extract is provided based on data from several manufacturers and research centers: key compounds and their functional activities are listed, along with differences in the chemical composition of the polar and non-polar fractions of the extract. The results of studies evaluating the bioactive properties of the extract under consideration are presented. The prospects for the use of the CO₂ extract of fir in functional food products are demonstrated, along with the current market status and opportunities for developing new food products containing the ingredient under consideration.*

Keywords: *CO₂ extract of Siberian fir, bioactive properties, functional raw material.*

The food industry is among the leading sectors in the adoption and successful application of the extraction method, in which liquefied carbon dioxide serves as the extractant. Unlike traditional methods, CO₂ extraction does not require volatile organic solvents; does not involve high temperatures or complex technical equipment; does not involve additional stages of extractant removal. This extraction method is based on the property of a gas to transition into a liquid state or fluid phase under the influence of pressure and temperature, possessing the permeability of a gas and solvent properties inherent to a liquid [7].

CO₂ extraction is one of the most promising technologies for obtaining components from plant raw materials, as it provides the purest and most efficient method for extracting natural flavor-aromatic compounds, pigments, and biologically active substances in their native state, that is, as close as possible to the properties of the raw material.

In addition to the tasks of improving the quality and safety of food products, a strategically important direction in the development of the food industry is the utilization of new types of raw materials. This is due to two key reasons, the first of which is the reduction of the vulnerability of the food system; the second is that the use of new types of raw materials contributes to the expansion of the product range and enables the creation of specialized nutrition products and functional products with enhanced nutritional value and bioavailability of nutrients.

Among the products combining both aspects analyzed above is the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir, whose properties, chemical composition, and potential applications are the subject of this article.

The raw materials for obtaining the extract under consideration are the needles, green cones, and young shoots (by-products of timber harvesting [29]) of Siberian fir (Latin: *Abies sibirica*), which naturally grows in the forests of Eastern and Western Siberia and occurs in Europe and western China [6].

Fir needles possess a unique property — during CO₂ extraction, two fractions are formed: lipid (non-polar)—a viscous liquid ranging from dark green to reddish-brown in color with a pronounced coniferous (sometimes camphoraceous) aroma, well soluble in non-polar solvents and poorly soluble in polar solvents; aqueous (polar)—a fluid liquid ranging from dark reddish to burgundy in color with a pronounced sweet coniferous aroma, well soluble in polar solvents and poorly soluble in non-polar solvents.

In addition to the CO₂ extract, essential oil is also obtained from fir needles by water-steam distillation. Studies using microcalorimetry (on the model reaction of cumene oxidation) [32] demonstrated that the antioxidant activity of the CO₂

extract of fir is twice as high as that of the essential oil. This is due to the fact that the CO₂ extract contains compounds absent in the essential oil, such as carotenoids, chlorophyll, lycopene, xanthophyll, zeaxanthin, and phytofluonol.

Figure 1 — Lipid and aqueous fractions of the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir

This confirms the advantages of the CO₂ extraction method for isolating biologically active substances and the potential use of carbon dioxide extracts as functional ingredients in food products.

The main compounds of the lipid fraction of the Siberian fir CO₂ extract, according to open data from one of the largest CO₂ extract producers in Russia, Bioceutics [31], are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Main compounds of the lipid fraction of Siberian fir CO₂ extract

Component	Functional activity
Bornyl acetate	Anti-inflammatory effect, reduction of nervous system excitability [13], antitumor activity in vitro [21].
Borneol	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-apoptotic, and anticoagulant activities; improvement of energy metabolism; promotes the penetration of substances into target organs [11].
Camphene	Possesses bactericidal properties [4], analgesic effects [20], reduces oxidative stress, and influences lipid metabolism [3].
α -pinene	Antioxidant [14], antibacterial activity [1], anti-inflammatory effect [16], antitumor effect [8].
β -carotene	Antioxidant activity, provitamin A [25].

Tocopherols	Used in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular, neurodegenerative, and oncological diseases, atherosclerosis, hyperlipidemia, osteoporosis; antioxidant [30].
Palmitic acid	It is a component of cell membranes, serves as a precursor for the synthesis of unsaturated fatty acids, and demonstrates antitumor activity [5].
Chamazulene	Exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties [15].
α - and β -linolenic acids	An unsaturated essential fatty acid of the omega-3 fatty acid class. Possesses membrane-protective and angioprotective effects. Immunomodulator, influences metabolism [22].
Linoleic acid.	Belongs to essential fatty acids, serves as a precursor to arachidonic acid, and is a component of the phospholipids of cell membranes [26].

The main compounds of the aqueous fraction of the CO₂ extract of fir, according to data from the company «SOLAGIFT» [19] and protocol test No. 15693 dated 10.11.21 from the Regional Testing Center «Pharmatest» FGBU VO PGFA MINZDRAVA Russia [23], are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 — Major compounds of the aqueous fraction of the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir

Component	Functional activity
Chlorophyll	Antioxidant, antimutagenic, antigenotoxic, anticancer, and lipid metabolism-modulating properties [12].
Lycopene	Antioxidant potential and protection against cardiovascular diseases [9].
Phytophluenol	Acts as an ultraviolet absorber, antioxidant, and possesses anti-inflammatory properties [2].
Ascorbic acid	Antioxidant involved in collagen synthesis; restores tocopherol [17].
Fe	Constituent of hemoglobin and myoglobin; serves as a coenzyme for cytochromes, catalase, and peroxidase. Facilitates oxygen transport; participates in redox reactions and energy metabolism [28].
Zn	Functions as a coenzyme; involved in DNA synthesis, tissue regeneration, and immune response [28].
Mg	Regulates the function of the nervous system and heart, participates in protein synthesis, and is necessary for maintaining calcium, potassium, and sodium homeostasis [27].

Component	Functional activity
Mn	Participates in the formation of bones and connective tissue. Essential for the functioning of the nervous system and antioxidant protection. Coenzyme involved in the synthesis of cholesterol and nucleotides [28].
Cu	Participates in iron metabolism and collagen synthesis, supports the nervous system and immunity, and acts as an indirect antioxidant [28].
3-Acetoxy-2-methylpyran-4-one	Used in antitumor therapy and in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, antioxidant [23].
4,5-Diamino-6-hydroxypyrimidine	Exerts a positive effect on the immune system by promoting the formation of an adaptive immune response. Applied in the treatment of autoimmune diseases and T-cell mediated hypersensitivity [23].
Phloroglucinol	An antispasmodic agent used to control pain associated with acute and chronic disorders of the urinary and biliary tracts [33].
Pyrimidine-4,6-diol-5-methyl	It is used in the treatment of viral diseases leading to chronic liver conditions [23].
Maltol compounds	Iron maltol is a relatively safe and effective oral iron therapy and may represent an effective alternative to intravenous iron [10]. They demonstrate stable and clinically significant improvements in hemoglobin levels and iron availability indicators (ferritin and transferrin saturation), and show that it is well tolerated during prolonged treatment [18].

To confirm the positive effect of the carbon dioxide extract of fir on the human body, studies of the aqueous fraction of the CO₂ extract were conducted by LLC 'Exxo Pharm' [24]. The studies confirmed the following effects from the course intake of the extract: anti-stressor, immunostimulatory, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, hemostimulatory, adaptogenic, and antioxidant effects.

In the Russian market, the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir is available both as a standalone product and as an ingredient in food products (phytococktails, marmalade, and caramel based on berries and the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir).

However, the market is not saturated with such offerings, presenting opportunities for the development and successful commercialization of new food products containing the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir, utilizing both the aqueous and lipid fractions of the extract.

Thus, the CO₂ extract of Siberian fir is a promising functional ingredient with proven antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, adaptogenic, and hemostimulating properties, which can be effectively used in the development of new food products as a flavor and aromatic additive as well as a source of biologically active substances.

References

1. Allenspach M, Steuer C. *α -Pinene: A never-ending story. Phytochemistry. 2021 Oct;190:112857. doi: 10.1016/j.phytochem.2021.112857. Epub 2021 Aug 5. PMID: 34365295.*
2. Aust O, Stahl W, Sies H, Tronnier H, Heinrich U. *Supplementation with tomato-based products increases lycopene, phytofluene, and phytoene levels in human serum and protects against UV-light-induced erythema. Int J Vitam Nutr Res. 2005 Jan;75(1):54-60. doi: 10.1024/0300-9831.75.1.54. PMID: 15830922.*
3. Baek S, Kim J, Moon BS, Park SM, Jung DE, Kang SY, Lee SJ, Oh SJ, Kwon SH, Nam MH, Kim HO, Yoon HJ, Kim BS, Lee KP. *Camphene Attenuates Skeletal Muscle Atrophy by Regulating Oxidative Stress and Lipid Metabolism in Rats. Nutrients. 2020 Dec 3;12(12):3731. doi: 10.3390/nu12123731. PMID: 33287349; PMCID: PMC7761825.*
4. de Freitas BC, Queiroz PA, Baldin VP, do Amaral PH, Rodrigues LL, Vandresen F, R Caleffi-Ferracioli K, de L Scodro RB, Cardoso RF, Siqueira VL. *(-)-Camphene-based derivatives as potential antibacterial agents against Staphylococcus aureus and Enterococcus spp. Future Microbiol. 2020 Oct;15:1527-1534. doi: 10.2217/fmb-2020-0131. Epub 2020 Nov 20. PMID: 33215538.*
5. Dong H, Chen J, Zhang H, Zhao M, Yue Y, Wang S. *Palmitic acid inhibits macrophage-mediated chemotherapy resistance in multiple myeloma via ALOX12 signaling. Int Immunopharmacol. 2024 Dec 25;143(Pt 1):113320. doi: 10.1016/j.intimp.2024.113320. Epub 2024 Oct 8. PMID: 39378653.*
6. Earle C. J. *Abies sibirica / Earle C. J. [Electronic resource] // The Gymnosperm Database: [website]. — URL: https://www.conifers.org/pi/Abies_sibirica.php (accessed: 27.01.2026).*
7. Gurin V., Kuts V., Maloshtan S., Barkholenko V. *Combined mobile supercritical CO₂ extraction plant // Chronos Natural and Technical Sciences. — 2021. — No. 6. — pp. 16-23.*
8. Jo H, Cha B, Kim H, Brito S, Kwak BM, Kim ST, Bin BH, Lee MG. *α -Pinene Enhances the Anticancer Activity of Natural Killer Cells via ERK/AKT Pathway. Int J Mol Sci. 2021 Jan 11;22(2):656. doi: 10.3390/ijms22020656. PMID: 33440866; PMCID: PMC7826552.*
9. Khan UM, Sevindik M, Zarrabi A, Nami M, Ozdemir B, Kaplan DN, Selamoglu Z, Hasan M, Kumar M, Alshehri MM, Sharifi-Rad J. *Lycopene: Food Sources, Biological Activities, and Human Health Benefits. Oxid Med Cell Longev. 2021 Nov 19;2021:2713511. doi: 10.1155/2021/2713511. PMID: 34840666; PMCID: PMC8626194.*

10. Khoury A, Pagan KA, Farland MZ. *Ferric Maltol: A New Oral Iron Formulation for the Treatment of Iron Deficiency in Adults*. *Ann Pharmacother*. 2021 Feb;55(2):222-229. doi: 10.1177/1060028020941014. Epub 2020 Jul 7. PMID: 32633548.
11. Liu S, Long Y, Yu S, Zhang D, Yang Q, Ci Z, Cui M, Zhang Y, Wan J, Li D, Shi A, Li N, Yang M, Lin J. *Borneol in cardio-cerebrovascular diseases: Pharmacological actions, mechanisms, and therapeutics*. *Pharmacol Res*. 2021 Jul;169:105627. doi: 10.1016/j.phrs.2021.105627. Epub 2021 Apr 21. PMID: 33892091.
12. Martins T, Barros AN, Rosa E, Antunes L. *Enhancing Health Benefits through Chlorophylls and Chlorophyll-Rich Agro-Food: A Comprehensive Review*. *Molecules*. 2023 Jul 11;28(14):5344. doi: 10.3390/molecules28145344. PMID: 37513218; PMCID: PMC10384064.
13. Matsubara E, Fukagawa M, Okamoto T, Ohnuki K, Shimizu K, Kondo R. *(-)-Bornyl acetate induces autonomic relaxation and reduces arousal level after visual display terminal work without any influences of task performance in low-dose condition*. *Biomed Res*. 2011 Apr;32(2):151-7. doi: 10.2220/biomedres.32.151. PMID: 21551951.
14. Rahmani H, Moloudi MR, Hashemi P, Hassanzadeh K, Izadpanah E. *Alpha-Pinene Alleviates Motor Activity in Animal Model of Huntington's Disease via Enhancing Antioxidant Capacity*. *Neurochem Res*. 2023 Jun;48(6):1775-1782. doi: 10.1007/s11064-023-03860-9. Epub 2023 Jan 23. PMID: 36689085.
15. Russo A, Bruno M, Avola R, Cardile V, Rigano D. *Chamazulene-Rich Artemisia arborescens Essential Oils Affect the Cell Growth of Human Melanoma Cells*. *Plants (Basel)*. 2020 Aug 6;9(8):1000. doi: 10.3390/plants9081000. PMID: 32781664; PMCID: PMC7464588.
16. Salas-Oropeza J, Jimenez-Estrada M, Perez-Torres A, Castell-Rodriguez AE, Becerril-Millan R, Rodriguez-Monroy MA, Jarquin-Yañez K, Canales-Martinez MM. *Wound Healing Activity of α -Pinene and α -Phellandrene*. *Molecules*. 2021 Apr 24;26(9):2488. doi: 10.3390/molecules26092488. PMID: 33923276; PMCID: PMC8123182.
17. Santos KLB, Bragança VAN, Pacheco LV, Ota SSB, Aguiar CPO, Borges RS. *Essential features for antioxidant capacity of ascorbic acid (vitamin C)*. *J Mol Model*. 2021 Dec 3;28(1):1. doi: 10.1007/s00894-021-04994-9. PMID: 34862566.
18. Schmidt C, Allen S, Kopyt N, Pergola P. *Iron Replacement Therapy with Oral Ferric Maltol: Review of the Evidence and Expert Opinion*. *J Clin Med*. 2021 Sep 28;10(19):4448. doi: 10.3390/jcm10194448. PMID: 34640466; PMCID: PMC8509126.

19. Solagift / [Electronic resource] // LLC “Solagift”: [website].— URL: <https://solagift.ru/#search> (accessed: 27.01.2026).
20. Tag Archives: health benefits of Camphene / [Electronic resource] // Greener Life Club Members: [website].— URL: <https://ayurvedicoils.com/tag/health-benefits-of-camphene> (accessed: 27.01.2026).
21. Xiaohua LI, Zhihang D, Jianjun Y, Yongyu Z, Yihang LI, Shifang L, Qu N, Depo Y, Lixia Z. Bornyl acetate extracted from *Sharen* () inhibits proliferation, invasion and induces apoptosis by suppressing phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase/protein kinase B signaling in colorectal cancer: *J Tradit Chin Med*. 2023 Oct;43(6):1081-1091. doi: 10.19852/j.cnki.jtcm.20231018.002. PMID: 37946470; PMCID: PMC10623251.
22. Yuan Q, Xie F, Huang W, Hu M, Yan Q, Chen Z, Zheng Y, Liu L. The review of alpha-linolenic acid: Sources, metabolism, and pharmacology. *Phytother Res*. 2022 Jan;36(1):164-188. doi: 10.1002/ptr.7295. Epub 2021 Sep 22. PMID: 34553434.
23. Analysis of the composition of the cellular juice of Siberian fir needles / [Electronic resource] // Regional Testing Center “Farmatest” of FSBEI HE PGFA of the Ministry of Health of Russia: [website].— URL: https://magazinrav.ru/article/analiz_sostava_kletochnogo_soka_pihtyi_sibirskoj (accessed: 28.01.2026).
24. Studies of Siberian fir cell sap / [Electronic resource] // LLC ‘Exxo Pharm’: [website].— URL: <https://uralfir.ru/science/researches/sok> (accessed: 28.01.2026).
25. Carotenoids. Significance for plants / [Electronic resource] // Studbooks.net: [website].— URL: https://studbooks.net/1295953/estestvoznanie/karotinoidy_znachenie_dlya_rasteniy (accessed: 27.01.2026).
26. Linoleic acid / [Electronic resource] // Scientific and Educational Portal ‘Great Russian Encyclopedia’: [website].— URL: <https://bigenc.ru/c/linolevaia-kislota-bd2fc9> (accessed: 27.01.2026).
27. Macroelements: types and their role in the body / [Electronic resource] // ROSKACHESTVO: [website].— URL: <https://rskrf.ru/tips/eksperty-obyasnyayut/makroelementy-kakie-byvayut-i-zachem-nuzhny-organizmu/> (accessed: 28.01.2026).
28. Microelements: types, their role, and effects on health / [Electronic resource] // ROSKACHESTVO: [website].— URL: <https://rskrf.ru/tips/eksperty-obyasnyayut/mikroelementy-kakie-byvayut-zachem-nuzhny-i-kak-vliyayut-na-zdorove/> (accessed: 28.01.2026).
29. Morozov V. I., Petrusheva N. A. Technological process of harvesting and processing coniferous foliage // *Lesotechnical Journal*.— 2019.— No. 3.

30. Nilova, L. P., Pilipenko, T. V., Potoroko, I. Yu. *Tocopherols and tocotrienols: properties, functions, natural sources. Analytical Review [Text]* / L. P. Nilova, T. V. Pilipenko, I. Yu. Potoroko // *Bulletin of the South Ural State University. Series: Food and Biotechnologies.* — 2021. — No. 1. — pp. 68-81.
31. *CO₂ extract of Siberian fir* / [Electronic resource] // *Biocutics: [website].* — URL: <https://www.biozevtika.ru/co2-extract-pihta/> (accessed: 27.01.2026).
32. Sizova, N. V. *Comparison of antioxidant activity of fir oil and fir CO₂ extract, sunflower oil, and CO₂ extract of sunflower seeds [Text]* / N. V. Sizova // *Chemistry of Plant Raw Materials.* — 2004. — No. 3. — Pp. 99-102.
33. *Phloroglucinol (Phloroglucinol)* / [Electronic resource] // *Vidal Directory «Medicinal Preparations in Russia»: [website].* — URL: <https://www.vidal.ru/drugs/molecule/3082> (accessed: 28.01.2026).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.29.13.076

测试—理论力学在线课程运动学习题
**TEST — PROBLEMS IN KINEMATICS FOR ONLINE COURSES
IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS**

Pirogov Sergey Petrovich

*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor
Tyumen Industrial University*

摘要：本文给出了运动学部分理论力学测试题的示例。值得注意的是，此类测试题的使用能够实现问题解答的自动化评估，这对于参与人数众多的在线课程至关重要。

关键词：理论力学，测试题，问题，运动学。

Abstract. *This paper presents an example of a test problem in theoretical mechanics for the kinematics section. It is noted that the use of such tests enables the automation of evaluating problem solutions, which is essential in online courses with large numbers of participants.*

Keywords: *theoretical mechanics, tests, problems, kinematics.*

Introduction

Courses in technical subjects— such as theoretical mechanics, strength of materials, theory of machines and mechanisms, etc.— include calculated-graphic assignments, i. e., independent problem solving. This requires a significant amount of instructors' time for assessment and review [1-5].

When developing online courses that can accommodate a large number of participants — up to several hundred — it is necessary to automate the evaluation of assignments.

To address this issue, test problems were developed for various sections of theoretical mechanics — statics, kinematics, and dynamics — combining problem solving and test completion with automatic grading.

Methods

Below is an example of a test problem in the kinematics section — the study of translational and rotational motion of a rigid body. The solution involves answering questions with multiple answer options. Thus, from the solution algorithm, a test is generated that can be automatically checked by any program.

Based on this method, an educational program can be created where, upon an incorrect answer, the student is referred to the theoretical material corresponding to the type of error, after which the test can resume from the question answered incorrectly.

Results

We present one variant of the task.

Body 1 moves along an inclined plane according to the law: $x = 2 + 70t^2$ (cm) and drives pulley 2, connected by a belt transmission to pulley 3 (Fig. 1). Dimensions of the pulleys: $R_2 = 50$ cm; $r_2 = 30$ cm; $R_3 = 60$ cm; $r_3 = 40$ cm; Motion time from the initial position $t_1 = 0.75$ s.

Fig. 1. Illustration for the example

1. The velocity of body 1 as a function of time is ... cm/s:
 $140t$ $2+70t^2$ $70t$ $2t+140t$

2. The angular velocity of link 2 is determined by the formula:
 v_1/r_2 v_1/R_2 v_1/r_3 v_1/R_3

3. The angular velocity of link 2 as a function of time is ... rad/s:
 $(14/3)$ $t(14/5)$ $t(7/3)$ $t(7/2)t$

4. The angular velocity of link 3 is determined from the equation:
 $\omega_2 R_2 = \omega_3 R_3$ $\omega_2 r_2 = \omega_3 R_3$ $\omega_2 R_2 = \omega_3 r_3$ $\omega_2 r_2 = \omega_3 r_3$

5. The angular velocity of link 3 as a function of time is ... rad/s:
 $(35/9)t$ $(10/3)t$ $(20/3)t$ $(70/9)t$

6. The angular velocity of link 3 at $t = 0.75$ s is ... rad/s:
 $2,92$ $3,89$ $7,78$ $5,84$

7. The angular acceleration of link 3 is ... rad/s²:

35/9 10/3 20/3 70/3

8. The velocity of point M is determined by the formula:

$\omega_3 r_3$ $\omega_3 R_3$ $\omega_2 R_2$ $\omega_2 r_2$

9. The velocity of point M at t = 0.75 s is ... cm/s:

117 195 233 88,66

10. The tangential acceleration of point M is found using the formula:

$\epsilon_3 r_3$ $\omega_3 r_3$ $\epsilon_3 R_3$ $\omega_3^2 r_3$

11. The tangential acceleration of point M at t=0.75 s is ...cm/s²:

156 182 203 102

12. The normal acceleration of point M is found using the formula:

$\omega_3^2 r_3$ $\epsilon_3 r_3$ $\omega_3 r_3$ $\epsilon_3 R_3$

13. The normal acceleration of point M at t=0.75 s is ...cm/s²:

341 422 537 602

14. The total acceleration of point M at t=0.75 s is ...cm/s²

375 451 632 711

Fig. 2. Velocity and acceleration of point M

15. The velocity of point M in Fig. 2 is directed along
1 2 3 4
16. The tangential component of the acceleration of point M is directed along
1 2 3 4
17. The normal component of the acceleration of point M is directed along
2 3 4 1
18. The total acceleration of point M is directed along
6 5 4 3

Discussion

The test contains 18 questions that enable assessment of the understanding of the fundamental concepts of point kinematics and rotational motion of a rigid body — velocity and acceleration of a point, angular velocity, and angular acceleration of a rigid body.

Such tests do not require a large number of variants and facilitate the automation of grading calculation and graphical assignments.

References

1. Pirogov, S. P. *Innovative technologies in theoretical mechanics courses for distance learning. Supporting University in the International Electronic Space: V International Scientific-Practical Videoconference — Tyumen, 2018. pp. 51-53.*
2. Pirogov, S. P. *Application of educational software in theoretical mechanics courses for distance education. Electronic Education: Prospects for the Use of SMART Technologies: 3rd International Scientific-Practical Videoconference — Tyumen, 2016. pp. 127-129.*
3. Pirogov, S. P. *Application of educational programs in theoretical mechanics courses for distance learning. Engineering Bulletin of the Don. — 2014. — No. 4-1 (31). P. 89.*
4. Pirogov S. P., Umanskaya O. L., Krivchun N. A., Kolosov V. I. *Test problems in the discipline “Theoretical Mechanics. Kinematics”. Certificate of database registration RU 2025623871, 17.09.2025. Application No. 2025623295 dated 30.07.2025.*
5. Kolosov V. I. *Development of an electronic textbook on theoretical mechanics. In the collection: Issues in the operation of transport systems. Proceedings of the All-Russian (National) Scientific-Practical Conference of Students, Graduate Students, and Young Researchers. Tyumen, 2024. pp. 278-280.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.29.62.177

基于结构和性能的轧制金属质量评估方法
**METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO QUALITY ASSESSMENT
ROLLED METAL BY STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES**

Fomikhina Irina Victorovna

*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Head of Laboratory
Institute of Powder Metallurgy named after Academician O. V. Roman,
National Academy of Sciences of Belarus,
Minsk, Republic of Belarus*

摘要：本文研究了焊接接头组织对结构钢结构性能的影响，探讨了焊接结构腐蚀损伤的原因，并揭示了组织形成模式，从而有助于提高焊接接头的质量、结构的可靠性和耐久性。

关键词：轧制产品，组织，性能，方法，质量。

Abstract. *The influence of the structure of welded joints on the performance of structures made of structural steels is studied. The causes of corrosion damage to welded structures are considered. The patterns of structure formation are revealed, which allow improving the quality of welded joints, reliability and durability of structures.*

Keywords: *rolled products, structure, properties, methodology, quality.*

Introduction

The production of high-quality Metallurgical Products that meet the requirements of normative-technical documentation, as well as the rational use of raw materials, fuel, and semifinished products during manufacturing, are among the most critical tasks of modern metallurgy [1]. Analysis of the causes of failure in parts made from structural steel grades indicates that a key factor influencing reliability and durability is the concentration of harmful impurities, both dissolved in the steel and present as non-metallic inclusions. Nonmetallic inclusions in steel occur as foreign bodies that disrupt the homogeneity of its structure. Non-metallic inclusions adversely affect the impact toughness of steel [2, 3]. Upon detection of banding in the ferrite-pearlite structure during the processing of hot-rolled stock, additional measures aimed at its reduction are implemented, significantly increasing the labor intensity of the entire technological process, as well as the time and cost of product manufacturing [3]. Grain size plays a crucial

role in determining the properties of steel. The finer the actual grain, the higher the strength (tensile strength σ_b , yield strength σ_r), plasticity (relative elongation δ , relative reduction ψ), impact toughness (KCU, KCV), and endurance limit σ_{-1} . The coarser the grain, the more susceptible the steel is to quenching cracks and deformations. Excessive overheating, besides causing coarse grain formation, may lead to the development of a Widmanstätten structure. With such a structure, steel becomes highly brittle, exhibits poor resistance to dynamic loads, and is unsuitable for products intended for critical applications. Surface decarburization reduces the strength characteristics of steel — strength, hardness, and consequently, resistance to deformation and wear. Systematization of control methods for Metallurgical Products, the development of quality criteria, and the timely diagnosis and elimination of structural defects at the production stage constitute a pressing task in modern materials science [4].

The aim of this work is to develop a methodological approach for assessing the quality of metallurgical products based on their structure and properties.

Research methods and principles

The investigations were conducted at the Accredited Testing Center of the Powder Metallurgy Institute named after Academician O. V. Roman of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, using fragments of rolled metal samples in service within the petrochemical industry of the Republic of Belarus. The macrostructure was examined using a high-resolution scanning electron microscope “Mira” by Tescan (Czech Republic) and a stereoscopic microscope “Altami CM0745.” The microstructure was investigated using a light microscope “MeF-3” by Reichert (Austria). The tensile test was performed on a universal testing machine Tinius Olsen H150K-U (United Kingdom). The Impact Bending Test was carried out on a pendulum impact tester “Tinius Olsen IT406” with a maximum pendulum impact energy of 406 J. Brinell hardness was measured using the TSh-2M hardness tester.

Methodological Approach to Quality Assessment of Metallurgical Products by Structure and Properties

The methodological approach to quality assessment of metallurgical products for the petrochemical industry integrates a comprehensive analysis of structure and properties in accordance with applicable standards. Structural characteristics determining quality comprise: macrostructure, contamination by non-metallic inclusions, laminations, grain size, presence of a decarburized layer, type of microstructure, and the morphology and uniformity of cementite distribution. Strength properties are evaluated by tensile strength, yield strength, and elongation. The scheme of comprehensive investigation of rolled metal is presented in Fig. 1.

The diagram shows the cut sections of specimens for structural investigation. According to the diagram, the study of contamination by non-metallic inclusions,

Laminations, and texture is conducted in the longitudinal section of the polished specimen. Grain Size, decarburized layer, and type of structure are analyzed in the cross-section of the polished specimen. Hardness Measurement, Chemical Composition, and strength characteristics are performed in the longitudinal or cross-sections depending on the assigned tasks.

Fig. 1 Scheme of comprehensive investigation of rolled metal: 1 — Laminations; 2 — Hardness; 3 — Texture; 4 — Contamination by non-metallic inclusions; 5 — Macrostructure; 6 — Chemical Composition; 7-8 — Billet and tensile specimen, 9 — Fracture with delaminations of the transverse impact specimen with V(U) notch; 10 — type of microstructure, Grain Size, decarburized layer.

Macrostructure analysis is performed according to GOST 10243 (ST SEV 2837) “Steel. Methods for testing and evaluating macrostructure.” Assessment of contamination by non-metallic inclusions is conducted according to GOST 1778 “Steel. Metallographic methods for identification of non-metallic inclusions.” Microstructure type, morphology, and uniformity of cementite distribution are determined according to GOST 8233 “Steel. Microstructure standards.” Laminations — according to GOST 5640 (ASTM E 1268) “Steel. Metallographic method for assessing the microstructure of rolled steel flat products. Decarburization depth — according to GOST 1763 (ST SEV 477, ISO 3887) ‘Steel.’ Methods for determining the depth of the decarburized layer. Grain Size — according to GOST 5639 ‘Steels and Alloys.’ Methods for detection and determination of grain size. Tensile testing is conducted in accordance with GOST 1497 ‘Metals.’ Tensile testing method and GOST 10006 (ISO 6892) ‘Metal Pipes.’ Tensile Test Method. Impact Bending Test according to GOST 9454 «Metals». Impact Bending Test Method at Low, Room, and Elevated Temperatures. Brinell Hardness according to GOST 9012 «Metals». Brinell Hardness Measurement Method.

1. Macrostructure

Macrostructure examination is conducted visually without specialized instruments. If necessary, additional defect investigations are performed using stereoscopic, optical, or scanning electron microscopes.

Figure 2 presents the most frequently encountered defects of rolled metal exhibiting rejection characteristics.

Fig. 2. Macrostructure of defects in rolled metal: *a, b, c* — delamination along the rolled slag inclusion; *d* — scaly structure.

Quality criterion. *Absence of shrinkage cavities, porosity, delaminations, films, and other defects. defects visible without special instruments.*

Fig. 3. Contamination by non-metallic inclusions in the rolled metal sample, 100×:
a — spot oxides 1 point; b — line oxides 2.5 points, sulfides 2 points;
c — sulfides 1 point, spot oxides 2 points, line oxides 2 points;
d — brittle silicates 3.0 points; e — non-deforming silicates 2.0 points;
f — brittle silicates 1.5 points, non-deforming silicates 1.0 point;

2. Contamination from non-metallic inclusions.

The universally accepted methodology in metallurgical practice for determining contamination of metallurgical products by non-metallic inclusions is the Sh method — comparing the fields of view of unetched polished sections with reference scales under a microscope at 100× magnification. Figure 3 presents the analysis of contamination by non-metallic inclusions based on the maximum score of the rolled metal sample.

The assessment of non-metallic inclusion contamination in deformed metallurgical products is performed on sections with longitudinal fiber orientation. The maximum or average score is determined depending on the requirements of the normative documentation. The following are analyzed: linear oxides (LO), spot oxides (SO), brittle silicates (BS), plastic silicates (PS), non-deforming silicates

(NDS), sulfides (S), linear nitrides and carbonitrides (LNC), spot nitrides and carbonitrides (SNC), aluminum nitrides (AN).

Quality criterion. *Steel contamination by non-metallic inclusions (oxides, silicates, and sulfides LO, SO, BS, PS, NDS, S) shall not exceed 2.5-3 points (average) and 3.5 points (maximum) according to TU and STP.*

3. Laminations

The scheme for cutting samples from flat rolled metal is presented in

Fig. 4. Scheme for cutting samples from flat rolled metal

The evaluation of laminations is conducted on longitudinal sections by comparing with standard images (Table B.3 — scale 3, ‘Standard images for the assessment of ferrite-pearlite laminations’ at 100× magnification). The diameter of the standard images is 80 mm. For the assessment of microstructural ferrite-pearlite laminations according to GOST 5640, a comparison method with reference scales is used, constructed based on the increasing number of pearlite bands, taking into account their continuity and the elongation degree of ferrite grains. Figure 5 presents photographs of ferrite-pearlite lamination microstructures.

Laminations are determined by the highest score found in at least three areas of the specimen. The modern generation of pipe steels exhibits a ferrite-bainite structure; therefore, new standard scales have been developed for them (table B.5 — scale 5 «Reference images for assessing ferrite-bainite laminations»). The scale for assessing the laminations in the structure of high-strength low-alloy steels is based on the increasing number of bainitic bands, considering their continuity and the equiaxed nature of grains in the ferritic bands, and consists of three rows

with six points each. The first two rows are designed to evaluate laminations at microscope magnifications of $100\times$ and $500\times$, while the third row assesses the anisotropy of ferrite at $500\times$ magnification.

Fig. 5. Laminations of the ferrite-pearlite structure, $100\times$:
a — 2 points; *b* — 4 points

Quality criterion. According to the requirements of STP 09100.17002.116, laminations in metal products for petrochemical industries should not exceed 2-2.5 points.

4. Decarburized layer

The metallographic method involves determining the depth of the decarburized layer by examining the microstructure under a microscope. Samples are cut perpendicular to the fiber direction. Two zones of decarburization are identified: the zone of complete decarburization and the zone of partial decarburization. The zone of complete decarburization is characterized by a pure ferrite microstructure. The zone of partial decarburization exhibits a microstructure different from that of the base metal. The total decarburization depth comprises the zones of complete and partial decarburization and is measured from the edge of the specimen to the base metal structure (Fig. 6). If a complete decarburization zone is absent, the partial decarburization zone is measured from the edge of the specimen to the base metal structure. According to the distribution of decarburization, it is classified as uniform — along the entire perimeter of the specimen — or localized on specific sections of the specimen perimeter. The depth of the decarburized layer is determined either as the maximum depth for the given specimen or as the average of five measurements taken at the locations exhibiting the most significant decarburization, with the maximum depth being indicated. The method is specified in the applicable product standards. If no such specification exists, the depth of decarburization is defined as the maximum depth for the given specimen.

Fig. 6. Decarburization, $\times 200$: *a* — steel 60 PP; *b* — steel 30KhGSA

According to TU 14-105-712-2003, ‘Sheet rolling of structural alloyed high-quality steel grade 30KhGSA.’ The depth of the complete decarburization zone is regulated by the technical conditions. According to TU, it must not exceed 2.5% of the actual sheet thickness on one side.

The permissible depth of decarburization in steel products is not a fixed constant and is regulated by GOST or technical conditions (TU) for a specific type of Metallurgical Products. The main standards depend on the steel grade and the diameter (thickness) of the product.

5. Widmanstätten structure

The Widmanstätten structure (Fig. 7) is not regulated.

Fig. 7. Widmanstätten structure, $\times 100$: *a* — grade 2; *b* — grade 3

Additional research is necessary to determine the impact of the Widmanstätten grade on steel embrittlement, which is particularly important for assessing the quality of rolled metal used in the oil industry.

6. Actual Grain Size

To determine the grain size, the grains visible under the microscope are compared with standard scale images, and the average grain diameter is measured. Using the comparison method, the polished section is examined under a microscope at 100x magnification, and the grain size is compared with the standard images on the scale (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Actual grain size in fine-grained and coarse-grained rolled steel 20, 100x:
a — grade 10 (11 μm); b — grade 8 (22 μm)

Quality criterion. According to the requirements of STP 09100.17002.116, the grain size must not exceed grade 8. The microstructure should consist of ferrite grains and sorbite-like or granular pearlite, arranged as uniformly as possible.

7. Strength, plasticity, hardness, toughness.

Tensile testing enables the assessment of metallurgical products quality based on ultimate strength, yield strength, and elongation (see Fig. 8). Attention should be paid not only to the conformity of actual characteristics with the standards but also to the plastic properties resource, determined by the ratio of ultimate strength to yield strength (σ_b/σ_T), which allows further deformation (e.g., bending to achieve the desired shape) without failure. It has been determined that the rolled metal exhibiting the best properties has yield strength at the minimally permissible level and tensile strength at the maximum, i.e., the ratio $\sigma_b/\sigma_T = 1.35$. A satisfactory result is when both the yield strength and tensile strength are at the minimally permissible level, $\sigma_b/\sigma_T = 1.14$. An acceptable ratio is $\sigma_b/\sigma_T = 1.09$; however, in this case, the plastic properties resource is virtually exhausted. It should be taken into account that steel undergoes aging over time, leading to slight hardening and a significant loss of plasticity. The tensile diagram of samples cut from rolled metal is shown in

Fig. 8. Tensile diagram of rolled metal samples.

Hardness Measurement allows determining the condition of the material. If the sample presented for research is small in size, ASTM tables can be used to convert hardness numbers into the material's tensile strength. Impact toughness enables the assessment of metal structure quality based on its capacity to absorb impact energy.

The mechanical properties of rolled metal are regulated by product standards.

References

1. *Atlas of Industrial Failures of Various Structures* / A. F. Ilyushchenko, L. V. Markova, V. A. Chekan, I. V. Fomikhina, V. V. Koleda. *Nat. Acad. of Sciences of Belarus, Institute of Powder Metallurgy*. — Minsk: Belarusian Science, 2017. — 312 p.
2. *Fomikhina, I. V. Mechanisms of Degradation of Structural Steels and Methods for Improving the Operational Properties of Products Made from Them: Dissertation ... Doctor of Technical Sciences: 05.16.09* / I. V. Fomikhina. — Minsk, 2018. — 398 p.
3. *Atlas of Industrial Failures of Various Structures Made from Non-Ferrous Metals and Alloys* / A. F. Ilyushchenko, L. V. Markova, V. A. Chekan, I. V. Fomikhina, V. V. Koleda. — Belarusian Science, 2022. — 364 p.
4. *Fomikhina, I. V. Methods of control and approaches to the elimination of technological and operational defects in structural steels* / I. V. Fomikhina. *National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Institute of Powder Metallurgy*. — Minsk: Belarusian Science, 2024. — 302 p.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.29.91.074

机器人助手对军事行动的潜在影响
**ON THE POTENTIAL IMPACT OF ROBOTIC ASSISTANTS
ON MILITARY OPERATIONS**

Tikhanychev Oleg Vasilyevich

PhD in Engineering, Professor

Academy Military Sciences,

Deputy Head of Department

Company group «Technoserv», Moscow, Russia

摘要：本研究的对象是军事机器人技术（特别是所谓的机器人伙伴）在现代武装冲突中的应用过程；研究主题是该过程的主要组成部分对军事训练和作战方式的潜在变化以及先进武器研发方向的影响。

本文采用一般科学分析和综合方法。研究的主要结论表明，技术和软件伙伴的出现将显著影响作战装备的发展，使其从所谓的“极限能力装备”的研发转向通过伙伴的软件、组成和设计现代化来提升作战能力，从而有望大幅降低维持高作战性能的成本，并改变武器的使用形式和方法。

关键词：军事机器人技术，机器人伙伴，软件助手，新型作战方式

Abstract. *The object of the study is the process of employing military robotics, specifically so-called robot companions, in the context of modern armed conflicts; the subject of the study is the influence of the main components of this process on the potential changes in methods of military training and conduct of hostilities, as well as approaches to the development of advanced weaponry.*

The article utilizes general scientific methods of analysis and synthesis. The primary conclusions of the conducted research indicate that the advent of technical and software companions will significantly affect the development of combat equipment, moving from the creation of so-called 'extreme capability equipment' towards enhancing combat capabilities through the modernization of software, composition, and design of the companions, promising a substantial reduction in costs for maintaining high combat performance and in the forms and methods of weapon employment.

Keywords: *military robotics, robot companions, software assistants, new methods of combat operations*

1. Introduction

The experience of modern armed conflicts demonstrates trends toward active informatization and robotization of the battlefield, altering the entire landscape of the combat environment [1]. At the same time, as evidenced by current research findings, the artificial intelligence (AI) implemented in robotic combat systems is not yet capable of replacing humans in combat. The situation is unlikely to change in the foreseeable future [2-6]. However, on the other hand, as experience shows, it is problematic for a human, due to their psychophysical characteristics, to counteract intellectualized combat systems.

Based on the combination of these factors, under current conditions, the creation of a collaboration between human actions and intellectualized systems, complementing and enhancing each other's best qualities, appears reasonable. This union potentially ensures an improvement in the quality of control algorithms for robotic-technical complexes (RTC). In accordance with the laws of dialectics, the result of this fusion may significantly influence the methods of conducting military operations, making the topic addressed in the article both timely and relevant.

2. Materials and Methods

A systemic approach was chosen as the methodological foundation of the study. The application of a systemic approach, along with decomposition methods and comparative analysis, enabled a comprehensive examination of the issues related to the combat use of software and software-hardware complexes as robot companions.

3. Results

As the analysis of modern local wars and armed conflicts has demonstrated, the situation on and above the battlefield has changed due to the active implementation of robotics. In this regard, it is worth recalling that, from a historical perspective and according to the laws of military science, every significant change in forms and methods has been accompanied by organizational changes in the structure of military formations and methods of troop employment. Clear examples of such influence include changes in fortification following the advent of artillery, the transition to dispersed formations with the emergence of automatic small arms, and so forth.

The motorization of troops required the formation of mixed-composition military units, including tanks, mechanized infantry, self-propelled artillery, mobile engineering, and communication units that complemented each other. However, tanks within these formations, to reduce losses from anti-tank weapons, were used in infantry accompaniment, slowing down to its speed, while the infantry itself was accompanied by artillery, which necessitated the intentional reduction of certain characteristics of the employed systems to ensure effective coordination. It is clear that such decisions, which lead to decreased effectiveness, are not made

arbitrarily; experience indicated that it was simply impossible to reduce losses of combat equipment during military operations otherwise.

For a sufficiently long period in the development of military art, this situation could not be corrected; it was an unavoidable price to pay for ensuring the effective joint use of combat assets with varying characteristics. However, at present, as has been demonstrated in practice, informatization and robotization of the combat space have introduced new factors and new opportunities. What has once again made relevant the search for solutions to the problem of troop interaction and the refinement of principles for organizing their deployment [7,8,9].

Current trends in armament development allow us to conclude that most prospective combat systems will consist of a primary combat asset complemented by auxiliary hardware-software and software complexes, ensuring effective realization of the fundamental capabilities of the base asset or the military unit as a whole. As auxiliary tools, physical and/or software robotic assistants (assistants, companions — terminology in this field has not yet been officially standardized) will likely be employed.

Currently, there are already examples of the implementation of such systems:

- software and hardware control and alert systems concerning the technical condition, which are quite actively used as “internal” components within the onboard equipment of modern aircraft. As technologies advance, such systems are increasingly being implemented at multiple levels, extending to individual infantry systems, such as the software components of the full-face Ronin helmet by Devtac;

- “External” systems are less widespread; a few examples currently include transport robot companions, the so-called “mules,” such as the American MUTT 600 (Multi-Utility Tactical Transport), autonomous transport robots SMSS (Squad Mission Support System), SMET (Squad Multipurpose Equipment Transport), and similar models [10, 11].

4. Discussion

The analysis conducted indicates that the use of robot companions on the battlefield is one of the significant directions in the development of combat robotics. An integral result of implementing the new qualities obtained through the use of robot companions will be changes in the characteristics of combat systems and battlefield equipment, and consequently, changes in the nature of warfare, principles of employment, and the structure of the forces conducting combat operations [12-14].

Firstly, the robotization of the battlefield, of which the appearance of companions is a part, has altered many paradigms that were previously considered fundamental. For example, whereas information used to be painstakingly gathered bit by bit and verified by multiple sources, after the saturation of the battlefield with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), it becomes so abundant that

information must be filtered and sifted. The paradigm of air defense (AD) has also changed: previously, the primary task was not to shoot down enemy aircraft, but to prevent them from delivering precise strikes. The use of combat UAVs and ground RTCs has given rise to the ‘brave pilot’ paradox, creating a need to destroy enemy UAVs and RTCs before they can strike, with the focus ideally shifting toward neutralizing the command centers of unmanned systems. Many such examples can be cited. Accordingly, changes in fundamental paradigms inevitably affect other components of military operations.

Secondly, within the framework of these changes, it is likely that the forms and methods of employing both units and individual equipment and military personnel will change. Due to their autonomy and self-sufficiency, they will, on the one hand, be able to independently accomplish many tasks; on the other hand, within the framework of coordination using AI components, they will exchange information more effectively and solve joint tasks related to the intersection of their operational sectors.

Thirdly, the emergence of technical companions and software assistants will significantly impact technological development. When developing armament programs, it will no longer be necessary to choose between the so-called ‘extreme capability equipment’, expensive but with high performance, and more mass-produced, cheaper equipment — supplementing serial equipment with companions easily upgrades its capabilities to the maximum. Simultaneously, this allows broad possibilities for modernization: to maintain specified characteristics, it will not be necessary to modify or replace the weapon system; it will suffice to replace or upgrade the cheaper robot companions, or sometimes merely update their software.

Fourthly, it is highly likely that the need to form tactical groups from units of different branches and types of troops to accomplish tasks and to ensure complex coordination of their actions will disappear — all types of support and provision will be carried out by robot companions.

And finally, as a result of these changes, the status of every combat participant fundamentally changes. With the introduction of robot companions, lower-level commanders and ordinary servicemen become not merely executors and operators of the RTC — each serviceman or combat vehicle commander becomes the leader of a small personal detachment of robot companions, through whom he analyzes the situation, makes decisions, and issues commands and target designations. This requires new management skills at all levels, the initiative, and coordination of actions. That is, the very paradigm of training military personnel at all levels is changing [15].

These aspects are detailed more thoroughly in Table 1.

Table 1 — Potential influence of the practical deployment of robot companions on the conduct of combat operations

Component of combat operations	Constituent elements of this component	Manifestation of the influence exerted by the use of robot companions
Direct organization and conduct of combat	Control	Refinement of the roles of commanders at all levels and even individual military personnel — each participant in combat operations is now not only a weapons operator but also the commander of a separate robot unit, from which they receive information and to which they issue commands and targeting instructions.
		Delegation of certain functions of situation assessment and action planning to software assistants employing AI technologies.
		The necessity to consider potential threats of deliberate influence on AI decision-making algorithms by the adversary, carried out covertly from users with the aim of indirectly controlling our actions.
	Interaction	On the one hand, internal coordination of the “swarm” and multifunctionality within a single unit and even for an individual serviceman. On the other hand, the formation of specific combat space fields and coordination at their intersections.
	Air defense and protection against ground RTC.	The paradigm shift in air defense from object coverage to destruction of aerial targets, coupled with a focus on neutralizing UAV command posts, necessitates involving companions in counteraction tasks.
Comprehensive support	Reconnaissance	Enhancement of informational awareness combined with the reduction of cognitive load on operators through automation of data processing by software assistants. Expansion of the range of information sources through automatic interaction of robotic companions with external systems
	Engineering support	Introduction of dedicated engineering reconnaissance and mine clearance tools addressing tasks based on individual requests
	Logistical support	Supply personalization and enhanced delivery responsiveness

	Electronic Warfare (EW)	The emergence of individual EW systems on one hand, and the necessity to organize protection of robot companions' actions from enemy EW on the other
Weapons development and personnel training	Development of equipment and armaments	Transition from developing equipment for predefined tasks to flexible design, with planning for developmental potential by expanding the range and structure of companions and updating their software
	Personnel Training	Training on expanded functionalities will be required at all levels of command: analysis of heterogeneous information, task formulation and goal setting, and management of subordinates.
		Development of skills not only in task formulation for personnel but also for software assistants and RTC utilizing AI technologies (prompt), as well as skills in interpreting results generated by AI.
Moral and Psychological Preparation	Studying the limits of applicability of RTC companions and preventing excessive reliance on results generated by AI tools.	

The features listed in Table 1 will be implemented not only for units (group companions) but also for individual weapon systems and even individual military personnel equipped with a 'swarm of companions' (personal companions).

The provisions formulated in the table represent potential capabilities; to realize them, it is necessary to consider and develop rules of application for both personal and group robot companions. Some initial data necessary for implementing this requirement are described in this article.

5. Conclusions

This article is the first to formulate the trend of the potential influence of battlefield robotics, the emergence of personal and group robot companions, and software assistants on the fundamental approaches to developing personnel training programs and advanced weapon development programs, as well as the reflection of these changes in documents governing the organization of combat operations.

It can be assumed that the outcome of implementing the trends described in this article will be the creation of autonomous man-machine systems whose properties and characteristics are not based on the principle of 'alignment with the weakest link', but on the synergy of the best qualities of humans, artificial intelligence, and technical devices. However, this does not preclude the possibility of the group employment of heterogeneous means — not for mutual backup to compensate for lacking combat capabilities, but as a synergistic aggregate of complementary, self-sufficient combat systems.

This conclusion is confirmed by changes in armament programs in many of the world's leading armies. A clear example is the United States' cancellation of the sixth-generation fighter development program for achieving air superiority, NGAD (Next Generation Air Dominance), in favor of developing a swarm of UAV-type CCA (Collaborative Combat Aircraft), such as the YFQ-44A, which, operating jointly with existing fighters, accomplish the same objective. Similar research is conducted by the company Anduril, which introduced the Fury UAV, employing its Lattice OS to provide autonomous capabilities and coordinate operations with manned aircraft as part of the MUM-T (manned-unmanned teaming) program. Some developments in this field have been practically implemented, albeit at the prototype stage: the Chinese "reliable wingman" UAV FH-97A designed to accompany J-35 fighters, the American drone XQ-58 Valkyrie, and others. A similar trend is also underway for ground vehicles, as demonstrated by the equipping of the Chinese VT4A1 advanced tank with two drones for reconnaissance and fire adjustment, and the inclusion of a reconnaissance UAV in the QN-506 tank support combat vehicle. Thus, the technical foundation for these changes is gradually being established, creating the necessity for organizational decisions.

However, so far this remains only a trend, selectively implemented within the framework of individual units. However, the important aspect is not this fact itself, but that adopting the provisions formulated in the article will enable refining the algorithm for developing requirements for weapon systems — shifting from the consideration of individual model characteristics to the formulation of comprehensive measures to ensure the specified characteristics during the creation of combat platforms. Moreover, as a consequence and a scientific regularity, the emergence of new capabilities should give rise to new methods of application.

References

1. Chirov D. and Novak K. (2018). *Promising areas for the development of special-purpose robotic systems*, *Security Issues*. 2: 50-59 <https://doi.org/10.25136/2409-7543.2018.2.22737>.

2. Lele A. "A military perspective on lethal autonomous weapon systems", in *Perspectives on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems (United Nations, New York, 2017)*, pp. 57-61.

3. Pffimlin É. *Drones et robots: La guerre des futurs (Levallois-Perret, France, 2017)*, pp. 13-17.

4. Wainer H., Dorans N. J., Flaugh R., Freen B., and Mislavy R. J. *Computerized Adaptive Testing: A Primer (2nd ed.)*. (Routledge, New York, 2000) <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410605931>.

5. Hamilton T. (2023). *How AI will Alter Multi-Domain Warfare. Future Combat Air & Space Capabilities Summit*, 4 URL: <https://www.aerosociety.com/events-calendar/raes-future-combat-air-and-space-capabilities-summit>.
6. Petrova D. A., Gaivoronskaya Y. V., and Mamychev A. Y. (2019). *Deadly autonomous systems: ethical, legal, political problems and prospects for their solution. Territory of new opportunities. Bulletin of Vladivostok State University*, 11(4): 33-43 <https://doi.org/10.24866/VVSU/2073-3984/2019-4/033-043>.
7. Davison N. "A legal perspective: Autonomous weapon systems under international humanitarian law", in *Perspectives on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems* (United Nations, New York, 2017).
8. Schuller A. (2017). *At the Crossroads of Control: The Intersection of Artificial Intelligence in Autonomous Weapon Systems with International Humanitarian Law*, *Harvard National Security Journal*, 8: 379-425
9. Ukhobotov V. and Izmestyev I. (2016). *On a pursuit problem under resistance of a medium. Bulletin of the South Ural State University series "Mathematics. Mechanics. Physics"* 8(2): 62-66 <https://doi.org/10.14529/mmph160208>.
10. Tikhanychev O. (2023). *Self-Check System of Heuristic Algorithms as a "New Moral" of Intelligent Systems*, *AIP Conference Proceedings*. 2700, 040028 <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0124956>.
11. Ćwiąkała P. (2019). *Testing Procedure of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) Trajectory in Automatic Missions. Appl. Sci.* 9, 3488 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9173488>.
12. Johnson D. (2016). *Computer Systems: Moral entities but not moral agents. In: Ethics and Information Technology*, 8: 195-204 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-006-9111>.
13. Dubanov A. (2021). *Simulation of the trajectory of the pursuer in space with the method of parallel approach. Program systems and computational methods*, 2: 1-10 <https://doi.org/10.7256/2454-0714.2021.2.36014>.
14. Tikhanychev O. (2024). *Development of situational algorithms for the use of robotic systems. E3S Web of Conferences* 531, 02004 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202453102004>.
15. Kurdenkova E. O., Cherepnina M. S., Chistyakova A. S., Arkhipenko K. V. (2022). *Effect of transformations on the success of adversarial attacks for Clipped BagNet and ResNet image classifiers. Proceedings of the Institute for System Programming of the RAS*, 34(6): 101-116 [https://doi.org/10.15514/ISPRAS-2022-34\(6\)-7](https://doi.org/10.15514/ISPRAS-2022-34(6)-7).

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.30.61.170

UDK 631.354

研究审查的理论过程、其机械损伤和分离大豆种子组合的两年期评估研究
**STUDY THEORETICAL PROCESS OF REVIEW, ITS MECHANICAL
INJURIOUSNESS AND SEPARATION OF SOYA SEEDS COMBINE
OF THE BIENNIUM ASSESSMENT STUDY**

Prisyazhnaya Irina Mikhaelovna

PhD in Engineering Sciences, Associate Professor

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6598-9089

Prisyazhnaya Serafima Pavlovna

Grand PhD in Engineering Sciences, Professor

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6022-4159

All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Soybean

Blagoveshchensk, Russia

摘要: 由于播种面积的扩大, 阿穆尔地区大豆产量的增加已达到饱和, 因此, 有必要寻找并引进创新技术, 以获得高质量、高产的种子。研究表明, 大豆存在生物学差异——种子质量。形成较早的种子具有更高的生长能量、发芽率、产量和绝对重量。目前已开发出一种种子提取和收集技术 (申请号: 2018108674, 2018年1月12日), 该技术操作简便, 但劳动强度大, 且由于该地区播种的种子质量差、破损严重 (平均高达20%的种子为劣质种子), 需要对种子田收割机进行现代化改造。

关键词: 大豆, 收割, 收割机, 优质种子, 发芽率, 产量, 产出。

Abstract. *The increase in soybean production in the Amur region due to the expansion of sown areas has exhausted its possibilities, therefore, it is necessary to identify and introduce innovative technologies for obtaining high-quality and more productive seeds. It is established that soybeans have a biological difference — the quality of the seeds. Seeds, the formation of which begins earlier, have increased growth energy, germination, productivity, higher absolute weight. The technology for the extraction and collection of these seeds has been developed (application № . 2018108674 of 12 January 2018), is simple, labor-intensive and requires modernization of the harvester for harvesting seed plots, due to significant damage and poor quality of seeds sown in the region (on average, up to 20% sow substandard seeds).*

Keywords: *soya, harvesting, harvester, quality seeds, germination, productivity, yield.*

1. Introduction

Soybean grain is a solid, elastic-plastic heterogeneous body containing a number of organic and inorganic substances. The grain is covered with a dense rind (seed shell) that protects its inner part. The shell of soybeans is 7% of the weight of the whole grain and consists of three layers: palisade, hypodermic and nutrient tissue [1]. When creating new working bodies of transporting devices, it is necessary to choose the material, modes of operation, technological gaps, curvature of the working body, etc.. Indicators of each design element. In order that, without the risk of destroying or changing the shape of the grain, these working organs may resist the action of external forces transmitted to it from parts of the structure and mass of the grain being moved, and in the forceful interaction of the seeds with the working elements of the threshing and transporting devices, the grain must not be overloaded beyond its natural limits of strength. Failure to comply with this requirement leads to local or general destruction of seeds — their microdamage and fragmentation.

2. Methods

When harvesting, the soybean grain and its constituent parts — the cotyledons, the peel and the embryo perceive external loads and their effect is transmitted to each other. Distinguish between concentrated and distributed forces. The concentrated force is the pressure transmitted to the soybean grain through a platform whose dimensions are very small in relation to the entire grain. In the calculations, due to the smallness of the site transmitting the pressure, the concentrated force will be applied at the point.

Figure 1. — Soybean grain: where a is the thickness, c is the width, c is the length of soy:

1 — semi adults, 2 — shell, 3 — embryo

Deformations are divided: elastic and residual. Pressure deformations are formed until the magnitude of external forces on the part of the working organs of threshing and transporting devices has not exceeded the known limit at which the grain is destroyed. From the impact of the edge of the screw due to the friction force and the force of its own weight, the grain, touching the screw, receives an impulse of rotational and translational movement. Thus, in a pinched state, it rolls over the casing from the thickness position to the position of its width or length, but at the same time remaining in the gap of a certain size equal to the thickness of the grain. When compressed with rolling the soybean grain in the auger, it will experience pressure from the screw and housing. [1, 2, 3]

Figure 2. — (a, b, v, g) The forces and speed of movement of the particle when moving in the auger transporter

When the soybean grain is pinched between the screw and the housing in the moving auger, the resulting pressure on the soybean grain from the screw according to the theory of contact stresses exceeds the elasticity of the grain by about 50 or more times, so the soybean grain is intensively destroyed. The condition of pinching soybean grain in a screw transporter can be considered with the help of (fig. 3). If for a moment the grain is in a pinched state, will be stationary in the gap relative to the auger and housing, the sum of the projections of forces acting on the grain on the axis of OX , OY , OZ should be zero:

Figure 3.— Force acting on the soybean grain in the screw transporter

The auger has an active traumatic element — the edge of the screw. The theoretical performance of the screw transporter in general [4, 5, 6], [7, 12] can be written:

Table 1. Probability of jamming and mechanical damage soybean grains in a screw transporter

Value the gap	Probability of jamming damage			
	by thickness	by width	by length	Full probability
0,0052	0,0466	-	-	0,0466
0,0054	0,0924	-	-	0,0924
0,0056	0,1571	0,0252	-	0,1823
0,0058	0,2295	0,0499	-	0,2794
0,0006	0,2881	0,0984	-	0,3845
0,0062	0,3108	0,1660	0,0609	0,5377

Value the gap	Probability of jamming damage			
	by thickness	by width	by length	Full probability
0,0064	0,2881	0,2381	0,0863	0,6125
0,0066	0,2295	0,2734	0,1151	0,6180
0,0068	0,1571	0,2736	0,1616	0,5923
0,0070	0,0924	0,2734	0,1894	0,5552
0,0072	0,0466	0,2381	0,1915	0,4762
0,0074	-	0,1660	0,1894	0,3634
0,0078	-	0,0964	0,1616	0,2879
0,0080	-	0,0499	0,1151	0,2293
0,0082	-	0,0252	0,0863	0,1868
0,0084	-	-	0,0609	0,1151
0,0086	-	-	-	0,0863
0,0088	-	-	-	0,0609

3. Results

Studies have shown that in a horizontal auger with an increase in clearance between the screw and the casing from 1.0 to 7.0 mm, the amount of damage to the soybean grain increases and reaches, according to theoretical data, up to 2.9...3.0% with $D_{sh} = 0.16$ m, and almost up to 3.8...4.0%. Further increase in the gap between the housing and screw auger to 10...11 mm leads to a decrease in the amount of damage to the soybean grain. This phenomenon is explained by the fact that with an increase in the gap, the tightening and ingress of grain into the pinch decreases and the amount of grain destruction decreases.

Figure 4.— Change in the amount of damage to the soybean grain by the horizontal auger, depending on the gap between the auger screw and the housing

- 1 -Theoretical data;
- 2 — Experimental steel screw;
- 3 — Experimental polyethylene screw.

Analytical dependence shows that with an increase in the unit volume of portions of the transported soybean grain, the magnitude of damage decreases, so it is rational to use large-diameter screws in auger transporters, while somewhat reducing the speed of grain movement. The resulting dependence made it possible to make a monogram, using which it is possible to determine the value of the rational gap between the screw of the auger and the casing when moving seeds of different thicknesses.

Figure 5.— Monogram to determine the amount of damage to the soybean grain in the auger, depending on the gap between the screw and the casing, diameter, length and speed

The productivity of damage to the soybean grain by the screw conveyor is affected by the angle of inclination of the auger axis to the horizontal θ , the radius of the auger r , the angle of ascent of the screw line of the screw conveyor α , the

angular velocity ω_0 , the coefficients of grain friction on the materials of the working organs f_1 and f_2 the size of the gap Z between the screw and the screw housing. The use of a softer elastic polyethylene screw with a lower coefficient of friction as a structural material of the working body of the screw of the screw will reduce the degree of tightening, pinching and mechanical damage to the soybean, but the probability of damage remains.

Theoretical studies have established that in cases where the gap between the housing of the transporter and the outer edge of the screw will be larger than the size of the grain, the pinching of single grains clearly should not be. But when moving the mass of the grain, taking into account the forces of adhesion between the grains, pinching is possible... An increase in the gap by any value, even three times the size of a single grain according to [9, 10, 11] does not completely eliminate its pinching. Since between the movable working organ, the screw of the auger and the fixed casing, a “passive layer” of grain is created (fig. 6.) and the gap is reduced again to the size of the seed, which in turn contributes to the jamming between the active working organ and the casing through the grains themselves.

Figure 6. — “Passive layer” of soybean grain remaining in the serial auger transporter with a gap between the screw and the casing equal to 7-7.2 mm

The working bodies of the scraper transporter are scrapers. The movement of grain is due to the dragging of a portion by a scraper on the surface of the platform or chute, on which there are irregularities. The constructive execution of these working bodies does not exclude the pinching of grain. At the scraper transporter, the gap appears as a result of wear of the elastic rubberized part of the scraper. In addition, under the influence of the forces of resistance to the movement of soy, the scraper tends to deviate from a perpendicular position towards the movement of the traction organ. When a corner scraper is deflected Θ creates a condition for tightening the grain under an elastic rubberized scraper

gasket. Soybean caught under the frame due to friction forces is dragged along the bottom and as a result experiences the force of the framing pressure associated with the weight of the scraper. As a result, the grain will be destroyed if its strength is lower than the total level of action of these forces. The power effect of scraping on soybean grain can be considered with fig. 7 (a, b). We assume that in the pinched state, the grain is stationary for a moment in the gap relative to the scraper and chute, so the sum of the projections of the forces acting on the grain on the axis of the OX, OY should be zero.

Thus, according to the conducted theoretical analysis, it can be considered that the natural tightening of the grain in the gap between the scraper and the chute will be feasible in the event that $f_1 > \text{tg } \gamma$. The analysis of the process of pinching the grain with a scraper shows that the active traumatic element is the edge of the scraper. Given that the transporter scraper moves a portion of the grain and between the edge of the scraper and the chute can pinch and damage the grain.

Figure 7.— Forces acting on the grain during movement and at the time of pinching it in the scraper transporter

The obtained analytical dependencies show that with an increase in the unit volume of portions of the transported grain, the magnitude of damage decreases, therefore, it is rational to use volume scrapers in scraper transporters in accordance with the developed and received patents (№ . 2004469, № . 2038995) [8]. Among the wide variety of conveyors for moving bulk cargoes, tape conveyors are significantly common... The simplicity of the design, lower energy consumption compared to other transporters, the absence of loading and pinching devices, with rational loading, unloading and movement of grain, you can give preference to the use of a brush and tape transporter, which can ensure the movement of allocated in the combine harvester with biphasic threshing of biologically complete grain with almost no mechanical damage.

4. Conclusion:

The following conclusions can be drawn: the working organs of the combine do not equally produce a forceful effect on the grain in the process of breaking its connection with the leaflets of the beans and damage. Analyzing the work on damage to soybean seeds, the working bodies on the power activity of exposure are divided into two groups:

(a) working bodies responsible for the extraction of grain from straw heaps;

b) working bodies producing the division of grain from grain heap and its transportation. Studying this, we can assume that the first group accounts for more than 59% of the damaged grain to the total amount of damaged grain... That is, by the amount of damaged grain, the group of units of the harvester of the threshing and separation device is in the first place, and from this it follows that its constructive and technological reassessment is an urgent task. The desire to reduce grain damage in soy harvesting in different ways does not lead to a solution to the problem of obtaining high-quality seeds, since their biological diversity was not taken into account. Therefore, the problem of reducing injury to the grain should be solved inseparably with the problem of the release of biologically valuable soybean seeds when it is threshed.

References

1. *Sinegovskaya V. T., Prisyazhnaya I. M., Prisyazhnaya S. P. Soybean s Productivity and Sowing Quality of Seeds j§ Depending on the Peculiarities of Two-Stage z Combine Threshing. Zemledeliya. 2018. No. 6. P. 41-43 (in Russ.). DOI: 10.24411/0044- M 3913-2018-10611.*
2. *Aldoshin N. Methods of harvesting of mixed crops. Proceeding of 6th International Conference on Trends in Agricultural Engineering 2016. Part 1. Czech University of Life Sciences Prague. Faculty of Engineering. P. 26-32.*
3. *The system of agriculture of the Amur region / under a general edition of the Dr. of agricultural sciences, the prof. Tikhonchuk P. V. Blagoveshchensk: Publishing house of the Far East GAU, 2016. 570 p., (4) p., (1) l. card.*
4. *Influence of physical and mechanical properties of seeds of different soybean varieties on the degree of their injury / Y. V. Oborskaya, O. P. Ran // Modern technologies of production and processing of agricultural crops: Sat. scientific. Art. Scientific-practical conf. (with international participation), dedicated to the 105th anniversary of the birth of a breeder, Honored Agronomist of the Russian Federation, labor veteran T. P. Ryazantseva. Blagoveshchensk: VNII soybeans. 2017. P. 257-265.*

5. Iovlev G. A., Goldina I. I. *Review of tests of combine harvesters for the quality of the technological process of threshing grain crops: Russia, Belarus // Theory and practice of world science. 2017. № 11. P. 56-61.*
6. Оборская J. V., Ran O. P. *Effect of physical and mechanical properties of seeds of various soybean varieties on the degree of their injury // Modern technologies for the production and processing of crops: WEB. Blagoveshchensk: LLC "Typography", 2017. P. 257-265.*
7. Gievsky A. M., Chernyshov A. V., Maslov D. L., Migulnov V. Yu. *Justification of the operation mode of the threshing and separating device of the combine during soybean harvesting // Bulletin of Voronezh State Agrarian University. 2019. № 1 (60). P. 50-56.*
8. Prisyazhnaya I. M., Prisyazhnaya S. P. *Improving the process of harvesting soybeans to obtain seeds in the combine of two-phase threshing: monograph. FGBNU FNC VNII Soy Blagoveshchensk: LLC «Typography», 2024. 208 p.*
9. Prisyazhnaya I. M., Prisyazhnaya S. P., Sinegovskaya V. T. *Mathematical modeling of the process of threshing and separation of grain in a two-phase threshing device of the combine // Achievements of science and technology of the agro-industrial complex. 2018. T.32. № 7. P. 76-79.*
10. Prisyazhnaya I. M. *Development of technology for obtaining high-quality seeds in combine soybean harvesting / I. M. Prisyazhnaya, S. P. Prisyazhnaya, M. O. Sinegovskiy // Innovative research as a locomotive for the development of modern science: Sat. scientific. Art. XVI International Scientific and Practical Conference. M.: NIC MISI. 2019. P. 25-28.*
11. Prisyazhnaya I. M., Prisyazhnaya S. P., Lipkan A. V. [et al.] *Study of sowing qualities of soybean seeds in seed farms of Amur region // Journal of Agriculture and Environment. 2021. No 3(19). DOI 10.23649/jae.2021.3.19.4.*
12. Sinegovskiy M. O. *Prospects for soybean production in the Far Eastern Federal District//Bulletin of Russian Agricultural Science. 2020. № 1. P. 13-16.*

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.31.49.199

特殊类型信息收集与传输系统矩阵的分析模型

**ANALYTICAL MODELS OF MATRICES OF SPECIAL TYPES
OF INFORMATION COLLECTION AND TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS**

Panov Sergei Anatolevich

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor

Minzhesarova Sabina Aleksandrovna

Bachelor's degree in additional education

*K. G. Razumovsky Moscow State University of Technologies
and Management (the First Cossack University),*

Moscow, Russia

摘要：本文重点研究一种特殊矩阵的关键特征解析计算方法，该矩阵用于分析离散和数字数据传输信道中的概率指标。本文提出了可用于确定吞吐量、误码率以及n个符号中出现m个错误的概率的解析公式和算法。特别关注利用现代数学工具优化计算过程，从而显著提高信道特征估计的精度和速度。研究成果对致力于提高现代数据传输网络效率和鲁棒性的电信系统开发人员、信号处理工程师和信息论专家具有重要意义。

关键词：矩阵；托普利兹矩阵；循环矩阵；矩阵迹；矩阵行列式；对角矩阵；矩阵逆。

Annotation. *This article focuses on the development of methods for analytically calculating key characteristics of a special type of matrix used to analyze probability indicators in discrete and digital data transmission channels. The paper presents analytical formulas and algorithms that can be used to determine throughput, error probability, and the probability of m errors in n symbols. Particular attention is paid to optimizing computational procedures using modern mathematical tools, which significantly improves the accuracy and speed of channel characteristic estimation. The research results are relevant for telecommunications system developers, signal processing engineers, and information theory specialists seeking to improve the efficiency and resilience of modern data transmission networks.*

Keywords: *matrix; Toeplitz matrix; circulant matrix; trace of matrix; determinant of a matrix; diagonal matrix; inverse to matrix.*

Introduction

In distributed control systems, information collection and transmission systems are one of the elements that determines control quality. The transition to a digital economy increases the flow of transmitted information across various communication channels, and the amount of information transmitted in IoT systems significantly increases the load on digital channels.

As noted in [1], when transmitting data from various levels of the collection system to higher levels, factors such as channel loss, deterioration in transmission quality due to channel damage, and switching to a slower channel, such as a backup, cause delays in data transmission. The data transfer rate between collection system nodes depends on the physical medium of the communication lines, which can be both slow and fast, the quality of the lines, and the data transmission protocol.

Issues of mathematical modeling in the design of information collection and transmission systems are becoming increasingly important and require various adequate mathematical models and calculation expressions for calculating digital message delivery characteristics.

When studying digital information transmission systems and calculating message delivery indicators, it is often necessary to manipulate matrices and functions of matrices. This paper presents the results of a study of one type of matrix encountered when calculating the noise immunity characteristics of digital information transmission over degrading channels.

Construction of analytical expressions for matrices of a special type

Let us introduce the following notations:

$$A = (a_{ij}) = \begin{cases} a, & i = j, \\ b, & i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Special cases of matrix (1):

$$R = (r_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j, \\ r, & i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$R_I = \{1, \forall i, j\}. \quad (3)$$

$$K = \begin{cases} x + y, & i = j \\ x, & i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

And the matrix R_e

$$R_e = (r_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j, \\ |i - j| \\ r, & i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The identity matrix, which we will denote by I everywhere henceforth, and a general diagonal matrix:

$$D = (d_{ij}) = \begin{cases} d, & i = j, \\ 0, & i \neq j. \end{cases}$$

Zero avoid specifying each time, we assume that all matrices used are square and that multiplication is feasible. A matrix of the form (1) is given in [2]. In [3], a matrix of the form (4) is called «combinatorial.»

By definition, matrix (1) (and hence matrices (2-4)) is Toeplitz and circulant [4]. Consequently, it possesses the properties characteristic of this type of matrix. However, unlike [4], we are more interested in the analytical rather than the computational aspects of circulant matrix properties.

The value of the determinant for matrix (1) of dimension n is:

$$\det(A) = (a - b)^{n-1} (a + (n - 1)b). \quad (6)$$

A significant property of matrix (1), which follows from the properties of circulant matrices [4], is that its inverse has the same form, and its elements are calculated using the formulas from [2]:

$$A^{-1} \begin{cases} \frac{(a+(n-2)b)}{c}, & i = j, \\ -\frac{b}{c}, & i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where $c = (a + (n - 1)b)(a - b)$.

The trace of matrix (1) is:

$$T_r(A) = na$$

Matrix (3), which is singular and can be represented in the form, possesses a number of remarkable properties:

$$R_I = uu^T, \text{ где } u^T = (1 \dots 1). \quad (8a)$$

Property 1. The following relation holds for matrix B:

$$R_I B = (B R_I)^T \quad (8)$$

Proof. Equation (8) is proved by direct verification.

Property 2. The following relation holds for matrix B:

$$R_I B R_I = \sum_{\{i,j=1\}}^n b_{ij} R_i \quad (9)$$

Proof. Property 2 can be proved either by direct multiplication or using representation (8a), in which case:

$$R_I B R_I = u u^T B u u^T,$$

since: $u^T B u = \sum_{ij=1}^n b_{ij}$, then it follows from here (9).

Corollary 2.1. [5] If $B = R_I$, it follows from Property 2 that:

$$(R_I)^3 = n^2 R_I,$$

или в общем случае:

$$(R_I)^m = n^{m-1} R_I.$$

Property 3. If D is a diagonal matrix, then:

$$(I + R_I D) R_I = (z + 1) R_I \tag{10}$$

Proof.

$$(I + R_I D) R_I = (R_I + R_I D R_I),$$

and from Property 2 it follows that $R_I D R_I = z R_I$ where $z = \sum_{i=1}^n d_i$ and from this it follows that:

$$(I + R_I D) R_I = (z + 1) R_I$$

Theorem. Let in a non-singular matrix A (nxn) each of the columns (rows) be a linear combination, such that any element of the matrix has the form, then the determinant of such a matrix is calculated by the formula:

$$\det A = \sum_{\{J_k\}} (\prod_{i=1}^n \alpha_j^i) \det A_{J_k} \tag{11}$$

$j \in J_k, j = \{p, q\}$, где $\{J_n\}$ a set of vectors of length n, each of which defines a combination of elements p, q, a $\det A_{J_k}$ — is the determinant of the matrix in which, compared to matrix A, the columns have been replaced according to the vector J_k .

Proof. We prove (11) by induction. For $n = 1$, the formula is true. According to the theorem on the linearity of the determinant with respect to a column (row) [6], we have:

$$\det A = \alpha_p^1 \det A_{p_{ij}} + \alpha_q^1 \det A_{q_{ij}}$$

Assume that formula (11) is valid for $n-1$, and prove it for the case where n columns are linear combinations. Indeed, for the case where the number of modified columns (i.e., those that are linear combinations) in matrix A is $n-1$, we have:

$$\det A = \sum_{\{n-1\}} \left(\prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \alpha_j^i \right) \det A_{J_k}$$

However, for each matrix A_{jk} and their 2^{n-1} (поскольку число различных сочетаний m элементов (риц) из $n-1$ элементов равно $C_{n-1}^m \sum_{\{J_{n-1}\}} C_{n-1}^m = 2^{n-1}$ whose n -th column is a linear combination, by the theorem of linearity of the determinant with respect to a column, we have:

$$\det A_{jk} = \alpha_p^n \det A_{p_{nj}} + \alpha_q^n \det A_{q_{nj}}$$

and according to the combinatorial multiplication rule, the number of terms equals 2^n

Corollary 1. When $\alpha_p^i = \alpha_p$, $\alpha_q^i = \alpha_q$, from (11):

$$\det A = \sum_{\{i=0\}}^n C_n^i \alpha_p^{n-i} \alpha_q^i \det A_{n-i,i} \quad (12)$$

where $A_{n-i,i}$ — is the matrix in which, relative to A , $n-i$ columns have been replaced by the column vector p_j and i columns have been replaced by the column vector g_j .

When α_p and/or $\alpha_q = 1$, the corresponding formulas are easily obtained from (12).

Corollary 2. If the column vectors p_j and/or g_j have the form:

$$P_j = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j, \\ 0, & i \neq j \end{cases}$$

then in formula (12) we have, respectively, either the determinant of a matrix of size $n-i$ or of size i . The boundary conditions are: when $i = 0$ $\det A_i = I$ and when $i = n$ $\det A_{n-i} = I$.

When studying systems that use a non-zero decision threshold (erasure systems), it is necessary to find the determinant of the matrix:

$$G_k^*(I + zRW), \text{ где } W_k = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j, \\ 0, & i \neq j, \\ w_i, & 1 \text{ the column number, } i = j \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

i.e.

$$G_k^* = \begin{cases} zw + 1, & j = i = 1, \rightarrow g_{ii}^*, \\ z + 1, & i = j, \rightarrow g_{ii}, \\ zrw, & i \neq j, j = 1, \rightarrow g_{ij}^*, \\ zr, & i \neq j, \rightarrow g_{ij}. \end{cases}$$

Or, in other words, matrix G has k modified columns ($k=1, n$) replaced by w columns. Let us transform the elements on the diagonal of the modified columns as follows:

$$g_{ii}^* = w(g_{ii} - 1) + 1.$$

Тогда используя теорему и следствия 1,2 определить матрицы (13) запишется в виде:

$$\det(G_k^*) = \sum_{i=0}^k w^{k-1} \cdot \det(G_{h-i,k,i}) C_k^i, \tag{14}$$

Where $\det(G_{h-i,k,i})$ is the determinant of a matrix of dimension $n-i$ with $k-i$ modified diagonal elements equal to $g = 1$.

One of the corollaries of the theorem and expressions (12, 13) can be the computation of the determinant for the matrix:

$$G = (I + zR), \text{ or} \tag{14a}$$

$$G = (g_{ij}) = \begin{cases} z + 1, i = j, \\ zr, i \neq j, \\ z \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Matrix (14a) coincides with matrix (1) when $a = az+1$, $b = zr$, and although from (6) it is easy to obtain that

$$\det(G) = (z + 1 - zr)^{\{n-1\}}(z + 1 + (n - 1)zr),$$

at the same time, from (14):

$$\det(G) = \sum_{\{i=0\}}^n z^{n-i} C_n^i \det(R_{n-i}),$$

where $\det(R_{n-i})$ is the determinant of matrix (2) of dimension $(n-i)$, equal to:

$$\det(R_k) = (1 - r)^{\{k-1\}}(1 + (k - 1)r), \tag{15}$$

for $\det(R_0) = 1$,

Applying Corollary 2 yields final expressions for the determinants of matrices that have identical minors.

For matrix (5), this condition does not hold, but an approximate formula can be obtained under the assumption that the k -th order minor coincides with the k -th order matrix, then:

$$\det(I + \alpha R) = \det(I + RA),$$

where $A = (a... \alpha)$,

$$\det(I + RA) \cong \sum_{\{i=0\}}^n C_n^i \det(R_{n-i}) \alpha^{n-i}.$$

For matrix (5):

$$\det(R) = (1 - r^2)^{n-1}, \Pi$$

$$\det(I + RA) \cong \frac{(\alpha(1-v^2)+1)^n v^2}{1-v^2}, v^2 \neq 1 \tag{16}$$

The authors was unable to determine whether expression (16) represents any bound for the determinant of matrix (5).

Let us proceed to find the matrix inverse to matrix (1). From the properties of circulant matrices, it follows that the inverse matrix will also be circulant. This holds true for special cases of matrix (1) as well. For this purpose, we can use the identity [5]:

$$((1/z) * I + R_I) = zI - \frac{z^2}{1+nz} R_I \tag{17}$$

To use (17), we transform matrix A as follows:

$$A = (bR_I + (a - b)I)$$

Then, it is quite straightforward to obtain the required expression. Applying formula (17) to find the inverse matrix G_k^w is impossible, and before proceeding to find it, we will present a number of useful relations.

$$(B + uv^T) = B^{-1} - \frac{B^{-1}uv^T B^{-1}}{1+v^T B^{-1}u} [10]. \tag{18}$$

where $v^T = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ $u = \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ \cdot \\ u_n \end{pmatrix}$. Since $R^I = uu^T$ then:

$$(B + R_I) = B^{-1} - \frac{B^{-1}R_I B^{-1}}{1+u^T B^{-1}u} \tag{19}$$

obviously:

$$u^T B^{-1} u = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n b_{ij}^{-1}.$$

If B is a non-singular diagonal matrix, i. e., $B = D$, then in (19):

$$D^{-1}R_I D^{-1} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{d_i^2}, i = j, \\ \frac{1}{d_j}, i \neq j, \end{cases}$$

and then:

$$(D + R_I) = (g_{ij}^{-1}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{d_i} - \frac{\frac{1}{d_i^2}}{1+\sum_i \frac{1}{d_i}}, i = j \\ \frac{-1/d_i d_j}{1+\sum_i 1/d_i}, i \neq j. \end{cases} \tag{20}$$

Similarly, for:

$$((1/z)D + R_I) = zD^{-1} - \frac{z^2 D^{-1} R_I D^{-1}}{1 + z \sum_i 1/d_i} \tag{21}$$

$$g_{ii}^{-1} = \frac{z}{g_i} - \frac{z^2/d_i^2}{1 + z \sum_i 1/d_i},$$

$$g_{ij}^{-1} = -\frac{z^2/d_i d_j}{1 + z \sum_i 1/d_i}$$

Formula (21) is a generalization of formula (17). Now, for matrix (13), written in the form:

$$G = (I + z R_I W) = ((1/z)W^{-1} + R_I)zW.$$

From (21), it is easy to obtain:

$$G^{-1} = \frac{1}{z}W^{-1} \left(zW - \frac{z^2 W R_I W}{1 + z \sum_i w_i} \right) = I - \frac{z R_I W}{1 + z \sum_i w_i}, \tag{22}$$

$$g_{ii}^{-1} = 1 - \frac{z w_i}{1 + z \sum_i w_i},$$

$$g_{ij}^{-1} = -\frac{z w_i}{1 + z \sum_i w_i}.$$

For matrix (2), in order to apply formula (19), we transform it as follows:

$$R = rR + (1 - r)I$$

Then:

$$G = (I + (z r R + z(1 - r)I)W)$$

Let us denote:

$$D = I + z(1 - r)W,$$

$$d_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 + z(1 - r)w_i, & i = j \\ 0, & i \neq j \end{cases}$$

Let us transform matrix G into the form (21):

$$G = \left(\frac{1}{zr} D W^{-1} + R_I \right) zrW$$

Introduce the notation: $a = zr$, $DW = F$ then, applying (21), we have:

$$G^{-1} = W^{-1}F^{-1} - \frac{\alpha W^{-1}F^{-1}R_1F^{-1}}{1 + \alpha \sum_i 1/f_i}$$

Substituting the notations, we obtain:

$$G^{-1} = D^{-1} - \frac{\alpha D^{-1}R_1WD^{-1}}{1 + \alpha \sum_i 1/f_i} \quad (23)$$

$$g_{ii}^{-1} = \frac{1}{z(1-r)w + 1} - \frac{zrw_i(z(1-r)w_i + z)^2}{1 + zr \sum_i \frac{w_i}{z(1-r)w_i + 1}}$$

$$g_{ij}^{-1} = - \frac{zrw_i / [(z(1-r)w_i + 1)(z(1-r)w_j + 1)]}{1 + zr \sum_i w_i / (z(1-r)w_i + 1)}$$

When $w = 1, i = 1$ we obtain expression (7) with $a = z + 1, b = zr$

The derived expressions (21-23) enable the computation of probabilistic characteristics of discrete channels with correlation properties described by matrix (1) and its special cases, for channels with fading signals and interference.

Conclusion

The obtained analytical expressions for matrix operations and matrix characteristics allow us to calculate probability indicators for receiving digital information in industrial network channels.

References

1. Polovnikov, M. S. *Adaptive algorithm for transmitting operational data via digital communication channels* / M. S. Polovnikov, V. I. Ukhov // *Automation in industry*. — 2015. — No. 8. — P. 60-63. — EDN VJNKSD.
2. Rao C. R. *Linear Statistical Methods and Their Applications*. — Moscow: Nauka, 1968. — 547 p.
3. Knuth D. E. *The Art of Computer Programming. Vol. 1*.
4. Voevodin V. V., Tyrtshnikov E. E. *Computational Processes with Toeplitz Matrices*. — Moscow: Nauka, 1987. — 320 p.
5. Panov S. A. *Results of the Analysis of Two System Criteria for the Quality of Discrete Message Transmission* // *System Modeling*. — Novosibirsk, 1984. — pp. 128-134.
6. Bolshakov I. A. *Extraction of Signal Streams from Noise*. — Moscow: Sovetskoye Radio, 1969. — 464 p.

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.31.56.178

基于深度学习的道路交通标志检测与识别研究
**RESEARCH ON DEEP LEARNING-BASED ROAD TRAFFIC SIGN
DETECTION AND RECOGNITION**

Hajiyev Haji Fakhraddin*Doctoral student**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan*

摘要：本文探讨了机器学习算法在道路交通标志检测与识别任务中的应用。研究指出了传统图像处理方法的不足，以及机器学习（特别是深度学习模型）在提高复杂交通环境下的准确性和鲁棒性方面的优势。文章认为，卷积神经网络等算法在实时交通系统和智能驾驶辅助系统中发挥着重要作用。机器学习被强调为提升道路安全和推进智能交通系统应用的关键技术之一。

关键词：交通标志识别，机器学习，深度学习，计算机视觉，智能交通系统

Abstract. *This article discusses the use of machine learning algorithms to apply towards the road traffic sign detection and recognition task. The study notes the downsides of the traditional approach to image processing and the benefits of machine learning and specifically deep learning models in enhancing the accuracy and robustness in the presence of complex traffic conditions. It is argued that algorithms like convolutional neural networks have a huge role to play in real-time traffic systems as well as intelligent driver assistant systems. Machine learning is highlighted as an important part of the technology that will be used to improve road safety and to advance the use of intelligent transportation systems.*

Keywords: *traffic sign recognition, machine learning, deep learning, computer vision, intelligent transportation systems*

In the twenty-first century, with the fast development of the intelligent transportation system, there is a huge demand for reliable and automated traffic perceiving technologies. Among these technologies, road traffic sign detection and recognition play an important role in the promotion of road safety, the efficiency of road traffic and the assistance of smart driving technology or even driverless driving technology. Traffic signs generate important parts of information about speed limits, warnings, prohibitions, and regulations of roads and their correct interpretation is of key importance to the human drivers and the intelligent vehicles. Traditional

traffic sign recognition methods mostly depended on the rule-based image processing algorithms such as color thresholding, edge detection, shape analysis, and handcraft feature extraction [5]. Although they proved to be of limited use in controlled settings, in real world settings with all the other conditions of varying illumination, weather conditions, octantions, motion non, background clutter and sign disuse these methods often failed. As a consequence, the limitations in the conventional approaches have triggered the usage of machine learning and data driven methodologies.

This thesis is dedicated to the use of machine learning algorithms used for the road traffic signs detection and recognition focusing on their superiority over the traditional methods in terms of: accuracy, robustness and adaptability. It states that methods based on machine learning represent a new way of believing objects in the traffic signs at the same time as smart systems can directly be taught of complicated visual patterns in an self-teaching data and can generalize how it could be driven. Traffic sign detection and recognition can be set as a machine learning problem with several stages of object localization, feature representation and classification. Detection is the problem of detecting the presence and position of the traffic sign in an image or a frame of the video, whereas recognition is detecting the sign in input image, and categorizing it in predefined set [2].

In the theory of machine learning, this problem is typically being solved using supervised learning: the models are trained using a dataset of already labeled images of traffic signs. The success of such systems depends on the quality of the training data, the feature extraction techniques, the model architecture and the optimization techniques. Unlike the traditional pipelines in which the features are manually designed, machine learning and deep learning in particular allows automatic feature learning which greatly improves the recognition performance. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been the most popular model for the recognition of traffic signs since their ability to capture the spatial hierarchies and visual invariable. CNN based models learn low level features such as edges and textures and high level semantic representations automatically, and hence, can be very suitable for a visual classification task in a complex traffic environment.

Popular modern day traffic sign detection systems are based on machine learning based object detection frameworks. Algorithms such as Faster R-CNN, You Only Look Once(Yolo) and Single Shot MultiBox Detector(SSD) have been widely used for localization of traffic signs in real time [3]. These models bring region proposal architectures, feature extraction architectures, and classification architectures in unison and efficient and accurate detection. Compared with traditional sliding window methods, deep learning-based detectors are much less complex in terms of computation, while better in detection quality. They are able to deal with the problem of scale variations, partial occlusions and different backgrounds which is common

for real world road scenes. Moreover, the process of transfer learning means that these models can share the pre-trained weights of models that have already been trained on large-scale datasets, this reduces the time it takes to train the model as well as improving generalisation of the model. Despite their advantages, models for detection are faced with challenges on small object detection because of the limited amount of traffic signs that fill small pixels in high-resolution images. This is a problem that involves architectural improvements, multi-scale feature fusion and data augmentation methods.

Once a traffic sign is recognized, the recognition problem is reduced to a classification problem. CNN based classifiers have performed close to humans on benchmark datasets such as German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (GTSRB), LISA Traffic Sign Dataset. Advanced architectures such as residual network and lightweight models have been used in order to find the balance between accuracy and efficiency. In recent studies, hybrid methods of CNN and ensemble and attention mechanism are further improved the robustness of the classification. These methods enhance the capability of the model to pay attention to the discriminative area of the traffic signs and ignore the irrelevant information of the background area. Additionally, data augmentation measures such as rotation, scaling and light illumination changes have also been found useful in making models more resilient to different environmental conditions [1].

Despite that there has been great progress in this direction; there are some challenges still in mind during applying machine learning algorithms to traffic sign detection and recognition. One major problem is the inconsistency of the standards of the traffic signs in different countries and regions, limiting generalization of the models which are trained using the region-specific datasets. Furthermore, different traffic signs occur significantly less times than others, a problem referred to as class imbalance, which can decrease the performance of classification. Real-time processing constraints is also a problem, especially for embedded systems for use in vehicles. High computational needs of deep learning models call for optimization approaches such as model compression, quantization and light-weight architectures. Additionally, ensuring of robustness under adverse conditions — including night-time driving, fog, rain and damaged signs — is still an area of ongoing research [4].

The scientific contribution of this thesis is that the process of detecting and recognizing traffic signs are considered as an integral learning system instead of much separated algorithmic components. By concentrating on the interaction between the stages of detection, feature learning stages and classification stages, the study demonstrates the pivotal importance of end-to-end optimization for real world application. Furthermore, the thesis focuses on the use of adaptive learning strategies and data-sets of a specific domain for increasing the robustness of a system. From a practical point of view machine learning based traffic signs recognition systems

have direct contributions to road safety issues, which includes: reduce human error, increase awareness of drivers and enable autonomous decision-making. These systems are one of the basic part of smart transportation systems and major component in the development of sustainable and smart mobility solutions.

Machine learning algorithms have brought a revolutionary change in the discipline of the road traffic signs detect and recognition. By breaking the inaccuracy, reluctance, unsuitability and other limitations of traditional image processing technology, the accuracy, adaptability and scalability in complex traffic scenarios of learning-based learning technology are higher [6]. While there are still some challenges in terms of the diversity of data, efficiency of computation and robustness in the real world, as machine learning methods continue to advance, its performance is projected to continue improving. The use of ML algorithms in the detection and recognition of traffic signs are not only a technological breakthrough but an important strategic requirement for better road safety and the future of intelligent transportation systems.

References

1. Møgelmoose, A., Trivedi, M. M., & Moeslund, T. B. (2012). *Vision-based traffic sign detection and analysis for intelligent driver assistance systems: Perspectives and survey*. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 13(4), 1484-1497.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2012.2209421>
2. Stallkamp, J., Schlipsing, M., Salmen, J., & Igel, C. (2012). *Man vs. computer: Benchmarking machine learning algorithms for traffic sign recognition*. *Neural Networks*, 32, 323-332.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2012.02.016>
3. Cireşan, D. C., Meier, U., Masci, J., & Schmidhuber, J. (2012). *Multi-column deep neural network for traffic sign classification*. *Neural Networks*, 32, 333-338.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2012.02.023>
4. Zhu, Z., Liang, D., Zhang, S., Huang, X., Li, B., & Hu, S. (2016). *Traffic-sign detection and classification in the wild*. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2110-2118.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.232>
5. Sermanet, P., & LeCun, Y. (2011). *Traffic sign recognition with multi-scale convolutional networks*. *International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 2809-2813. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2011.6033589>
6. Redmon, J., Divvala, S., Girshick, R., & Farhadi, A. (2016). *You Only Look Once: Unified, real-time object detection*. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 779-788.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.91>

DOI 10.34660/INF.2026.32.58.082

所研制酸液组合物对碳酸盐岩储层井底深层增产的有效性
**EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DEVELOPED ACID COMPOSITION
FOR DEEP STIMULATION OF THE BOTTOMHOLE ZONE
IN CARBONATE RESERVOIRS**

Baturin Nikita Igorevich*Engineer of the 1st Category**Tatar Research and Design Institute of Oil***Fattakhov Irik Galikhanovich***Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor, Director of Enhanced Oil**Recovery, Wave and Biotechnology**Tatar Research and Design Institute of Oil*

摘要：本研究考察了一种先前开发的用于碳酸盐岩油藏近井区深层处理的酸液配方。该酸液配方与石油生产相关，专为碳酸盐岩油藏近井区酸化处理而设计，可用于化学溶解阻碍油气和凝析气藏近井区的岩石和沉积物。它还可用作碳酸盐岩地层射孔和水力压裂过程中的工艺液。应用该酸液配方可显著提高碳酸盐岩油藏油田在各种地质和物理条件下的油井产能，从而带来显著的技术经济优势。基于对大量油井产能动态定量指标变化的数据集进行统计分析，研究结果表明，在碳酸盐岩油藏近井区深层酸化处理过程中使用该酸液配方后，油井产能动态指标得到了显著提升。

关键词：酸液组成、深部增产、油藏近井区、碳酸盐岩油藏、平均增产幅度、应用效果

Abstract. *This study examines a previously developed acid composition intended for deep treatment of the near-wellbore zone in carbonate reservoirs. This acid composition, related to oil production and designed for acid treatment of the near-wellbore zone in carbonate reservoirs, can be used for the chemical dissolution of rock and deposits obstructing the near-wellbore zone of oil, gas, and gas condensate reservoirs. It can also be employed as a technological fluid during perforation and hydraulic fracturing of carbonate formations. This provides a significant techno-economic advantage from the application of the developed acid composition to enhance the productivity of wells operating under various geological and physical conditions of carbonate reservoir fields. Based on the statistical analysis of an extensive dataset on changes in quantitative indicators of well performance dynamics before and after the use of the specified acid composition*

during deep acid treatment of near-wellbore zones in carbonate formations, the authors have demonstrated an increase in the efficiency of reservoir and deposit development of carbonate reservoirs at various fields.

Keywords: *acid composition, deep stimulation, near-wellbore zone of the reservoir, carbonate reservoir, average increment, effectiveness of application*

Based on the review of materials from several informational reports on the provision of scientific-technical and geological-technical services, it can be concluded that to achieve the maximum effective impact on the near-wellbore zone of the productive carbonate reservoir formation, the following conditions must be met collectively: uniform impact along the entire effective length of the treatment interval; High-quality contact of active acid compositions with the rock surface; Deep penetration of the active acid composition into the rock. Due to the limited development of integrated methodologies and modeling tools for processes occurring in the near-wellbore zone of the reservoir (NWZR), it is necessary to enhance the technological efficiency of various types of well stimulation operations using acid treatment.

Acid treatment of the NWZR is an effective method for cleaning the productive formation from various contaminants. These contaminants may form in the near-wellbore area during drilling, casing cementing, or oil and gas production. One such treatment is deep penetrating stimulation of the bottomhole zone (BHZ), which delivers a prolonged deep-acting effect by dissolving components of the carbonate reservoir, thereby increasing the filtration area and redistributing the acid composition flow throughout the thickness and depth of the perforation zone. The distinguishing features of deep-penetrating BHZ treatments are:

- the use of reaction rate retarders that enable redistribution of acid composition flow throughout the entire thickness and into the depth of the BHZ;
- the use of solvents and diverters that modify the rheology of the fluid formed as a result of the acid composition reacting with the rock;
- the possibility of cyclic injection with increased penetration depth and higher injection volumes;
- the average calculated skin factor after deep-penetrating BHZ treatment is below -1 .

Deep-penetrating BHZ are classified as high-technology BHZ due to the increased demands on preparation, personnel qualifications, equipment, as well as on technological injection regimes.

The technical effect of the acid composition under consideration was achieved by formulating an active composition for deep-penetrating BHZ of carbonate formations, containing 50% synthetic hydrochloric acid at 12% concentration, 1.5% iron stabilizer, 1.5% water-soluble demulsifier, 1.5% surfactant, 2.0% acid

corrosion inhibitor, and 43.5% fresh technical water. This acid composition is used in the technologies of deep stimulation of BHZ in carbonate reservoir formations in oil and gas wells of various fields [1]. Figures 1-3 present the actual results of changes in the average values of oil production, liquid production, and well water cut, respectively, during the first three months, the last three months, and the entire period following the application of the considered acid composition in technologies for deep stimulation of BHZ in carbonate reservoir formations.

Figure 1 — Changes in average oil production at wells after BHZ

Figure 2 — Changes in average liquid production at wells after BHZ

Figure 3 — Changes in average water cut at wells after BHZ

Based on the data presented in Figures № 1–№ 3, the following can be observed:

— the acid composition under consideration was applied in deep-penetrating BHZ treatment technologies in 23 oil-producing wells across various oil and gas fields of the company;

— oil production over the entire period following the application of the evaluated acid composition in deep stimulation BHZ technologies of carbonate reservoirs increased in 20 out of 23 wells, corresponding to an effectiveness of 86.95 %;

— fluid production over the entire period following the application of the evaluated acid composition in deep stimulation BHZ technologies of carbonate reservoirs increased in 19 out of 23 wells, corresponding to an effectiveness of 82.61 %;

— the water-cut of wells throughout the entire period following the application of the considered acid composition in deep stimulation technologies of BHZ in carbonate reservoir formations decreased in 6 out of 23 wells, i.e., the effectiveness of this acid composition was 26.09 %.

Figure 4 — Specific oil production at wells before and after deep BHZ stimulation

Figures 4-6 show the actual values of oil-specific production, fluid-specific production, and water-cut in wells for 3 months before and 12 months after the application of the considered acid composition in deep stimulation technologies of BHZ in carbonate reservoir formations.

Figure 5 — Specific fluid production at wells before and after deep BHZ stimulation

Figure 6 — Specific water cut of wells before and after deep BHZ stimulation

Figure 7 — Average increase in oil and liquid production in wells after deep stimulation of the BHZ

Figure 8 — Average increase in water cut and productivity index of wells after deep stimulation of the BHZ

The data presented in Figures No. 4 to 6 show that:

— the average specific oil production at wells before deep BHZ stimulation was 2.295 t/day, and after deep BHZ stimulation increased to 3.504 t/day (a rise of 52.68%);

— the average specific fluid production in wells before conducting deep BHZ treatment was 2.756 t/day, and after conducting deep BHZ treatment, it was 4.493 t/day (an increase of 63.03 %);

— the average specific water cut of wells before conducting deep BHZ treatment was 14.083 %, and after conducting deep BHZ treatment, it was 17.377 % (an increase of 3.294 %).

Figures 7-8 present the average increases in such parameters as oil production, fluid production, water cut, and productivity index following the application of the considered acid composition in deep BHZ treatment technologies for carbonate reservoir formations.

Based on the data presented in Figures № 7 and № 8, it can be concluded that:

— the average increase in oil production in wells after deep stimulation of the BHZ is 1.185 t/(day·month);

— the average increase in liquid production in wells after deep stimulation of the BHZ is 1.721 t/(day·month);

— the average increase in well water cut after conducting deep-penetrating BHZ treatment is 3.279%/month;

— the average increase in the well productivity index after conducting deep-penetrating BHZ treatment is 0.076 t/(day·atm·month).

Additional oil production from effective wells amounts to 10,792.43 tons, and including ineffective wells, 10,331.03 tons. From all the data presented above, it can be concluded that the considered acid composition is effective when applied in technologies for deep-penetrating BHZ treatments of carbonate reservoir formations, as the majority of wells (82.61 %) demonstrate maximum productivity, maximum intensification of target layers, and minimization of dispersion. The application of the considered acid composition in technologies for deep stimulation of the BHZ in carbonate reservoir formations was carried out based on acid treatment modeling results, during which optional adjustments to the model and graphical representation of the simulation process were made, aiming to calculate the optimal projected technical and economic efficiency.

The optimized acid composition, designed for deep treatment of the bottom-hole zone in carbonate reservoirs, possesses the following set of properties:

— promotes the formation of new channels in the porous structure of the formation, thereby increasing the contact area of the acid composition with the rock;

— ensures effective removal of the finest particles and chemical reaction products during flushing and commissioning operations following acid treatment;

— enhances the interaction between the acid solution components and the surface of the treated rock;

— broadens the applicability of the acid composition for treating carbonate rocks in both porous and fractured reservoirs by enabling control over the reaction rate;

— extends the service life of well equipment.

References

1. Pat. 2824107 Russian Federation, IPC C09K 8/74. Acid composition for treatment of the near-wellbore zone of a carbonate reservoir / Dmitrieva A. Yu., Baturin N. I., Abusalimov E. M., Ilyin A. Yu., Akhmetshin F. A.; Applicant and patent holder Public Joint Stock Company "Tatneft" named after V. D. Shashin. — No. 2024104908; filed 27.02.2024; Published: 06.08.2024, Bull. No. 22. — 11 p.

科学出版物

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

国际科学大会的材料

2026年02月11日，中华人民共和国北京

编辑A. A. Siliverstova

校正A. I. 尼古拉耶夫

2026年02月11日，中华人民共和国北京
USL。沸点：98.7。 订单253. 流通500份。

在编辑和出版中心印制
无限出版社

